

STAR FORMATION IN AND AROUND NEARBY GALAXIES

A Thesis

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Dedicated to Shobha

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Declaration

This thesis is a presentation of my original research work. Wherever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due reference to the literature, and acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions.

The work was done under the guidance of Yogesh Wadadekar, at the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Mumbai.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Omkar Bait', written on a light-colored rectangular background.

(Omkar Bait)

In my capacity as supervisor of the candidate's thesis, I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Yogesh Wadadekar', written on a light-colored rectangular background.

(Yogesh Wadadekar)

Date: 30th August, 2019

Abstract

Galaxy formation and evolution is one of the most active areas of research in astronomy. In recent times there have been several developments on the observational fronts particularly with the discovery of several relations between galaxy physical properties. The exact details of how they come about still remains to be understood. Such a development has been primarily possible due to a deluge of multi-wavelength data ranging from the ultra-violet (UV) to the radio, mainly due to wide field surveys e.g., the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) in the optical. This thesis makes use of these multi-wavelength (UV to radio) data to study galaxies with the main focus on star formation (SF) and quenching. It is divided in two parts: SF and quenching within galaxies and on SF, ionized gas and neutral gas in galaxy outskirts.

What drives galaxy evolution in massive galaxies? We do this by studying the inter-correlation between galaxy morphology, SF and environment in the nearby Universe. However, most of the studies on SF in galaxies rely on standard scaling relations between star formation rate (SFR) and observed properties such as ultra-violet or $H\alpha$ luminosity to estimate the SFR which in principle can vary between galaxies. To probe the limits of such relations we use an extremely low-mass, compact and starbursting population of galaxies as laboratories to compare SFR estimated using different relations, particularly those using the radio continuum and optical emission lines. Although on large spatial scales, and for a large statistical sample, galaxy formation and evolution can be studied using several scaling relations, detailed resolved studies of galaxies, particularly with gas, show that galaxy evolution can be very complicated. We then shift the focus to the galaxy outskirts. Here, we study two scenarios, involving the presence of

large amounts of ionized and neutral gas around galaxies using the SDSS IV Mapping Nearby Galaxies at Apache point observatory (MaNGA) Integral Field Unit (IFU) survey and with the Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT) respectively. I will describe the two parts of this thesis in the following.

Galaxies in the local Universe show a bi-modal distribution on the optical color-magnitude diagram (Baldry et al., 2004; Strateva et al., 2001) with actively star forming “blue cloud” galaxies and passively evolving “red sequence” galaxies. The region between these two populations is defined as the “green valley” (Wyder et al., 2007a). It is thought to be a transition zone between the blue cloud and the red sequence (Wyder et al., 2007a). Thus, green valley galaxies can give us insight into the process of quenching and its dependence on morphology and other galaxy parameters. Moreover, it well known that the various galaxy properties e.g., morphologies, stellar mass, gas properties and environment show correlations with each other. And it is not clear which of these are fundamental.

Among these parameters, galaxy morphology remains the most difficult to quantify. This is because, finding the visual morphologies of millions of galaxies from large scale galaxy surveys is difficult. Hence, several recent studies on star formation have mostly ignored the morphologies of galaxies. Galaxy Zoo (Lintott et al., 2008) has classified the morphologies of a large number of galaxies, but gives a crude classification in terms of only late-type (which includes all types of spiral galaxies) and early-type (ellipticals and S0s) galaxies. On the contrary, in our study we use the detailed visual morphologies (in 12 types – ellipticals, S0-, S0, S0/a, Sa, Sab, Sb, Sbc, Sc, Scd, Sd, Sdm, Im) from the Nair & Abraham (2010a, NA10 hereafter) catalogue, and hence we can distinguish between different kinds of spiral galaxies. We can also differentiate between ellipticals and S0s which the Galaxy Zoo morphologies do not.

Here we want to revisit the relation between classical visual morphologies and star formation in the modern context of the MS of star-forming galaxies, the transitioning population of green valley galaxies, and the quenched

galaxies, and also as a function of environment from the low to high densities. In particular, we want to study the relation between the specific SFR (sSFR)-morphology, morphology-density, and density-sSFR. Since all three of the parameters, morphological T-type, sSFR, and environmental density are known to correlate with each other, in each of the correlations we also study the differential effect of the third parameter.

Our sample is drawn from the NA10 catalogue of detailed visual morphological classification of 14,034 galaxies. NA10 galaxies were selected from the SDSS DR4 with spectroscopic redshift in the range $0.01 < z < 0.1$, and extinction corrected apparent magnitude limit of $g < 16$ mag. For galaxies in our sample, we use optical imaging data from the SDSS DR12 (Alam et al., 2015) in u, g, r, i , and z bands. In order to have a better constraint on recent star formation, we make use of Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX) data in the far-UV (FUV) and near-UV (NUV) filters. We use near-IR model photometry from the 2 Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS) in J, H , & K bands (Skrutskie et al., 2006). Mid IR data are taken from the Wide-Field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE; Wright et al. (2010)) in all four channels - W1, W2, W3, and W4. We construct our sample by cross-matching the NA10 catalogue (after removing the Sdm and Im galaxies) with archival data from GALEX, SDSS, 2MASS, and WISE which gives us 7763 galaxies. For each of the galaxies in our sample, we model the SED, using the publicly available Multi-wavelength Analysis of Galaxy Physical Properties (MAGPHYS) code (da Cunha et al., 2008, dC08 hereafter) in 14 bands. We select good fits by putting a critical $\chi^2 < 5$ (Hayward & Smith, 2015). We further restrict ourselves to only high mass galaxies ($> 10^{10}M_{\odot}$) which gives us a final sample of 6194 galaxies. We use the median values of stellar mass and SFR for each galaxy in our sample following dC08. For all of these galaxies, we also have local environmental density information from Baldry et al. (2006).

Using multi-wavelength data, from UV-optical-near-mid IR, for ~ 6000 galaxies in the local Universe, we study the dependence of star formation on the morphological T-types for massive galaxies ($\log M_*/M_{\odot} \geq 10$). We

study the fraction of late-type spirals (LTS), early-type spirals (ETS), S0s, and ellipticals (Es) in bins of log specific star-formation rate (sSFR). Interestingly we find that the trends for different morphological types are quite different. We find that, early-type spirals (Sa-Sbc) and S0s predominate in the green valley (defined from [Salim, 2014](#)), which is a transition zone between the star forming and quenched regions. When we do a finer differentiation within the early-type spirals, i.e. as we move from Sa to Sbc spirals, the fraction of green valley and quenched galaxies decreases, indicating the important role of the bulge in the quenching of galaxies. The fraction of early-type spirals decreases as we enter the green valley from the blue cloud, which coincides with the increase in the fraction of S0s. This points towards the morphological transformation of early-type spiral galaxies into S0s which can happen due to environmental effects such as ram-pressure stripping, galaxy harassment, or tidal interactions. We also find a second population of S0s which are actively star-forming and are present in all environments. We also find that such a relation between the morphology and star-forming state does not change in different environmental bins. We also studied in detail the other two combinations, i.e. fraction of star-forming/quenched/green-valley galaxies in a fixed environmental bin and fraction of ETS, LTS, S0s and Es in fixed environmental bins. We find that in all the correlations, the correlation between sSFR and morphology is the strongest. We also computed the partial correlation coefficient for each pair of parameters (morphological T-type, sSFR and environmental density) while keeping the third parameter as a control variable. Yet, again we find that morphology most strongly correlates with sSFR, independent of the environment, while the other two correlations (morphology-density and sSFR-environment) are weaker. Thus, we conclude that, for massive galaxies in the local Universe, the physical processes that shape their morphology are also the ones that determine their star-forming state.

There is now an overwhelming amount of evidence which suggests that the neutral Universe underwent a phase transition and was reionized by $z \sim 6$ (see e.g., [Becker et al., 2001](#)). However, the nature of sources (star-forming galaxies or Active galactic nuclei (AGN)) which contributed to this

transition is still under debate. It is widely believed that star-formation (SF) plays the major role in providing the ionizing photons required for fully ionizing the Universe (Barkana & Loeb, 2001). Several observations and simulation suggest that a significant fraction may be contributed by the low mass starburst galaxies (e.g., Dressler et al., 2015), a subset of which could be Lyman- α emitters (LAEs).

It is very difficult to do a detailed multi-wavelength study of these faint high- z galaxies due to sensitivity limitations of the current generation telescopes and hence it is useful to search for their local analogues. Currently, the best low- z candidates for such galaxies are the bright green and compact (typically ≤ 5 kpc) galaxies termed as “green peas” (GPs; Cardamone et al., 2009) discovered by the volunteers from the Galaxy Zoo project. These galaxies have high SFRs, relatively low stellar masses ($\sim 10^{9-10} M_{\odot}$), low metallicities, compact sizes (typically ≤ 5 kpc), very high [OIII]/[OII] ratios (e.g., Jaskot & Oey, 2013) and bright green color in SDSS images due to the large [OIII] λ 5007 Å equivalent width (EW). Such compact star-forming galaxies are also known to leak a significant amount of Ly- α continuum photons (Izotov et al., 2016). Yang et al. (2017) have recently searched for the low redshift counterparts ($z < 0.05$) of green pea galaxies in the SDSS *ugriz* broadband images. This gives them the sensitivity to probe the fainter (and hence lower stellar mass and metallicity) counterparts of green peas. They have found a sample of extremely starbursting dwarf galaxies with even smaller sizes (≤ 1 kpc), lower stellar masses, low metallicities, termed as “Blueberry” (BB) galaxies (Yang et al., 2017). These are also supposed to be the local analogs of the high- z faint Lyman- α emitters (Yang et al., 2017).

A complementary study of this peculiar population of galaxies at radio frequencies can provide an independent estimate of their total (dust-obscured and unobscured) SFRs (e.g., Condon, 1992). Radio emission from high redshift ($z \sim 3 - 4$) Lyman-break galaxies (LBGs) has been reported only by stacking analysis, (e.g., Carilli et al., 2008). This stacked radio luminosity was also found to be systematically lower than those expected from the

ultra-violet (UV) luminosity (Carilli et al., 2008). However, for such galaxies, it is hard to separate the effect of an increased inverse Compton (IC) cooling of the relativistic electrons due to scattering from cosmic microwave background (CMB) photons versus an intrinsic deficit. The local analogues of LBGs and LAEs will have a negligible amount of IC-CMB losses and are also easier to detect. However, in a previous study only two green peas were directly detected in the radio using the GMRT (Chakraborti et al., 2012).

In this study, we push these radio studies to the even younger and lower mass population of blueberry galaxies. We report their first ever radio detections, which has been possible due to the wideband backend of the uGMRT (uGMRT, Gupta et al., 2017) allowing us to reach an rms of $\sim 15 \mu\text{Jy}/\text{beam}$ with reasonable integration time at 1.25 GHz. Here we compare their radio-based SFRs with the optical and UV+IR based SFR and also estimate their non-thermal fraction.

In this pilot study, we selected a subset of the 40 confirmed blueberry galaxies from Yang et al. (2017) as follows. The SFR from Yang et al. (2017) were used to calculate the expected non-thermal flux density at 1.4 GHz for a normal star-forming galaxy following Yun & Carilli (2002). Since this calibration can vary for our population of young starburst galaxies, we selected 10 of the brightest sources to ensure direct detections. These galaxies were observed using uGMRT (project ID: 34_123) at Band-5 (1000-1450 MHz) with ~ 2 hrs on source.

Here, we present a radio continuum study of a population of extremely young starburst blueberry galaxies at ~ 1 GHz using the uGMRT. We detected 9 out of the 10 sources in our sample. We find that the radio-based SFR is suppressed by a factor of ~ 3.3 (median value) compared to that of the $\text{H}\alpha$ based SFR. We see a similar trend when we compare with the UV+24 μm based SFR. Such a suppression might be due to (i) the young ages of these galaxies as a result of which a stable equilibrium via feedback from supernovae has not yet been established (ii) escape of cosmic ray electrons via diffusion or galactic scale outflows. The estimated non-thermal fraction in these galaxies has a median value of ~ 0.49 , which is

also relatively lower than that in normal star-forming galaxies at such low frequencies. Thus, our study shows that the high- z LAEs too might have intrinsically suppressed radio emission. However, an inter-comparison between $H\alpha$, UV+24 μm and radio based SFR does not show any consistent relation. Such deviations might be due to the stochastic nature of star-formation and/or varying dust properties in these galaxies. A detailed UV-IR SED fitting study is necessary to reliably estimate their SFRs. These two studies end Part-I of this thesis.

It is relatively rare to find large amounts of ionized gas in the outskirts of galaxies. In the few cases where we do find ionized gas in the galaxy outskirts, it is either due to galaxy outflows due to strong starbursts or from active galactic nuclei (AGN). Of them the case of Hanny's Voorwerp (Lintott et al., 2009) is particularly interesting. Here large amounts of emission in the g-band, due to strong emission in the [OIII] $\lambda\lambda$ 4959,5007 was serendipitously found lying near the spiral galaxy IC 2497 by one Galaxy Zoo volunteer Hanny van Arkel. It has been suggested that the gas in Hanny's Voorwerp has a tidal origin (Józsa et al., 2009). This gas was then photoionised by the nucleus of IC 2497, which, in turn, was a quasi-stellar object (QSO) that has faded dramatically in the last 10^5 years, thus producing a quasar light echo (Lintott et al., 2009; Schawinski et al., 2010). About 19 more such objects were later discovered by the Galaxy Zoo volunteers which are together termed as extended emission-line regions (EELRs; Keel et al., 2012b). Using the MaNGA IFU survey's entire public data release of 2755 galaxies, we have searched for more such cases of Hanny's Voorwerp using the $H\alpha$ line. The previous searches of such EELRs relied on broadband fluxes and they are hence sensitive to objects with large equivalent widths. Using IFU data from MaNGA we are able to search for more fainter counterparts of these objects, due to which the EELRs in our study do not have any bright optical counterparts in the SDSS and in the deeper imaging data release 5 from the Dark Energy Camera Legacy Survey (DECaLS) and data release 6 of the Mayall z -band Legacy Survey (MzLS) + Beijing-Arizona Sky Survey (BASS).

Our sample is drawn from MaNGA survey (Bundy et al., 2015, MaNGA) which was part of SDSS DR14. This recent data release contains a sample of 2,812 MaNGA datacubes. These datacubes were analysed using the Pipe3D data analysis pipeline by the MaNGA team and their final catalogue of 2,755 galaxies forms our sample, wherein we search for outlying $H\alpha$ emitters.

We identify a region of $H\alpha$ emission as an outlying $H\alpha$ emitter if the following three criteria are satisfied: 1) A signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of $H\alpha$ flux greater than 5 and which covers atleast one MaNGA PSF which corresponds to ~ 5 spaxels. 2) No bright optical counterpart in SDSS *gri* colour composite image or in the DECaLS, MzLS/BASS *gri* colour composite image. 3) $H\alpha$ velocity of the emitter which is different (typically upto 400 km/s) from the velocity field of the parent galaxy and/or the $H\alpha$ emission is clearly extra-planar. Using this criteria we identify 6 outlying $H\alpha$ emitters in the entire SDSS IV MaNGA survey.

We have carried out a systematic search for outlying $H\alpha$ emitters in the entire SDSS IV MaNGA survey. Using the criteria described above, we have discovered six outlying $H\alpha$ emitters with no bright underlying optical continuum emission in DECaLS and MzLS/BASS survey. These outlying $H\alpha$ emitters all have extended structure in the $H\alpha$ image and a different velocity field from that of the host galaxy. Their emission line ratios show that they are photoionised due to an active galactic nucleus (AGN) or a mixture of both an AGN and star formation. A comparison of their $H\alpha$ luminosity with that of Hanny’s Voorwerp shows that some of them are fainter counterparts of Hanny’s Voorwerp like objects. In the following we show another peculiar case of large amounts of neutral gas lying around a quenched galaxy.

Almost all of the previously known ring galaxies have multi-phase interstellar medium with HI and molecular gas, dust and usually bright optical counterpart. Only one case of an optically devoid HI ring is known at present – the ‘Leo ring’ (Schneider et al., 1983). Here the HI is distributed in the form of a spectacularly large and clumpy ring of about 200 kpc diameter around the early-type galaxy (ETG) pair NGC 3384 and M105, and has no

obvious ultra-violet (UV)/optical counterpart. It was thus long thought to have a primordial origin (Schneider et al., 1983). However, recent observations found UV (Thilker et al., 2009), optical (Michel-Dansac et al., 2010), weak dust emission (Bot et al., 2009) and also metal-line absorption in the ring (Rosenberg et al., 2014). The metallicity of the Leo ring was found to be pre-enriched (Michel-Dansac et al., 2010; Rosenberg et al., 2014) suggesting a galactic origin. Targeted simulations further showed that it could also have a collisional origin (Michel-Dansac et al., 2010) or a tidal origin (Bekki et al., 2005).

Our target AGC203001 is selected such that it has a early-type morphology with no signs of active SF, like those studied in Section 2. But it is an unusual ETG because it hosts large amounts of neutral hydrogen as found from single dish measurements HI measurements. The GMRT 21 cm line observations of AGC 203001 were carried out on 23rd and 24th December 2017 for a total on-source time of ~ 10 hours with the GMRT software backend. The total bandwidth was configured at 16.66 MHz divided into 512 channels, thus corresponding to a velocity resolution of ~ 7 km/s, and centered at the heliocentric redshift of AGC 203001. The data analysis was carried out using standard tasks in the Astronomical Imaging Processing System package. We reach a noise level of ~ 0.67 mJy/beam for a velocity resolution of 14 km/s and with a beam size of $38.02'' \times 35.24''$. The HI integrated intensity image and velocity field were made using the task MOMNT.

We have obtained deep g , r , and i optical images of the field around AGC 203001 with the MegaCam camera installed on the Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) with surface brightness level of ~ 28 mag/arcsec².

Here we report GMRT discovery of an extremely large (~ 115 kpc in diameter) HI ring, located around a massive quenched galaxy, AGC 203001, but off-centered, with respect to it (see Fig. 5.1). This ring does not have any bright extended optical counterpart unlike several other known ring galaxies. The deep CFHT image shows however several regions with very faint optical emission. Such an extended HI structure is very rare with only

one other case known so far – the Leo ring. Conventionally, off-centered rings have been explained by a collision with an “intruder” galaxy leading to expanding density waves of gas and stars in the form of a ring. However, in such a scenario the impact also leads to large amounts of star formation in the ring which is not observed in the ring presented in this paper. An alternative scenario for the formation of such massive, optically devoid HI clouds is the stripping of a gas-rich low surface brightness (LSB) galaxy with an extended HI disc by the tidal field of galaxy groups ([Bekki et al., 2005](#)).

List of Publications:

1. **Omkar Bait**, Yogesh Wadadekar, Sudhanshu Barway *Outlying $H\alpha$ emitters in SDSS-IV MaNGA*, 2019, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society **485**, 428B.
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Contents

List of Figures	xxiii
List of Tables	xxvii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 On multi-wavelength (UV-radio) study of galaxies	2
1.2 Multi-wavelength SED modelling	10
1.2.1 The MAGPHYS code	12
1.3 Observational studies on galaxies	13
1.3.1 Galaxy morphological classification	14
1.3.2 Star-forming main sequence of galaxies	16
1.3.3 Atomic gas scaling relations	20
1.4 A brief overview on galaxy environment	21
1.4.1 Quantifying galaxy environment	22
1.4.2 Morphology-density relation	23
1.5 The problem of galaxy quenching	25
1.5.1 Green valley galaxies:	29
1.6 A brief overview on star-forming dwarf galaxies	30
1.6.1 The local star-forming dwarf galaxy zoo	31
1.7 Star formation, ionized and HI gas in galaxy outskirts	32
1.8 Outline of the thesis	38
2 On the interdependence of galaxy morphology, star formation, and environment in massive galaxies in the nearby Universe	41
2.1 Introduction	41
2.2 Sample selection and data analysis	43

CONTENTS

2.2.1	Sample selection	43
2.2.2	Morphological Classification	44
2.2.3	Deriving stellar masses and SFRs using SED fitting	47
2.2.4	Environmental Density	48
2.3	Results and Discussion	48
2.3.1	Relation between morphology and specific star-formation rate	48
2.3.1.1	Dependence of morphology on the sSFR- M_* plane	55
2.3.1.2	Fraction of galaxies of different morphologies at fixed sSFR, and the differential effect of environment	57
2.3.1.3	Fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies at fixed morphological T-type, and the differential effect of environment	61
2.3.2	Relation between morphology and local environment	65
2.3.3	Relation between specific star formation rate and local environment	70
2.3.4	Partial correlation coefficient between morphological T-type, sSFR, and Σ	73
2.4	Summary	74
2.5	Conclusion and Future Work	77
3	Radio continuum properties of blueberry galaxies	79
3.1	Introduction	79
3.2	GMRT Observations	81
3.2.1	Sample	81
3.2.2	Data Analysis	84
3.3	Results	85
3.3.1	Comparison between radio and $H\alpha$ based SFRs	85
3.3.2	Comparison between radio, UV+24 μ m and $H\alpha$ based SFRs	87
3.4	Discussion	89
3.4.1	Young ages	89
3.4.2	CRE escape via diffusion/outflows	89
3.5	Future Work	90

4	Hα emission around galaxies in SDSS-IV MaNGA	93
4.1	Introduction	93
4.2	Sample Selection	95
4.2.1	The MaNGA survey	96
4.2.2	PIPE3D value added catalogue	97
4.2.3	Optical Photometric data	98
4.2.4	Selection Criteria	98
4.3	Results and Discussions	101
4.3.1	Integrated properties of outlying H α emitters	101
4.3.1.1	BPT diagram	103
4.3.2	Comparison of H α luminosities of xHAEs with literature	106
4.4	Remarks on individual sources	107
4.5	Summary and Future Work	113
4.6	Integrated spectrum of each of the sources in our sample	114
4.7	List of artefacts found in the MaNGA datacube	114
5	Discovery of a large HI ring around the quiescent galaxy AGC 203001	125
5.1	Introduction	125
5.2	Target selection	127
5.3	Observations and data analysis	127
5.3.1	Deep HI imaging of AGC 203001	127
5.3.2	Deep optical imaging of the HI ring	128
5.4	The HI ring around AGC 203001	128
5.5	Discussion	132
5.5.1	Comparison with HI observations of early-type galaxies	135
5.5.2	Possible formation scenarios for the ring around AGC 203001	136
5.6	Conclusion & Future Work	138
6	Summary of the thesis and Future Work	139
	Bibliography	141

CONTENTS

List of Figures

1.1	The GMRT array configuration	9
1.2	Overview on SED fitting	10
1.3	UV to FIR SED fit of a galaxy using MAGPHYS	13
1.4	Hubble tuning fork	14
1.5	Star-forming main-sequence	18
1.6	Atomic gas scaling relations	20
1.7	Morphology density relation	24
1.8	Overview on quenching of massive galaxies	25
1.9	Quenched fraction with mass and environment	28
1.10	XUV discs	33
1.11	Collisional Debris around NGC 5291	35
1.12	Hanny's Voorwerp	36
1.13	The Leo ring	37
2.1	Morphology histogram	45
2.2	A best-fit SED for a galaxy in our sample using MAGPHYS	49
2.3	Stellar mass distribution for our sample	50
2.4	sSFR distribution of our sample	51
2.5	Environmental density distribution for our sample	52
2.6	Galaxy MS from our sample	53
2.7	Dependence of sSFR on stellar mass for ETS further split into more detailed morphologies	54
2.8	Fraction of galaxies of different morphological type as a function of sSFR	58
2.9	Fraction of galaxies of different morphological type as a function of sSFR split with environment	59

LIST OF FIGURES

2.10	Fraction of star-forming, green valley and quenched galaxies for a fixed morphological T-type going to Es to Im spirals	62
2.11	Fraction of star-forming, green valley and quenched galaxies for a fixed morphological T-type further split in environment	63
2.12	Fraction of different morphological type as a function of environment	66
2.13	Fraction of different morphological types as a function of environment further split with their star-forming state	67
2.14	Fraction of star-forming, green valley and quenched galaxies for fixed environmental bins	70
2.15	Fraction of star-forming, green valley and quenched galaxies for fixed environmental bins split with different morphological class	71
3.1	Radio images of blueberry galaxies	83
3.2	Comparison between radio and $H\alpha$ based SFR	85
3.3	Estimated non-thermal fraction as a function of stellar mass for our sample of blueberry galaxies.	87
3.4	Comparison between radio, $H\alpha$ and $UV+24\mu m$ based SFR	88
4.1	MaNGA observation of a galaxy with ID 8601-12701	99
4.2	MaNGA observation of a spiral galaxy 8257-12703	101
4.3	Final Sample of outlying $H\alpha$ emitters in the SDSS MaNGA.	102
4.4	Integrated fluxes and uncertainty of the various outlying HAEs	104
4.5	BPT diagram for the outlying HAEs	105
4.6	outlying emission for X1	108
4.7	Continued. Here we show the outlying emission for X3.	109
4.8	Continued. Here we show the outlying emission for X4.	110
4.9	Continued. Here we show the outlying emission for X5.	111
4.10	Integrated spectrum for X1	115
4.11	Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X2.1 and its corresponding host galaxy.	116
4.12	Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X2.2 and its corresponding host galaxy.	117
4.13	Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X3 and its corresponding host galaxy.	118

LIST OF FIGURES

4.14	Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X4 and its corresponding host galaxy.	119
4.15	Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X5 and its corresponding host galaxy.	120
4.16	List of artefacts in the MaNGA datacube which appear like unresolved blobs.	122
4.17	Continued list of artefacts in the MaNGA datacube	123
4.18	List of artefacts in the MaNGA datacube with extended features.	124
5.1	The HI ring around AGC 203001	129
5.2	The HI velocity map of the ring.	130
5.3	A zoom-in near the possible optical counterparts to the ring	131
5.4	Large scale image of the HI ring with the CFHT image in the background	133
5.5	Comparison of the HI ring with other early-type galaxies	134

LIST OF FIGURES

List of Tables

1.1	RC3 catalogue T-types	17
2.1	Corresponding morphological T-types from the NA10 and RC3 catalogues.	46
2.2	Morphological fraction of galaxies which are in star-forming, green valley and quenched regions.	55
2.3	Fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies each mor- phological type.	61
2.4	Fraction of different morphological types in different environmental bins	68
2.5	Fraction of galaxies in different environments for a given morphological type	68
2.6	Fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies in low, intermediate, and high densities.	71
2.7	Fraction of galaxies in low, intermediate, and high densities which are in star-forming, in green valley, and in the quenched regions.	72
2.8	Results from the partial correlation coefficient analysis. The errors on the correlation coefficients are calculated using the jackknife method. . .	74
3.1	Blueberry sample and observations details	82
5.1	Positions and magnitudes of optical counterparts to the ring	128

LIST OF TABLES

1

Introduction

Understanding how galaxies form and evolve in the Universe is still a major field of research in astronomy. Several developments have occurred both on the observational and theoretical/simulation fronts in recent times. Especially on the observational front there has been a deluge of multi-wavelength data ranging from the ultra-violet to the radio, mainly due to wide field surveys e.g., the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) in the optical. Such developments have also been coupled with recent developments on complete multi-wavelength spectral energy distribution (SED) modelling of galaxies. This has been possible due to a better understanding of stellar population synthesis and dust modelling. In this thesis, we make use of these large volumes of data to study various aspects of star formation (SF) in and around nearby galaxies. We do this by studying the SEDs of galaxies ranging from massive galaxies (with a variety of morphologies) to low-mass dwarf galaxies. This forms Part-I of this thesis. In Part-II of this thesis, we study different aspects of star formation in galaxy outskirts using the recently released integral field unit (IFU) data from the Mapping Nearby Galaxies at APO (MaNGA) survey and HI spectral line observations using the Giant Metrewave Telescope (GMRT).

In this section, I will introduce various observational aspects of galaxy formation and evolution from the literature with an emphasis on star formation. In Sec. 1.1, I will first introduce the multi-wavelength (UV to radio) data used in this thesis and will broadly describe what information we can derive from it. In Sec. 1.2, I will describe the SED modelling of galaxies which combines multi-wavelength data to self-consistently derive galaxy physical parameters. In Sec. 1.3, I will describe the various observational

1. INTRODUCTION

studies of galaxies, particularly relating the galaxy morphology, star formation and gas properties. In Sec. 1.4, I will describe the role of the environment in galaxy studies. In Sec. 1.5, I will describe the phenomenon of galaxy quenching and why it is difficult to pinpoint the exact physical mechanism which causes it. In Sec. 1.6, I will then shift to galaxy evolution in the dwarf galaxy (low mass) regime and specifically describe the population of star-forming dwarf galaxies, which will lay the foundation for results on blueberry galaxies (Chapter 3). In Sec. 1.7, I will lay the foundation for the second part of my thesis, where I will describe unusual cases with large amounts of ionized, neutral gas and star formation events in galaxy outskirts. This section will lay the foundation for Chapter 4 and Chapter 5. Finally, in Sec. 1.8, I will present the complete outline of this thesis describing how the two parts of this thesis are organized.

1.1 On multi-wavelength (UV-radio) study of galaxies

In order to get a complete picture of the physical conditions within a galaxy multi-wavelength spectro-photometric observations (which are preferably spatially resolved) is very useful. In the past, this was only possible for a handful of galaxies. With the advent of several large area surveys e.g., the SDSS in the optical, the all sky UV survey using the Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX) etc., it is now possible to obtain multiwavelength data for large samples of galaxies. The SDSS spectroscopic survey further provides emission and absorption line information for the central regions of about 700,000 galaxies. Recently, with the advent of IFU surveys like the SDSS MaNGA and the Sydney-AAO Multi-object Integral field spectrograph (SAMI) survey, it has become possible to study stellar and ionized gas properties, in a spatially resolved fashion. These developments in large-scale multiwavelength observations have gone hand in hand with several advances in the multi-wavelength spectral energy distribution (SED) modelling of galaxies. This thesis exploits advances in both these areas in order to understand several aspects of star formation in galaxies.

Keeping in mind the various science goals in this thesis, I will now describe the multiwavelength datasets, from UV to radio that are of relevance to this work. I will briefly describe the various galaxy physical parameters that can be estimated using them. I will briefly provide the technical details of each of the telescopes used. I will then briefly mention how multiwavelength data can be used to estimate galaxy

1.1 On multi-wavelength (UV-radio) study of galaxies

physical parameters self-consistently using SED modelling. I will describe some of the 3D datacubes, optical (integral field units) and HI spectral line datacubes and how they reveal the inner workings of galaxy evolution.

- **Ultra-violet (UV; 912 Å to 3000 Å):** The continuum emission at UV wavelengths of galaxies is dominated by young massive stars. This makes UV an ideal tracer of recent SFR, typically on the timescales of 10-100 Myr (Kennicutt & Evans, 2012). It has been found in several studies that UV can probe low-level SFR, typically found in optically red (using the colour magnitude diagram) ETGs which cannot be probed by other tracers like H α (e.g., Fang et al., 2012; Kaviraj et al., 2007; Salim et al., 2012; Yi et al., 2005). UV imaging studies have found several cases of low-level SF much beyond the optical disk of the galaxy, termed as extended UV disks (XUV disks; e.g., Thilker et al., 2007). This is because the optical light is not sensitive to sSFR below 10^{-11}yr^{-1} (Conroy, 2013). Thus, just optical data is not enough to trace all levels of SF in a galaxy and UV plays an important role. However, UV is also strongly affected by dust attenuation. Thus just the UV cannot be used to trace the total SFR, particularly in moderately to highly dusty galaxies. Typically the UV based SFR is combined with a IR tracer to get an estimate of the total SFR.

In this thesis, we have used the space-based Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX) telescope to study our galaxies in the UV. GALEX has a field of view of 1.2 degrees and a resolution of $\sim 5''$. It has two filters, near UV (NUV) ranging from 1750 Å to 2800 Å and far UV (FUV) ranging from 1350 Å to 1750 Å. In the two studies where we have used the GALEX telescope, the data were extracted from the GALEX all-sky survey using the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST¹).

- **Optical (3000 Å to 1 μ m):** The optical waveband is rich in information with its continuum tracing the stellar population of intermediate age stars and its absorption lines giving an idea of the metallicity, age of the stellar population, and of stellar velocity and velocity dispersion. On the optical continuum there are several recombination lines which provides a wide variety of information. Some

¹<https://galex.stsci.edu/GR6/>

1. INTRODUCTION

of the important lines are: Hydrogen Balmer lines ($H\alpha$, $H\beta$ and so on), the [OIII] triplet (these are the [OIII] λ 4932, 4959, 5008), the O[II] doublet (these are the [OII] λ 3727, 3730), [NII] doublet (these are the [NII] λ 6549, 6585), [SII] doublet (these are the [SII] λ 6718, 6732) and the O[I] doublet (these are the [OI] λ 6302, 6365) to name a few. Here the Hydrogen recombination lines, particularly the $H\alpha$ is a very good indicator of SFR mainly from massive O-type stars. It traces SFR on relatively shorter timescales of ~ 10 Myr (Kennicutt & Evans, 2012). [OII] can also be used to trace the SFR. Other lines like the [NII], [SII] and [OIII] can be used to estimate the gas-phase metallicity within a galaxy. A combined study of the line ratio of the various emission lines using the Baldwin-Philip-Terlevich (BPT) diagram can be used to distinguish their sources of photoionization e.g., SF from a HII region, Seyferts, and low-ionisation emission line regions (LINERs) (e.g., Kauffmann et al., 2003c; Kewley et al., 2006). All of this coupled with the fact that much of the good quality optical astronomy can be done using ground-based telescope makes optical the most widely studied wavelength in galaxy science (and also in the whole of astronomy). In recent times, using integral field units (IFUs) one can do these studies in a resolved fashion within galaxies. Here several spectral fibres (like those of the SDSS) are bundled together to form an IFU. This gives the various spectral properties discussed above in two dimensions around a galaxy. Moreover the spectroscopy also gives a resolved view of the velocity field of a galaxy.

In this thesis, we have extensively used the Sloan Digital Sky Survey's (SDSS) publicly available optical photometric and spectroscopic data from the Data Release 14 (Abolfathi et al., 2018). The SDSS survey is being carried out using the Apache Point Observatory (APO) in Sunspot, New Mexico. SDSS has a 2.5 metre size primary mirror, the images have a median seeing of $\sim 1.4''$ and typically reach a 5-sigma depth of 22.70 mag in the r -band. The photometric survey was carried in 5 bands namely u, g, r, i and z . The spectroscopic data are acquired using a $2''$ fibre centered around each galaxy. The SDSS fibre has a uniform wavelength coverage from 3600 Å to 10,400 Å. We have also used the recently released SDSS IV MaNGA IFU data (Bundy et al., 2015) in this thesis. For more information on the MaNGA IFU instrument see Sec. 4.2.1 and for details on the MaNGA survey see Bundy et al. (2015). We have also used the recently available deeper

1.1 On multi-wavelength (UV-radio) study of galaxies

imaging (compared to SDSS) from the Dark Energy Camera Legacy Survey (DECaLS), and the Mayall z -band Legacy Survey (MzLS) and Beijing-Arizona Sky Survey (BASS). DECaLS is being carried out on the Dark Energy Camera on the Blanco 4m telescope at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory in g, r , and z bands reaching a 5-sigma depth of 23.54 mag in the r -band. The MzLS is being carried out using the MOSAIC-3 camera at the prime focus of the 4-meter Mayall telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory in z -band with a 5-sigma depth of 22.60 mag. And the BASS survey is being carried out on the 90Prime camera at the prime focus of the Bok 2.3-m telescope in g and r bands with a 5-sigma depth of 23.65 and 23.08 mag in the g and r bands respectively. [Dey et al. \(2019\)](#) gives an overview of these three imaging surveys. We have also used the 3.6m Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) at Mauna Kea, Hawaii to obtain a very deep image ($\sim 28 - 29$ mag/arcsec²) with the MegaCam camera in g, r and i bands. MegaCam has a very wide field of view of 1 deg² and offers a median seeing of 0.7 " at Mauna Kea.

- **Infrared (1 μ m to 300 μ m):** The infrared regime is divided in three parts: Near Infrared (NIR; 1 μ m to 2.4 μ m), Mid Infrared (MIR; 2.4 μ m to 20 μ m) and Far Infrared (FIR; 20 μ m to 300 μ m).

In galaxies, NIR continuum emission probes the emission from the low mass evolved stellar population. These stars are a major contributor to the total stellar mass of a galaxy. Hence the NIR bands alone (particularly the K-band) can be used as a good proxy to estimate the stellar mass of a galaxy. In this thesis, we have used the Two Micron All-Sky Survey (2MASS; [Skrutskie et al., 2006](#)) to study galaxies in the NIR. 2MASS survey was carried out on two 1.3m telescopes at Mt. Hopkins and at Cerro Tololo, Chile. It is an imaging survey in three NIR bands: J (1.25 μ m), H (1.65 μ m), and K_s (2.16 μ m).

MIR continuum emission in galaxies is due to hot dust coming from small grains which are stochastically heated to high temperatures by the absorption of individual UV photons. Superimposed on this smooth continuum, are various strong emission lines ranging from 3.3 μ m to 12.7 μ m mainly attributed to the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH). In this thesis we have used the Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer All-Sky (WISE; [Wright et al., 2010](#)) data. WISE is based on a

1. INTRODUCTION

dedicated space-based imaging telescope in four bands: W1 ($3.4 \mu\text{m}$), W2 ($4.6 \mu\text{m}$), W3 ($12 \mu\text{m}$), W4 ($22 \mu\text{m}$). The angular resolution is $\sim 6''$ in the first three bands and $\sim 12.0''$ in the W4 band. The MIR continuum emission particularly in the W4 band coupled with the GALEX FUV luminosity is a good indicator of the total SFR in a galaxy (see e.g., [Kennicutt & Evans, 2012](#); [Murphy et al., 2011](#)).

FIR emission in galaxies on the other hand is due to thermal emission from cold dust. This is mainly remitted radiation from the dust which is heated due to UV radiation from young massive stars. The total FIR emission in galaxies can be used to estimate the dust mass and the peak of the dust emission is a good indicator of the dust temperature in the interstellar medium. Like MIR and UV studies, due to absorption from the Earth's atmosphere, FIR astronomy also has to be done using space-based telescopes. The most noteworthy of these FIR telescopes is the IRAS mission which mapped the sky at 12, 25, 60 and $100 \mu\text{m}$. An important discovery of the IRAS mission has been the so-called "Ultra-luminous IR galaxies" (ULIRGS) which are extremely dusty and highly star-forming galaxies. Recently the Herschel ATLAS survey with the Herschel space observatory has mapped a large area of the sky in 100, 160, 250, 350 and $500 \mu\text{m}$. Another important contribution of FIR data on galaxy evolution has been the discovery of a relatively tight dust mass-SFR correlation for SF-galaxies (e.g., [da Cunha et al., 2010](#)). This has been shown to arise from a relatively simple closed-box model of dust formation and destruction due to supernovae ([Hjorth et al., 2014](#)). Interestingly, some of the ETGs with dust show an offset from this relation of SF galaxies which could be due to galaxy mergers which perhaps also formed these ETGs ([Rowlands et al., 2012](#)). In this thesis, we have not used any FIR data because this reduces our sample size considerably. With the availability of the H-ATLAS data on a large sample of galaxies in the future, we aim to carry out a statistical study of galaxies from UV to FIR in the local Universe ([Driver et al., 2016](#)).

- **Radio (10 MHz to 50 GHz):**

The radio sky is visible from the ground continuously from 10 MHz (below which there is significant scattering of the incoming radiation by the ionosphere) upto

1.1 On multi-wavelength (UV-radio) study of galaxies

about 50 GHz (above this there is significant absorption from the water vapor in the atmosphere). Above 50 GHz, we enter the sub-mm regime and one has to observe from a relatively dry site like the Atacama desert where the Atacama Large millimetre array (ALMA) is based. Karl Jansky was the first person to identify the cosmic origin of radio waves from the centre of the Milky Way in around 1933. Radio Astronomy later became a well established field due to the pioneering work of Grote Reber in Australia and many technological developments post World War II.

In galaxies, a significant amount of radio continuum emission arises from star-forming regions. This continuum emission is composed of two components: a flat spectrum thermal component arising from the free-free emission (thermal bremsstrahlung) between free electrons and ionized hydrogen in HII regions and a steep spectrum non-thermal component arising due to synchrotron radiation from relativistic electrons moving in magnetic fields. In cases where the central black-hole is active in a galaxy, the accretion disk of the black-hole, can also give out a large amount of radio emission on top of the emission from star formation. In some special cases, along with a core radio emission in the centres of galaxies there can be accompanying kpc scale radio jets, the most famous being the Cygnus A radio jets. In some exceptional cases the radio jet can be extend to extremely large scale of several Mpcs. On top of this continuum at low frequencies (1.4 GHz and below), there is the HI 21-cm (1420.4057 MHz) emission arising from neutral hydrogen atoms due to the hyperfine spin flip transition between the spins of the proton and the electron. The HI 21 cm emission from a galaxy is optically thin and thus the integrated HI line flux can be used to estimate the total HI gas mass, independent of the temperature.

Single dish radio telescopes have played an important role in the study of the Galactic ISM, study of external galaxies (both using the integrated flux and spectroscopy), pulsars and recently the elusive fast radio bursts (FRBs). The largest single dish radio telescope for a long time was the 305m Arecibo telescope and which has now been overtaken by the Five hundred meter Aperture Spherical Telescope (FAST). Since the radio wavelengths are large, one needs a sufficiently large aperture to get good spatial resolution. However, even the largest single

1. INTRODUCTION

dish telescopes can only give a resolution of several arcmins. This is not sufficient for most extragalactic studies and is not a match with the resolution of the optical telescopes. This is where aperture synthesis technique (first developed by Martin Ryle) comes in. Here, several radio dishes are spread in a large area spanning several kilometres across. The voltages from every other telescope are correlated (termed as visibilities) to form N^2 combinations (where N are the total number of antennas) which gives the total number of baselines. These visibilities (which are distributed on a plane called the $u-v$ plane) are the Fourier transform of the image on the sky. However, because of sparse sampling of the $u-v$ plane due to only a few telescopes the image cannot be obtained from just one set of $u-v$ points. This is where the earth rotation aperture synthesis imaging technique comes in. As the Earth rotates, a source can be tracked on the sky and as the integration time on the source increases the $u-v$ plane starts to fill. Even then there will be several gaps in the $u-v$ plane depending on configuration of the telescope array. This needs to be filled using various sophisticated techniques (usually some form of interpolation). Radio images can then be made at different resolutions by deconvolving the visibilities from the appropriate scales. See [Taylor et al. \(1999\)](#) and [Thompson et al. \(2017\)](#) for a through introduction to synthesis imaging in radio astronomy. Thus the choice of the array to make a radio image depends very much on the science case. The various radio interferometry telescopes have approached this in different ways. For instance the Karl Jansky Very Large Array (JVLA) which has 27 antennas in a Y-shaped array. However, these telescopes can be moved to five different configurations. These are the A, B, BnC, C and D array with decreasing spatial resolution from A to D array. The Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT) has 30 antennas in a fixed but hybrid configuration, with 16 antennas spread in an almost Y-shaped array. The remaining antennas are randomly distributed in the central region called the central square. See [Fig. 1.1](#). Such an array can thus be used for both high imaging (using the full array) and low resolution diffuse imaging using the central square. Using such an array one can map the radio sky in various fixed broadbands and in a narrow band mode (usually centered around an emission line) with a given number of spectral channels. The narrow-band mode with usually a large number of spectral channels is used to get a better velocity resolution which is necessary for spectral

1.1 On multi-wavelength (UV-radio) study of galaxies

line observations (e.g., the HI spectral line observations). For instance, the legacy GMRT operates in various low frequency bands from L-band and below with upto 32 MHz bandwidth and upto 512 spectral channels. Recently the GMRT has been upgraded with wideband feeds with bandwidths upto 400 MHz and upto 16k spectral channels (Gupta et al., 2017). In this thesis, we have used the legacy GMRT in the HI spectral line mode to map HI around quenched galaxies. We have also used the upgraded GMRT with its 400 MHz bandwidth at L-band to observe a sample of dwarf galaxies which are extremely compact and starbursting, termed as blueberry galaxies.

Figure 1.1: The GMRT array configuration. cf. http://gmrt.ncra.tifr.res.in/gmrt_hp/Users/doc/WEBLF/LFRA/node164.html.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.2 Multi-wavelength SED modelling

Figure 1.2: An overview of the process followed by typical SED fitting codes. Figure from Conroy (2013).

In this section, I will briefly give an overview on multiwavelength spectral energy

distribution (SED) modelling and how it can be used to self-consistently derive the various physical properties of galaxies. Briefly, this is achieved by fitting the observed data to the modelled spectrum of a galaxy. Modelling of such a spectrum relies on developments on various fronts, from the availability of high quality spectral data of different types of stars and understanding their evolution in different phases and the initial mass function (IMF). This is then coupled with the star formation history of a galaxy to obtain a spectrum of simple/composite stellar populations of galaxies. Such a spectrum is then attenuated by dust and then re-emitted in the form of PAH, MIR and FIR continuum (usually assuming energy balance). I will begin by giving an overview of the general method of modelling the SED of a galaxy. I will then describe the Multi-wavelength Analysis of Galaxy Physical Properties (MAGPHYS; [da Cunha et al., 2008](#)) model in some detail, which we have used in this thesis. The entire process of stellar population synthesis (SPS) modelling is summarized in [Fig. 1.2](#).

Let us first consider the idea of a simple stellar population (SSP). SSP gives the evolution of the SED of a galaxy for a single, coeval stellar population, for a given metallicity. At a time t after the initial stars form in the stellar population, it can be described using the following equation ([Conroy, 2013](#)):

$$f_{\text{SSP}}(M, t) = \int_{m_{\text{lo}}}^{m_{\text{up}}(t)} f_{\text{star}}[T_{\text{eff}}(M), \log g(M)|_t, Z] \Phi(M) dM, \quad (1.1)$$

where M is the stellar mass of the zero-age main sequence star, Z is the stellar metallicity, f_{star} is the spectrum of a star for a given effective temperature ($T_{\text{eff}}(M)$), surface gravity $\log g(M)|_t$ and Z . $\Phi(M)$ is the initial mass function. The f_{SSP} is the SSP spectrum, which is obtained by integrating the spectrum of stars with different stellar masses ranging from m_{lo} to m_{up} . The lower stellar limit m_{lo} is usually taken as the hydrogen burning limit and corresponds to $\sim 0.1 M_{\odot}$ whereas the upper limit is time dependent and increases as stars evolve. The T_{eff} and $\log g$ are dependent on the stellar isochrones.

Such a simple stellar population of stars could arise in a galaxy due to a single burst in the star formation. However, in reality galaxies have a complex star formation history (SFH) which is typically a slowly declining function of time with some initial starburst which triggered the star formation in a galaxy. Most studies assume an exponentially decaying SFH with a set of random burst superimposed on it (e.g., [Kauffmann et al.,](#)

1. INTRODUCTION

2003a; da Cunha et al., 2008). Thus under the assumption that the SFH of a galaxy can be described as a sum of a series of bursts of SF with a given SSP, one can integrate these SSPs upto some time to obtain a composite stellar population for a given time. Usually, the metallicity of the different SSP formed at a given time is kept fixed, but even that can have a time dependence and can be integrated over. This however, only gives a dust unattenuated spectrum of a galaxy. Usually SPS models also assume some form of dust attenuation, usually the Calzetti law or the Charlot & Fall (2000) time-dependent model. Some of the modern SPS models also consider dust emission in their model. The dust is emitted in different wavelengths from the MIR in the form of PAH emission, and warm dust in the MIR and cold dust in the FIR. There are a number of models available in the literature, the most famous are the physically motivated models by Draine & Li (2007) and the phenomenological models by da Cunha et al. (2008) adopted in the MAGPHYS code. In this thesis, we have used the MAGPHYS code which we will describe below.

1.2.1 The MAGPHYS code

MAGPHYS is a code used to estimate various physical properties of a observed SED of a galaxy. MAGPHYS creates a library of template spectra and finds the best-fit spectrum to the available data in UV, optical, near and mid IR bands. MAGPHYS uses the “CB07 library”, which is the unpublished version of the Bruzual & Charlot (2003) stellar population synthesis model, with a Chabrier initial mass function. A set of optical library templates are constructed, by varying the star formation history, which is modeled as an exponentially decaying star formation rate with random bursts of star formation superimposed on it, and also by varying metallicity from 0.02 to 2 times solar metallicity. The two-component Charlot & Fall (2000) model is used to estimate the amount of dust attenuation. In this model, the dust attenuation is higher around young stars (age $< 10^7$ Myr) as they are born in dense molecular clouds. This attenuated light is distributed (assuming a energy balance) in the the infrared region in three forms: PAH emission line features, MIR dust continuum from the warm dust and the FIR continuum emission from the cold dust. Here the MIR and FIR continuum dust emission is modelled as a greybody with different dust temperatures and emissivities. MAGPHYS then performs a χ^2 fit on the given data, say in UV, optical, and IR bands with the entire library of template SEDs. For each parameter in the model,

Figure 1.3: A typical UV to FIR best-fit SED of a galaxy using the MAGPHYS model. The lower panel shows a residuals to the fit. Figure from [Conroy \(2013\)](#)

MAGPHYS also builds a likelihood distribution by weighting the parameter value with the probability given by $\exp(-\chi^2/2)$. Fig. 1.3 shows a typical good MAGPHYS fit to the UV to FIR SED of NGC337.

1.3 Observational studies on galaxies

A complete theory on galaxy formation and cosmological evolution should be able to reproduce the various observed relations between galaxy properties. In the last few decades, this has motivated a large number of observations and has led to a surge of new relations between galaxy properties and their evolution. Moreover, such relations have also helped in constructing various phenomenological models of galaxy formation and evolution and provided various prescriptions for cosmological scale galaxy simulations.

In this section, I will briefly describe the various standard relations between galaxy physical properties, particularly relating to SF. First, I will broadly describe the galaxy morphological classification and some general properties of galaxies. I will then describe two of the main scaling relations. The galaxy main sequence, a fairly strong relation between the star formation rate and stellar mass of galaxies. And then I will describe the various gas scaling relations relating the gas mass with a number of above mentioned

Figure 1.4: Hubble tuning fork diagram. Figure from <https://blog.galaxyzoo.org/2011/02/23/the-hubble-tuning-fork/>

galaxy properties. Note that all of the results presented here are valid for local galaxies, a study of which is the aim of this thesis.

1.3.1 Galaxy morphological classification

Optical imaging studies of galaxies has a very long history in astronomy. A important breakthrough came with the advent of optical photographic plates. This led of optical studies in a large sample of galaxies (by the standards of that time) where it was found that their visual appearances can be classified in two broad categories. These are late-type spiral galaxies (henceforth LTS) and early-type galaxies (henceforth ETG). Late-type galaxies are primarily disk (which has a exponentially decreasing light profile) dominated systems with prominent spiral arm features. These galaxies also have a spheroidal component in the center termed as a bulge¹, with different levels of promi-

¹It may be defined as the excess light over the exponential disk

nence. Early-type galaxies are those which have a very prominent spheroidal component at their centre. Of them ellipticals (Es), are “purely ” spheroidal systems and S0s are spheroid plus disk systems with no apparent spiral arms. Such a classification was first proposed by Reynolds (1920) and Hubble (1926). Lenticulars (S0s) and irregulars were later added to this classification. Edwin Hubble famously arranged these galaxies in the so called “Hubble tuning fork” diagram (see Fig. 1.4; Hubble (1936)). Here the spiral galaxies with and without a bar (in the centre) are arranged on the two prongs of a tuning fork and the base is formed by Es with decreasing ellipticity. The different Es are denoted by E_n , where $n = 10 \times (1 - b/a)$. Here ‘b’ is the minor axis and ‘a’ is the major axis of the galaxy. Thus n is zero for a completely spherical galaxy and such a galaxy is represented as E0. And E1, E2, E3, ..., so on represent Es with ever increasing ellipticity. At the point of intersection of the prongs, at the base of the tuning fork lie the S0 galaxies. There have been several modifications and additions to the original Hubble tuning fork diagram with the inclusion of rings and bars etc. However, a detailed description of all of them is beyond the scope of this thesis (see e.g., van den Bergh (1998), Buta (2011) for detailed reviews).

In the following, I will briefly describe a continuity approach taken towards extending the Hubble classification scheme by de Vaucouleurs (1959). Here the most important change is that the broad classes of ETGs and LTS are further classified in terms of various stages. The stages are defined differently for Es, S0s and spirals. The different stages of Es are compact ellipticals (c0), normal ellipticals (E0) and late-type ellipticals (E+) which show some hints of a faint disk. On the other hand, the different stages of S0s are represented by early (S0-), intermediate (S0⁰) and late (S0+). S0- shows very smooth light profiles and the level of features increases as we move to S0+ stage. The spirals are classified in different stages as Sa, Sab, Sb, Sbc, Sc, Scd, Sd, Sdm, Sm and Im. Here, Sa galaxies show a prominent bulge component, tightly wrapped with smooth spiral arms. As we go on to Sab, Sb, Sbc and Sc, the prominence of the bulge decreases and the opening angle of the spiral arms increases. The spiral arms also start becoming more patchy. Scd and Sd galaxies appear to be almost bulgeless and have very patchy spiral arms. Sdm galaxies are mostly bulgeless galaxies which shows faint hints of spiral arms. Similarly, Sm galaxies are also bulgeless and have a single spiral arm. Sometimes, if a bar is present it is also displaced from the disk. In the last stage of the de Vaucouleurs sequence of spirals lie the magellanic irregulars (Im). These

1. INTRODUCTION

galaxies have some of the lowest luminosities and sometimes also shows the presence of bars. These morphological types are represented using distinct numerical T-types as listed in Table 1.1.

Remarkably, various physical parameters (in terms of their size, optical colors, luminosity, HI mass fraction, etc.) of galaxies are known to correlate with morphology (Roberts & Haynes, 1994). The average star formation rate (SFR) also shows a strong trend with morphology, with a low rate of star formation in Es and S0s, and increasing as we go to spiral galaxies (Kennicutt, 1998a).

In recent times, with the advent of large galaxy samples, it is very difficult to individually classify each galaxy. Several attempts have been made to tackle this limitation. This may involve using citizen science projects like the Galaxy Zoo (Hart et al., 2016; Lintott et al., 2008) or machine learning (Domínguez Sánchez et al., 2018). One important limitation of using visual classification is the inherent subjectivity in defining galaxy morphology. This has motivated quantification of morphologies using physical parameters like the concentration, asymmetry, smoothness, Gini and M20 (CASGM; e.g., Abraham et al., 1994; Conselice et al., 2000; Lotz et al., 2004), bulge to total (B/T) ratio. However, the mapping of such physical measures of morphologies with the visual morphologies of the Hubble T-types shows a lot of scatter (e.g., Weinzirl et al., 2009).

3D galaxy kinematics has proven to be an useful way to classify galaxy morphology. In particular, the work on local ETGs by the ATLAS^{3D} collaboration (Cappellari et al., 2011) using the SAURON integral field observations has shown that they can be classified in terms of fast and slow rotators (Emsellem et al., 2011). Contrary to expectation they have found that majority of the local ETGs ($\sim 86\%$) are fast-rotators (Emsellem et al., 2011). This has motivated them to revise the Hubble tuning fork diagram into a comb diagram (Emsellem et al., 2011). The stellar (baryonic) specific angular momentum of galaxies and stellar (baryonic) mass relation of galaxies is another way to objectively quantify galaxy morphology and it shows a strong correlation with the Hubble T-types (Cortese et al., 2016; Fall & Efstathiou, 1980; Fall & Romanowsky, 2018; Obreschkow & Glazebrook, 2014; Romanowsky & Fall, 2012). However, such studies are limited to only a few thousand galaxies due to lack of 3D kinematics data; a situation which will improve rapidly in the near future.

1.3.2 Star-forming main sequence of galaxies

Table 1.1: Corresponding morphological T-types from the RC3 catalogues ([de Vaucouleurs et al., 1991](#)).

Class	c0	E0	E+	S0-	S0	S0+	S0/a	Sa	Sab	Sb	Sbc	Sc	Scd	Sd	Sdm	Sm	Im
RC3	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

1. INTRODUCTION

Figure 1.5: The star-forming main sequence of galaxies. Figure from (Peng et al., 2015)

Observations have shown that galaxies exhibit a tight correlation between their star formation rate (SFR) and stellar mass (M_*), the so-called ‘main-sequence’ of SF galaxies (MS) in the local Universe (Brinchmann et al., 2004; Daddi et al., 2007; Elbaz et al., 2007; Noeske et al., 2007; Salim et al., 2007). The scatter in this MS is typically of the order of 0.3 dex. Fig. 1.5 shows the tight relation between M_* and SFR. It is interesting to note that although SF galaxies have various kinds of morphologies (as discussed in Sec. 1.3.1) they all lie on the same relation. This has motivated several authors to develop models of galaxy evolution where they remain in a quasi-steady state for a long time. This is enabled by an interplay between gas accretion, SF and feedback driven galaxy outflows which acts as counterbalances and keep a SF galaxy on the MS for long periods of time (e.g., Davé et al., 2011; Lilly et al., 2013; Schaye

et al., 2010; Tacchella et al., 2016). The variations between these processes in different galaxies are also used to explain the scatter in the MS (e.g., Tacchella et al., 2016). Such a MS has also been found at high redshifts of up to 4 (e.g., Peng et al., 2010; Schreiber et al., 2015, 2017). Interestingly, such a MS relation is also seen at kpc scales within galaxies using recent integral field unit (IFU) surveys (e.g., Cano-Díaz et al., 2016; Hsieh et al., 2017; Medling et al., 2018).

Along with the population of these SF galaxies there are also galaxies which are significantly away from this relation as seen in Fig. 1.5. These galaxies are termed as quenched galaxies. I will discuss them in detail in Sec. 1.5.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.3.3 Atomic gas scaling relations

Figure 1.6: The various atomic gas scaling relations of galaxies. Each of the panels from top-left, top-right, bottom-left and bottom-right shows the relation between gas fractions versus M_* , stellar mass surface density, sSFR and NUV-r colour, respectively. Figure from [Catinella et al. \(2018\)](#).

Cold gas, in the form of atomic hydrogen (HI), is the fuel for star formation in galaxies. This is quantified using the well-known Kennicutt-Schmidt (KS) law of star formation ([Kennicutt, 1989](#); [Schmidt, 1959](#)). In its most modern form, the KS law gives a relation between the total gas mass surface density with the total SFR surface density with an exponent of 1.4. Here, the total gas mass involves a sum of the HI mass and molecular hydrogen (H_2) mass. The H_2 mass is estimated using the CO line and assuming a single H_2/CO conversion factor. It has also been shown that there is a correlation between the HI content and the size, luminosity, morphological type, and environment of galaxies ([Roberts & Haynes, 1994](#)).

In recent times, studies have been done on a large sample of galaxies for which HI

1.4 A brief overview on galaxy environment

single dish spectra are obtained. These studies include the extragalactic HI blind survey using Arecibo telescope, the Arecibo Legacy Fast ALFA survey (ALFALFA; Giovanelli et al., 2005; Haynes et al., 2018), a mass-selected targeted survey of SDSS galaxies, the GALEX Arecibo SDSS Survey (GASS; Catinella et al., 2010) and its extended version, the xGASS (Catinella et al., 2018). An important result of these studies has been that the HI gas fraction shows a strong correlation with the stellar mass, stellar mass surface density, $sSFR$ and $NUV - r$ colour (e.g., Catinella et al., 2012, 2018) as shown in Fig. 1.6. Catinella et al. (2012, 2018) have further defined a gas fraction plane which is a relation between the gas fraction and a linear combination of the stellar mass surface density and the $NUV - r$ colour. Zhang et al. (2009) argued that such a relation is a direct consequence of the global KS law for star formation (Kennicutt, 1998b). Such a scaling relation is also found for molecular gas fraction and M_* , $sSFR$ etc. An extensive study on this has been done using the COLD GASS survey (Saintonge et al., 2011) using the IRAM telescope to measure the CO(1-0) line to estimate the molecular mass.

However, there are several galaxies which are outliers on this relation whose nature is yet to be systematically investigated. A few attempts have started in this direction. This involves the study of HI-excess galaxies, which are above the gas fraction plane (Geréb et al., 2016, 2018). Parkash et al. (2019) have studied a sample of 91 galaxies using IFU data which show little or no sign of SF and yet have HI in them. They find that most galaxies are Low Ionization Emission-line RegionS (LIERS). The HI eXtreme (HIX) galaxy survey (Lutz et al., 2017) is targeting some of the most gas rich galaxies in the southern hemisphere. We have also started a survey of galaxies which show little or no sign of SF yet have large reservoirs of gas (as measured from the single dish measurements from the ALFALFA survey) using the Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT). In Chapter 5, I will discuss a pilot study of a typical galaxy in our survey, AGC 203001 and briefly describe the sample selection of other galaxies in our survey.

1.4 A brief overview on galaxy environment

In the last few sections, I gave an overview of the various physical properties of galaxies. Many of these properties are dependent on the galaxy environment. In the following, I will describe in some detail some of the ways in which galaxy environment is quanti-

1. INTRODUCTION

fied. I will then describe the now-famous morphology density relation and how the SF properties of galaxies depend on the galaxy environment.

1.4.1 Quantifying galaxy environment

The environment of a galaxy is a fairly broad term and it is quantified in multiple ways in the literature. Of these some of the most popular are: 1) the galaxy local surface density 2) galaxy group/cluster properties quantified either by the group richness or halo mass 3) whether a galaxy is a central or satellite and 4) by indentifying where the galaxy lies in the large-scale structure whether a galaxy is in a group, in a filament or void.

In order to measure the galaxy local surface density authors in the literature use two distinct methods: nearest neighbour and fixed aperture. Both the methods use a measure, n , which is the number of neighbours around a given galaxy. In the nearest neighbour method the galaxy local surface density is simply given by

$$\Sigma_n = \frac{n}{\pi r_n^2}, \quad (1.2)$$

where r_n is the distance to the n th nearest neighbour and Σ_n is the galaxy local surface density. The number of neighbours, n is kept fixed (5th or 10th and sometimes an average of the two) and then r_n is measured to obtain the density. In the fixed aperture method, the area or volume probed around a galaxy is kept fixed within which the total number of galaxies are counted. The galaxy density is usually given by a density contrast as,

$$\delta = \frac{\delta\rho}{\rho} = \frac{N_g - \bar{N}_g}{\bar{N}_g}, \quad (1.3)$$

where N_g is the number of galaxies in the fixed aperture and \bar{N}_g is the mean number of galaxies expected if they were randomly distributed in the aperture volume (Croton et al., 2005; Muldrew et al., 2012). If the redshift information is available for all the galaxies in the sample, a velocity cut of ± 1000 km/s is typically adopted around each galaxy. This is done to avoid the overestimation of the density in cases where galaxies appear close to each other in the images but in reality they are far away in the third dimension. For a thorough analysis of these two measures of galaxy density refer to Muldrew et al. (2012).

1.4 A brief overview on galaxy environment

Another method to quantify a galaxy environment is by measuring the group properties in which a galaxy resides. As is now widely known that other than isolated galaxies, many of the galaxies are found in groups which are gravitationally bound by the group's dark matter halo potential. In order to find the group associations it is crucial to have redshift information for a large number of galaxies. This is possible with surveys like the SDSS spectroscopic survey. In these methods, first a friends-of-friend algorithm (e.g., [Davis et al., 1985](#)) is used to identify group associations (group centres, members etc.). Then a tentative value of the group properties like mass, size and velocity dispersion is assigned to each group. Then assuming that galaxies follow a Navarro-Frenk-White (NFW; [Navarro et al., 1997](#)) profile the group membership is updated and the group properties are recomputed. Then using an iterative method the final masses, sizes and velocity dispersion of the group is inferred till there are further changes in the group associations (e.g., [Yang et al., 2007](#)).

1.4.2 Morphology-density relation

1. INTRODUCTION

Figure 1.7: The morphology density relation of galaxies. Figure from Dressler (1980).

Dressler (1980) found that the Hubble morphological types of galaxies show a strong correlation with the density of galaxies, termed as the “morphology-density” relation. Here as the environmental density increases the fraction of late-type galaxies decreases and the fraction of early-type and S0 galaxies increases. A similar relation exists for the fraction of late-type (and early-type galaxies) as a function of group/cluster centric distance. Such a relation has also been found using a large number of galaxies in the SDSS survey by Goto et al. (2003). The morphology-density relation suggests that the galaxy environment plays an important role in shaping galaxies. And since the star formation state of a galaxy is also closely related to the morphologies of galaxies, the galaxy environment also leads to a decline in SF of galaxies. Thus, when a galaxy enters a galaxy, cluster processes like ram pressure stripping, galaxy strangulation and galaxy harassment are invoked to explain such a relation. However, it is not very clear what are the dominant processes which lead to such transformations (see Sec. 1.5). Moreover, it is also not clear if the various observed correlations are causal or are driven by another

parameter. In Chapter 2 we do a more detailed analysis of these inter-correlations for massive galaxies and study the strengths of these correlations after removing the effect of other parameters.

1.5 The problem of galaxy quenching

Figure 1.8: Diagram showing the various mechanisms that can quench massive galaxies. cf. [Man & Belli \(2018\)](#).

Galaxies below the star-forming MS are termed as quenched galaxies. These are passively evolving with very little SF and are mostly early-type in morphology. Such a transition can happen due to various physical processes and the exact cause(s) for this cessation of star formation is still heavily debated ([Man & Belli, 2018](#)). I will now briefly describe the various ways of quenching a galaxy (see ([Man & Belli, 2018](#)) for a detailed discussion):

- Starvation: In these scenarios, the gas accretion on galaxies reduces from high to

1. INTRODUCTION

low redshifts which leads to an overall decline in the sSFR with time and eventual quenching of the galaxy (Feldmann & Mayer, 2015). The other possibility is galaxy strangulation (Larson et al., 1980). Here, when a satellite galaxy falls into the dark matter halo of a cluster, the tidal forces remove the diffuse outlying gas rather than dense gas which stops further accretion of gas onto the galaxy. The remaining gas in the galaxy will be slowly consumed and it will slowly quench.

- Gas heating mechanisms: In these scenarios, the gas surrounding the galaxy does not cool efficiently to form cold molecular gas (the birthplace of new stars). Such heating can happen due to virial shocks when gas falls on to massive dark matter haloes ($> 10^{12}M_{\odot}$), a process termed as halo quenching (e.g., Dekel & Birnboim, 2006). This coupled with the AGN feedback, which can heat the surrounding gas (radio-mode feedback), further helps to maintain the quenched state of a galaxy (e.g., Bower et al., 2006; Croton et al., 2006).
- Low star formation efficiency: In these scenarios, quenching can happen not due to lack of fuel for SF (as in the previous cases) but due to a diminished star formation efficiency ($SFE \equiv SFR/M_{\text{gas}}$). This can happen due to the presence of a bigger bulge which can provide additional turbulence in the disk and stabilize it against fragmentation, a process termed as morphological quenching (Martig et al., 2009). SFE can also be reduced due to magnetic field pressure which can reduce high-mass SF and thus quench galaxies (Tabatabaei et al., 2018).
- Rapid consumption of gas: Here, the quenching takes place when the gas consumption rate is larger than the rate at which the gas can be replenished, typically through some form of violent processes. Galaxy major mergers are one possibility, where during the merger, gas is rapidly consumed due to a burst of SF which is followed by quenching (Mihos & Hernquist, 1996). The other possibility is compactification (Zolotov et al., 2015), where a high-redshift galaxy undergoes a phase of contraction into a compact star-forming galaxy (blue nugget) where gas is consumed rapidly. This is followed by a transition to a quiescent phase of star formation (red nugget).
- Removal of existing cold gas: In these cases, the cold gas is removed from a galaxy thus eventually quenching a galaxy. This can happen due to quasar-

1.5 The problem of galaxy quenching

mode feedback, where the supermassive black hole can release enough energy and momentum to expel the gas (Di Matteo et al., 2005). Large scale gas inflows can also arise during galaxy mergers, which can feed the supermassive black hole to power the quasar. When a satellite galaxy falls into a galaxy cluster, the denser cold gas in the outer regions (which is loosely bound) can get easily stripped due to the ram-pressure from the hot ionized gas of the cluster (Gunn & Gott, 1972). This can also contribute to galaxy quenching.

Thus, there are several possible physical mechanisms which can quench galaxies. Fig. 1.8 gives an overview of these mechanisms from Man & Belli (2018). However, as of now there is(are) no observational evidence(s) which can clearly differentiate between the various scenarios¹ although some studies have suggested that strangulation might be the primary cause of quenching using a sample of nearby SDSS galaxies (Peng et al., 2015; Trussler et al., 2018). In all, it is expected that no matter which physical mechanism quenches a galaxy, there has to be some form of gas heating mechanism which maintains the quenched state of a galaxy for several Gyrs by preventing gas accretion.

A phenomenological approach to galaxy quenching has led to several insights. It has been found that there are two completely separable processes : ‘mass quenching’ by which star-forming galaxies undergo rapid quenching above the Schechter mass (M^*), and ‘environmental quenching’ which produces a second component of quenched galaxies at the lower mass end (Baldry et al., 2006; Peng et al., 2010). Such conclusions are generally reached because we see a clearly separable dependence of the quenched fraction on both the stellar mass and environment. Fig. 1.9 shows the dependence of the fraction of quenched galaxies with respect to the M_* and galaxy environment measured using the overdensity parameter. One can see that for a fixed environmental density (stellar mass) the quenched fraction increases with increasing stellar mass (environmental density). Other studies have shown that the passive state of a galaxy correlates strongly with its internal structure e.g., with stellar surface mass density (Kauffmann et al., 2003b), in particular with $\Sigma_{1 \text{ kpc}}$, the inner 1 kpc stellar surface mass density (Cheung et al., 2012; Fang et al., 2013; Woo et al., 2015) or with bulge

¹This was one of the main conclusions reached in a recent conference on “The Physics of Quenching Massive Galaxies at High Redshift” at the Lorentz Center.

1. INTRODUCTION

Figure 1.9: The fraction of quenched galaxies as a function of stellar mass and environment. Figure from Peng et al. (2010).

mass (Bluck et al., 2014) and also with σ , the central velocity dispersion (Teimoorinia et al., 2016; Wake et al., 2012). Such a correlation is stronger for the central galaxy in a dark matter halo than for satellites. Omand et al. (2014) have shown that quenching depends both on the stellar mass and the effective radius R_e . It is important to note

that these correlations may not necessarily mean that there is a causal connection between the quenching process and galaxy structural parameters. [Lilly & Carollo \(2016\)](#) have shown using a simple toy model that such correlations can naturally arise if we consider the [Peng et al. \(2010\)](#) mass-quenching model along with the observed redshift evolution of mass-size relation for star-forming galaxies. The passive fraction also shows dependence on halo mass ([Weinmann et al., 2006](#); [Wetzel et al., 2012](#); [Woo et al., 2013, 2015](#)). Thus there are several observed correlations of quenching on various physical properties but they are unable to point us to any specific physical mechanisms which quenches galaxies.

1.5.1 Green valley galaxies:

In order to differentiate between different quenching mechanisms a targeted study on galaxies in transitions between the SF and quenched state, the so called “green-valley” (GV) can be very useful. Morphological studies of GV galaxies have found that they are typically early-type discs (S0-Sa; e.g., [Bait et al., 2017](#); [Bouquin et al., 2015](#); [Bremer et al., 2018](#); [Ge et al., 2019](#); [Gu et al., 2018](#); [Mendez et al., 2011](#)). Several studies have used the GV galaxies to constrain the quenching timescale. Here, a study by [Schawinski et al. \(2014\)](#) has found that there is no single quenching timescale in the GV and that it is a mixed population. For early-type galaxies the quenching timescale is very rapid (< 250 Myr) while for late-type galaxies it is very slow (> 1 Gyr) (see also [Smethurst et al., 2015](#)). Thus the GV population in the local Universe is a heterogeneous population and it can be very different at high redshifts. A detailed study of GV population using the complete cycle of gas (atomic and molecular), dust and stars as a function of redshift can possibly help in understanding the physical mechanisms behind quenching.

1.6 A brief overview on star-forming dwarf galaxies

According to the hierarchical galaxy formation model, the smallest structures formed first in the Universe which later merged to form larger structures. Thus, in this model dwarf galaxies will be the first galaxies to form stars in the Universe which would then undergo various events of mergers and accretion which would transform them into the massive galaxies we observe today. In order to understand the initial onset of star formation in the Universe one has to study these high-redshift galaxies. However, due to sensitivity limitations it is extremely difficult to do their detailed study. Very few galaxies are known at very high redshifts (of $z \sim 6$) with only one known at redshifts of $z \sim 11$ as of yet (Oesch et al., 2016). We also know that there is the so-called downsizing of galaxies (Cowie et al., 1996) wherein the massive galaxies are in place early on and the low mass galaxies (the dwarf galaxies) have only recently started to form stars. This makes star forming local dwarfs an ideal laboratory to study the complex processes of star formation, gas accretion and feedback in the early Universe.

Much of the discussion in the previous section was applicable to massive galaxies (here we mean galaxies with $M_* > 10^9 M_\odot$). The morphologies, star formation properties, environment and dark matter properties (dark matter fraction) are very different in the low mass regime (dwarf galaxies). In particular, the fraction of spirals, ellipticals and irregulars are very different for dwarfs than for massive galaxies. Most of the dwarfs have irregular morphologies and their star formation is highly stochastic. Dwarfs typically have lower metallicities compared to the massive galaxies (Berg et al., 2012; Lee et al., 2006). Moreover they lack spiral density waves and hence the physical conditions in the interstellar medium which leads to star formation are very different from massive galaxies. Particularly in Chapter 3, we will show that the standard calibration to estimate the SFR from rest-frame radio continuum luminosity (e.g., Kennicutt & Evans, 2012) is not valid for blueberry galaxies, which are a peculiar type of compact starbursting dwarf galaxies.

In the following, I will briefly introduce some of the known population of star-forming dwarfs in the local Universe, keeping in mind the study on radio continuum properties described in Chapter 3. I will focus mainly on their morphological and star formation properties.

1.6.1 The local star-forming dwarf galaxy zoo

There are numerous types of star forming dwarfs galaxies, these include the blue compact dwarfs (BCDs; e.g., [Gil de Paz et al., 2003](#); [Thuan & Martin, 1981](#); [Zwicky & Zwicky, 1971](#)), blue diffuse dwarfs (BDDs; [James et al., 2015, 2017](#)) and the recently discovered blueberries ([Yang et al., 2017](#)). BCDs are defined as those galaxies which have an absolute B-band magnitude lower than -18.15, they are less than a kpc in size and have strong emission lines ([Thuan & Martin, 1981](#)). BDDs were discovered in a search for extremely metal poor galaxies in the SDSS using a morphological criteria by ([James et al., 2015](#)). Here the galaxies were chosen in the SDSS such that they have a blue diffuse stellar continuum on which a bright and blue point-like star-forming region is embedded. These galaxies have lower metallicities ($7.43 < 12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) < 8.01$; [James et al., 2017](#)). Then there are the population of peculiarly bright green and compact galaxies termed as “green pea” galaxies ([Cardamone et al., 2009](#)) discovered by the volunteers from the Galaxy Zoo project. These galaxies have extremely high SFRs, low stellar masses, low metallicities, compact sizes (typically ≤ 5 kpc) and have a bright green color due to the extremely strong [OIII] $\lambda 5007$ Å emission line. [Yang et al. \(2017\)](#) have searched for even younger and lower stellar mass counterparts of the green peas in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) *ugriz* broadband images. They have found a sample of 40 starburst dwarf galaxies with even smaller sizes (≤ 1 kpc), lower stellar masses, low metallicities, termed as “Blueberry” galaxies. Blueberries lie very close to the theoretical threshold of the maximum-starburst, and do not host an active nucleus ([Rong et al., 2018](#)). Blueberries are supposed to be the local analogs of the faint end of high- z LAEs. ([Yang et al., 2017](#)). [Rong et al. \(2018\)](#) using Hubble Space Telescope (HST) images of two blueberries have shown that they might be dwarf-dwarf merging systems. Moreover, their blueberry galaxies also show extended diffuse emission and they are not as compact as the [Yang et al. \(2017\)](#) blueberries. Some of the [Yang et al. \(2017\)](#) blueberries also show some signs of extended features and it is possible that since they are at a relatively higher redshift they might be missing out on the diffuse stellar emission in the SDSS imaging. Recently [Elmegreen & Elmegreen \(2017\)](#) have found even less massive and higher specific star formation rate (sSFR) counterparts of blueberry galaxies, called “Little Blue Dots” (LBDs). Finally, there are the so-called “tidal dwarf galaxies” (TDGs; e.g., [Boquien et al., 2010](#); [Duc & Mirabel, 1994](#); [Duc](#)

1. INTRODUCTION

[et al., 2007](#)), which are galaxies formed in the tidal debris of galaxy-galaxy interactions. TDGs lie away from the mass-metallicity relation of dwarfs ([Berg et al., 2012](#); [Lee et al., 2006](#)) and have higher metallicities for their given M_B . This is because TDGs originate in the tidal tails of stripped gas from galaxy interactions and are hence, pre-enriched.

1.7 Star formation, ionized and HI gas in galaxy outskirts

The detailed physics of star formation in galaxies is not fully understood. It is governed by complex processes involving an interplay between local and large-scale conditions e.g., local gas densities, pressure, chemical enrichment, galactic rotation, density waves, cloud-cloud collisions and magnetic fields. There are various models which have taken a top-down approach to explain the large scale relation between star formation and gas with the gravitational instability criteria using the Toomre parameter ([Toomre, 1964](#)). Using this parameter one finds that galaxy discs are marginally stable over most of the disc and become completely stable in the outer regions (see [Krumholz, 2015](#), for details). Although, these models can explain star formation within discs, they predict almost no star formation in the outskirts. However, we do see many cases of low level (and sometimes even large amounts of) star formation in galaxy outskirts. Galaxy outskirts thus provides a relatively cleaner environment, devoid of density waves, which can be used as a laboratory to test the various models of star formation. In this thesis, we have taken an observational approach and found interesting cases of large amounts of ionized and neutral gas in galaxy outskirts (see [Chapter 4](#) and [Chapter 5](#)).

In this section, I will show several examples (meant to highlight the importance of studying galaxy outskirts) of star formation, ionized and HI gas in galaxy outskirts. I will first show a case of an extended UV (XUV) disc in NGC 5055, where one sees low level star formation in the UV from GALEX. I will then show the case of NGC 5291 where one sees large amounts of star formation and a ring of neutral gas mainly arising due to collision with another galaxy. I will then show the case of Hanny's Voorwerp which is a large region of ionized gas away from the host galaxy IC 2497, arising mainly due to photoionization from an active galactic nucleus (AGN). Finally, I will show a spectacularly large HI-dominated ring, the Leo-ring which is largely devoid of any optical counterpart and whose origin remains elusive even today.

XUV discs:

Figure 1.10: NGC 5055, an example of a XUV disc. Left Panel: GALEX FUV image of the galaxy. Right Panel: 2MASS K_s -band, DSS2-red, and DSS2-blue image shown as an RGB colour composite image. In both the panels the green contour represent the FUV surface brightness at $27.25 \text{ AB mag/arcsec}^2$. The yellow contour represents the region which encompasses 80% of the K band light. Figure from [Thilker et al. \(2007\)](#).

Within a galaxy one observes $H\alpha$ emission arising due to photoionization mostly by O stars in HII regions. However, the GALEX UV filters probe a population of OB stars and can thus observe low levels of star formation. Using this [Thilker et al. \(2005\)](#) discovered UV emission arising from the outskirts of M83 which is associated with low level star formation. Such an extended UV disc, termed as a XUV disc, was found around several galaxies in a systematic search in the GALEX survey by [Thilker et al. \(2007\)](#). Fig. 1.10 shows an example of a XUV disc around NGC 5055. The green contour represents the UV surface brightness which corresponds to the threshold below which no star formation is expected based on the $H\alpha$ tracer (see [Thilker et al., 2007](#)). Notice that in the GALEX FUV image (left panel) you see clumps of recent star formation which also appear to be distributed in a spiral pattern. However, there is very little K-band flux, which mainly traces the old stars, and it is very diffuse. The

1. INTRODUCTION

exact nature of star formation in these regions of XUV discs is still poorly understood. Such a recent star formation event in the galaxy outskirts might be due to continued gas accretion on these galaxies from the intergalactic medium (Thilker et al., 2007).

Next we move to another interesting case where unlike the low level star formation discussed here, we see large amounts of star formation and other material in galaxy outskirts.

Collisional Debris:

NGC 5291 is an extreme example of collisional debris around galaxies. This galaxy is surrounded by a large HI ring which is formed most likely due to the interaction with another neighbouring galaxy, the Seashell galaxy (Duc & Mirabel, 1998; Longmore et al., 1979; Malphrus et al., 1997). Fig. 1.11 shows the HI map of the galaxy in blue from Bournaud et al. (2007). Interestingly, there are several star-forming clumps shown in pink formed in the HI ring. These clumps of star formation could also be gravitationally bound objects which formed independent dwarf galaxies (Bournaud et al., 2007; Duc & Mirabel, 1998; Longmore et al., 1979). Interestingly, the dynamical mass modelling of three of the dwarf galaxies formed in this collisional debris show that they contain sufficient amount of dark matter. Given that these dwarf galaxies are formed from reprocessed material in collisional debris they are expected to be devoid of any nonbaryonic dark matter (Bournaud et al., 2007). And hence the dark matter in these galaxies is very likely to be baryonic dark matter, possibly in the form of cold gas. The collisional debris around NGC 5291 demonstrates that there can be significant amount of baryonic dark matter around galaxies which can solve the missing mass problem.

Ionized gas in galaxy outskirts: The case of Hanny's Voorwerp:

Although there are cases of ionized gas in galaxy outskirts arising due to photoionization from star formation, there are also very interesting cases of large amounts of ionized gas away from the galaxy ionized due to a faded active galactic nuclei. Here, I will present the spectacular case of Hanny's Voorwerp discovered by the citizen scientist, Hanny van Arkel (Lintott et al., 2009). Fig. 1.12 shows the ionized gas structure around IC 2497. The currently known formation mechanism of such structures is thought to be a quasar light echo. In this picture a past interaction/merger can distribute large

Figure 1.11: Collisional Debris around NGC 5291. The blue colour map shows the large HI ring, which is overlaid on the optical image in white. The pink shows the UV image from GALEX. Figure from [Bournaud et al. \(2007\)](#).

amounts of HI gas around the host galaxy, in this case IC 2497. Some of this gas from the interaction can also be fed to the central black hole which will get activated and/or the black hole could have been already active. This tidal gas around the host galaxy can then get photoionized by the central AGN leading to such structures of ionized gas. [Józsa et al. \(2009\)](#), indeed found such large HI clouds encompassing Hanny's Voorwerp. [Keel et al. \(2012b\)](#) did a systematic search of such structures with the help of Galaxy

Figure 1.12: Colour composite image of Hanny's Voorwerp with the [OIII] mapped to green and $H\alpha$ + [NII] mapped to red. The inset image shows the larger field of view around Hanny's Voorwerp which also shows the nearby galaxy IC 2497. Figure from [Keel et al. \(2012a\)](#).

Zoo volunteers in a large sample of SDSS imaging survey. They have found 19 more such cases of Hanny's Voorwerp. In Chapter 4, I will describe some more new cases of candidate Hanny's Voorewerp which we found the SDSS MaNGA IFU data.

The Leo ring:

Figure 1.13: Left Panel: The Leo ring with the HI gas distribution shown in brown overlaid on the deep deep optical CFHT g, r, i colour composite image. Right Panel: Zoom-in image on the various UV knots identified in GALEX by Thilker et al. (2009) shown using white contours. Notice the various blue optical counterparts identified in the CFHT image coincident on the UV condensations. Figure from Michel-Dansac et al. (2010).

In all the previous cases the outskirts of galaxies showed multiple prominent components, such as ionized and neutral gas, and stars. However, there is one curious case of a very large HI dominated ring with negligible number of stars in it, the Leo ring (Schneider, 1985; Schneider et al., 1983, 1989). Fig. 1.13 shows the distribution of HI around the host galaxy NGC3384/M105 in brown overlaid on the deep optical CFHT g, r, i colour composite image. Due to the lack of any optical counterpart, it was long believed that the gas in this ring has a primordial origin having very little metallicity and hence no star formation. However, Thilker et al. (2009) found several

1. INTRODUCTION

UV condensations in this ring suggesting recent star formation, although very faint. [Michel-Dansac et al. \(2010\)](#) then found several optical counterparts to the UV. Using the UV and optical photometry they estimated the metallicity of this ring and found that it is consistent with the gas having a galactic origin. They also showed that such a ring can be formed by collisions, possibly with the nearby galaxy M96.

Such a ring is extremely rare, with only one known so far. In [Chapter 5](#), we will show a second case of such an HI dominated ring around the galaxy AGC203001.

1.8 Outline of the thesis

This thesis makes use of multiwavelength (UV to radio) data to study galaxies with the main focus on star formation and quenching. This study is divided in two parts: SF and quenching within galaxies and on SF, ionized gas and neutral gas in galaxy outskirts. [Chapters 2](#) and [3](#) address the first part of the thesis. Here [Chapter 2](#) is ‘On the interdependence of galaxy morphology, SF and environment in massive galaxies in the nearby Universe’. As we have seen earlier on in this introduction, the morphology, SF properties and the environment of a galaxy are closely correlated to each other. We addressed the question of which of the three is the primary driver for massive galaxies in the local Universe. We have also found the visual morphologies of galaxies which populate the galaxy MS and addressed the question of what are the morphologies of galaxies that are currently undergoing the quenching and what is their dependence on environment. This Chapter is based on [Bait et al. \(2017\)](#). In [Chapter 3](#), contrary to the previous study, we focus on a population of extremely low mass, compact and starbursting dwarf galaxies, which were recently discovered by [Yang et al. \(2017\)](#) termed as “blueberry” galaxies. These galaxies are thought to be the local analogues of high redshift faint Lyman- α emitters. These galaxies are very rare and we do not yet know what leads to them having such compact sizes and high levels of SF. Here we mainly study their radio continuum properties using the uGMRT. Particularly, we study their rest frame radio luminosity based SFRs and compare them with the UV, optical and IR based SFRs. In the following two chapters, [Chapter 4](#) and [Chapter 5](#), we shift the focus to the galaxy outskirts. In [Chapter 4](#) (based on [\(Bait et al., 2019b\)](#)) we use the recently released SDSS IV MaNGA IFU data to search for large-scale H α emission in the galaxy outskirts in the entire MaNGA data-release. We find a peculiar sample of six outlying

H α emitting galaxies which we study in detail, particularly the cause of photoionization in such systems. In Chapter 5, we consider a typical massive ETG galaxy with no signs of active SF, like those studied in Chapter 2. But it host large amounts of neutral hydrogen as found from single dish measurements from the ALFALFA survey. We mapped this galaxy in HI using the legacy GMRT to find that the gas is distributed in the form of a large ring. We also obtained a deep image (~ 28 mag/arcsec²) of this galaxy using the Megacam instrument on CFHT telescope to find that the HI ring has no bright optical counterpart. We discuss in detail on the formation mechanisms of such large optically devoid HI rings. In Chapter 6, we will finally summarize the two parts of this thesis and will briefly discuss how some of the open questions raised in this thesis can be answered using some of the upcoming telescopes and surveys.

1. INTRODUCTION

2

On the interdependence of galaxy morphology, star formation, and environment in massive galaxies in the nearby Universe

This chapter is based on [Bait et al. \(2017\)](#).

2.1 Introduction

With the advent of large area galaxy surveys, like the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS, [York et al. \(2000\)](#)), it was found that in the local Universe, galaxies show a bi-modal distribution on the optical color-magnitude diagram ([Baldry et al., 2004, 2006](#); [Kauffmann et al., 2003a](#); [Strateva et al., 2001](#)) with actively star forming “blue cloud” galaxies and passively evolving “red sequence” galaxies. The region between these two populations is defined as the “green valley” ([Wyder et al., 2007a](#)). It is believed that the green valley of galaxies is the transition zone between the blue cloud and the red sequence ([Mendez et al., 2011](#); [Schiminovich et al., 2007](#); [Wyder et al., 2007a](#)), and contains galaxies that have undergone recent quenching of star formation ([Salim et al., 2007](#)). Along with the star-formation properties, green valley galaxies also have morphological properties (quantified by the value of the Sérsic index) intermediate between star-forming and passive galaxies ([Schiminovich et al., 2007](#)). Thus, green valley galaxies can give us in-

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

sight into the process of quenching and its dependence on morphology and other galaxy parameters. Moreover, as discussed in Sec. 1.3 and 1.4, the various galaxy properties e.g., morphologies, stellar mass, gas properties and environment show correlations with each other. And it is not clear which of these are fundamental.

Although most of these parameters are quantified directly, galaxy morphology remains to be the most difficult to quantify. This is because, finding the visual morphologies of millions of galaxies from large scale galaxy surveys is difficult. Hence, several recent studies on star formation have mostly ignored the morphologies of galaxies. Galaxy Zoo (Lintott et al., 2008) has classified the morphologies of a large number of galaxies, but gives a crude classification in terms of only late-type (which includes all types of spiral galaxies) and early-type (ellipticals and S0s) galaxies. On the contrary, in our study we use the detailed visual morphologies (in 12 types – ellipticals, S0-, S0, S0/a, Sa, Sab, Sb, Sbc, Sc, Scd, Sd) from the Nair & Abraham (2010a) catalogue, and hence we can distinguish between different kinds of spiral galaxies. We can also differentiate between ellipticals and S0s which the Galaxy Zoo morphologies do not.

In this chapter, we want to revisit the relation between classical visual morphologies and star formation in the modern context of the MS of star-forming galaxies, the transitioning population of green valley galaxies, and the quenched galaxies, and also as a function of environment from the low to high densities. We use multiwavelength data from UV-optical-mid IR and model the SED of ~ 7000 galaxies to estimate the stellar mass and SFRs. Due to the availability of UV data we can also define a green valley. In particular, we want to study the relation between sSFR-morphology, morphology-density, and density-sSFR. Since all three of the parameters, morphological T-type, sSFR, and environmental density are known to correlate with each other, in each of the correlations we also study the differential effect of the third parameter. Further, in order to determine which correlation is the strongest, we compute the partial correlation coefficient for each of the three correlations while keeping the third parameter as the control variable.

This chapter is organised as follows. In Section 2.2, we discuss our sample selection and our multiwavelength data from UV-optical-IR. We then briefly discuss the spectral energy distribution (SED) fitting technique using which we derive the stellar mass and SFR for our whole sample. We also discuss the morphological classifications and environmental density measurements for our whole sample. We then show our results

and discuss them in Section 2.3. Our main results on the relation between star formation and morphology are in Section 2.3.1. In Section 2.3.2, we study the morphology-density relation for our sample of galaxies and separately study this relation for star-forming, green valley and quenched galaxies. In Section 2.3.3, we study the relation between the remaining two parameters, log sSFR and environmental density. In Section 2.3.4, we then analyse which correlation between the three parameters, morphological T-type, sSFR, and environmental density is strongest by computing the partial correlation coefficient. Finally, we summarize our results and conclude in Section 2.4.

Throughout this chapter we use the standard concordance cosmology with $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$ and $h_{100} = 0.7$.

2.2 Sample selection and data analysis

2.2.1 Sample selection

Our sample is drawn from the [Nair & Abraham \(2010a\)](#) (hereafter NA10) catalogue of detailed visual morphological classification of 14,034 galaxies. NA10 galaxies were selected from the Sloan digital sky survey (SDSS) DR4 with spectroscopic redshift in the range $0.01 < z < 0.1$, and extinction corrected apparent magnitude limit of $g < 16$ mag. For galaxies in our sample, we use optical imaging data from the SDSS DR12 ([Alam et al., 2015](#)) in u, g, r, i , and z bands. In order to have a better constraint on recent star formation, we make use of Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX) data in the far-UV (FUV) and near-UV (NUV) filters. We use near-IR data from the 2 Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS) in J, H , and K bands ([Skrutskie et al., 2006](#)), wherein we use the model photometry. Mid IR data are taken from the Wide-Field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE; [Wright et al. \(2010\)](#)) in all four channels - W1, W2, W3, and W4. We construct our sample by cross-matching the NA10 catalogue with archival data from GALEX, SDSS, 2MASS, and WISE which gives us 7,831 galaxies. Of these, we have flux measurements in all the 14 bands for 6,819 galaxies. For 594 galaxies we have flux measurements in 13 bands due to missing flux in the W4 filter, and for 418 galaxies we have flux measurement in 10 bands due to missing fluxes in all the 4 WISE filters. For all of these galaxies, we also have local environmental density information from [Baldry et al. \(2006\)](#).

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

All our sources are resolved in the four WISE bands and are also associated with the 2MASS extended source catalogue, hence we calculate the fluxes using elliptical aperture photometry measurement (w?gmag column in the WISE catalogue). Furthermore, the WISE pipeline measurements for resolved sources are known to be systematically fainter by approximately 0.35 mag, 0.28 mag, 0.44 mag and 0.3 mag in the W1, W2, W3 and W4 band respectively, and we correct for these offsets¹ (Brown et al., 2014) before calculating the fluxes. After these corrections are made, as mentioned in the WISE documentation¹, these fluxes still have an error of $\sim 20\%$.

2.2.2 Morphological Classification

The visual morphologies in our final sample are taken from our parent sample of NA10. In NA10 the authors have done a careful morphological classification for every galaxy using SDSS images in all the five bands u, g, r, i, and z. NA10 can differentiate between different kinds of spirals galaxies into Sa, Sab, Sb, Sbc, Sc, Scd, Sdm, Sm, and Im. It can also differentiate between lenticular galaxies into S0- , S0, and S0/a. Galaxies from NA10 which have somewhat doubtful classification (denoted by ?), and galaxies with highly uncertain classification (denoted by :) are not included in our sample. The comparison of the morphological classification from NA10 with the RC3 catalogue (de Vaucouleurs et al., 1991) is shown in Table 2.1. Since NA10 does not differentiate between c0, E0, and E+ we group them together into ellipticals (Es). Similarly, NA10 does not differentiate between S0 and S0+ morphologies and hence we group them together and refer them as S0. Thus, in our classification scheme, we have three types of lenticular galaxies, S0-, S0, and S0/a. Figure 2.1, shows the number of galaxies for each of the morphological classes in our sample. We have very few galaxies from Sdm-Im morphologies since our sample contains only massive galaxies and hence we remove them from our sample. This reduces our sample to 7,763 galaxies. The authors in NA10 have classified their entire sample twice and have estimated a mean deviation of less than 0.5 T-types.

We will use such a detailed morphological classification only in Section 2.3.1.3. For all other sections we will group together all types of lenticular galaxies (S0-, S0, and

¹http://wise2.ipac.caltech.edu/docs/release/allsky/expsup/sec6_3e.html

Figure 2.1: Number of galaxies in our sample with various morphologies, ranging from Es (red), S0s (green), and spirals (blue). We group together spirals ranging from Sa-Sbc and refer to them as early-type spirals (ETS), and Sc-Sd types which we refer as late-type spirals (LTS). Since we have only massive galaxies in our sample, we have very few number of late-type spiral galaxies. Sdm, Sm, and Im morphologies are removed from our final sample.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Table 2.1: Corresponding morphological T-types from the NA10 and RC3 catalogues.

Class	c0	E0	E+	S0-	S0	S0+	S0/a	Sa	Sab	Sb	Sbc	Sc	Scd	Sd	Sdm	Sm	Im
NA10	-5	-5	-5	-3	-2	-2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RC3	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

S0/a) and refer them as S0s. And within spiral galaxies we make two groups: early-type spirals (ETS) ranging from Sa-Sbc types, and late-type spirals (LTS) ranging from Sc-Sd types.

2.2.3 Deriving stellar masses and SFRs using SED fitting

For each of the 7,763 galaxies in our sample, we model the SED, using the publicly available Multi-wavelength Analysis of Galaxy Physical Properties (MAGPHYS) code (da Cunha et al., 2008) (dC08 hereafter). We will briefly describe the SED modeling done by MAGPHYS here; for a detailed description, we refer the reader to dC08.

We used the MAGPHYS SED fitting technique to model the individual SED using 14 bands, ranging from UV-midIR, of 7,763 galaxies in our sample. Following the suggestion of Hayward & Smith (2015) of using a conservative value for the critical χ^2 of 5, we removed all the galaxies with higher χ^2 from our sample. This criterion reduces the sample to 7020 galaxies. Figure 2.2 shows a typical example of a good fit SED in our sample. Notice that due to lack of data points the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) emission features and FIR dust emission are not very well constrained and hence we refrain from using dust mass and dust luminosity in our analysis. We use the median values (the 50th percentile of the marginalized posterior probability distribution function) of stellar mass and SFR for each galaxy in our sample (following dc08). For every galaxy we also estimate the uncertainty in estimating the stellar mass and SFR using the 16th and 84th percentile of the marginalized posterior probability distribution, which will be the lower and upper error bars respectively, following dc08.

Figure 2.3, shows the histogram of stellar mass for the sample for 7020 galaxies. As our focus in this study is only on massive galaxies and their dependence on sSFR, morphology and environment. Hence, we restrict our sample to only massive galaxies ($\log M_*/M_\odot \geq 10$). The dashed vertical line in Figure 2.3 shows the stellar mass cut. This finally reduces our sample to 6194 galaxies, which we will use in this work. We caution the reader that the results presented in this study are valid only for massive galaxies; these could significantly change for lower mass galaxies, where different physical processes may play a role in shaping their nature. Figure 2.4, shows the distribution of sSFR for our final sample. The sSFR is obtained by dividing the SFR by the stellar mass for each galaxy. The sSFR is a proxy for the star formation history of the galaxy,

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

where a high value of sSFR suggests recent star formation and a low value is an indicator of an older stellar population with little or no recent star formation. Therefore, following [Salim \(2014\)](#), we define star-forming galaxies with $\log \text{sSFR} \geq -10.8$, green valley galaxies with $-11.8 < \log \text{sSFR} < -10.8$, and quenched galaxies with $\log \text{sSFR} \leq -11.8$.

2.2.4 Environmental Density

We use the local surface galaxy density from [Baldry et al. \(2006\)](#) as a measure of the environment. It is determined using, $\Sigma_N = N/\pi d_N^2$, where d_N is the distance to the N th nearest neighbour which are within the redshift range $\pm \Delta z c = 1000$ km/s for galaxies with spectroscopic redshifts or within the 95% confidence limit for galaxies with photometric redshifts only. Following [Baldry et al. \(2006\)](#), we use the best estimate, Σ , obtained by averaging the Σ_N for the 4th and 5th nearest neighbour. Figure 2.5 shows the histogram of $\log \Sigma$ for our final sample of galaxies. Further we split our sample into low density ($\log \Sigma \text{ (Mpc}^{-2}) < -0.5$), intermediate density ($-0.5 < \log \Sigma \text{ (Mpc}^{-2}) < 0.5$), and high densities ($\log \Sigma \text{ (Mpc}^{-2}) > 0.5$).

2.3 Results and Discussion

Galaxy morphology, sSFR, and environmental density are correlated with each other. It is possible that the correlation between any two of the parameters is driven by the dependence on the third parameter. Hence, in each of the following subsections we study the correlation between any two of the parameters along with the differential effect of the third parameter. We also compute the partial correlation coefficient for each the three correlations while keeping the third parameter as the control variable.

2.3.1 Relation between morphology and specific star-formation rate

In this section, we study the dependence of morphology on the sSFR- M_* plane. We then examine the fraction of galaxies of different morphologies at fixed sSFR, and also the differential effect of environment on it.

Figure 2.2: Shows a typical good fit SED in our sample. The x-axis is the observed frame wavelength and y-axis is the luminosity in solar units. The dots are the observed fluxes in 14 bands from GALEX FUV and NUV (blue), SDSS u, g, r, i, z (green), 2MASS J, H, K (yellow) and the four WISE bands (red). GALEX, SDSS, and 2MASS points show 1σ errors calculated using the magnitude errors from the corresponding catalogs. The four WISE bands have errors of 20%. The green line shows the best fit SED. Notice that the PAH emission around $10 \mu\text{m}$ is not well constrained due to the sparse sampling in this region. Similarly, the dust emission peak around $100 \mu\text{m}$ is not well constrained due to lack of far infrared observations.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Figure 2.3: Histogram of stellar mass derived using SED fitting from MAGPHYS. In the final sample only galaxies with $\log M_*/M_\odot \geq 10$ are included.

Figure 2.4: Histogram of sSFR, obtained by dividing the SFR with the stellar mass for each galaxy (note that the x-axis is inverted), showing a bi-modal distribution. We define the star-forming region ($\log sSFR \geq -10.8$), green valley ($-10.8 > \log sSFR > -11.8$), and quenched region ($\log sSFR \leq -11.8$) following [Salim \(2014\)](#).

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Figure 2.5: Histogram of local environmental density ($\log \Sigma \text{ (Mpc}^{-2}\text{)}$) for our final sample of galaxies. The dashed lines separate the sample into low, intermediate, and high densities.

Figure 2.6: Left Panel: Dependence of specific star formation rate on stellar mass for our entire sample. The contours shows the $1/V_{max}$ -corrected density of galaxies on the stellar mass and sSFR plane. The errorbars on the top-right corner shows the typical uncertainties in the estimating the stellar mass and sSFR from MAGPHYS. The region between the horizontal green lines defines the green valley from [Salim \(2014\)](#). Galaxies above the upper green line ($\log sSFR = -10.8$) are termed as star forming, and those lying under the lower green line ($\log sSFR = -11.8$) are termed as quenched galaxies. This shows the star-forming main sequence of galaxies, the quenched region at $\log M_*/M_\odot \geq 10.5$, and a well separated transition zone (green-valley) between the two populations. Right Panel: Same as the left-panel after splitting our whole sample, where top left: LTS, top right: ETS, bottom-left: S0s, bottom-right: Es. The shading in blue shows the $1/V_{max}$ -corrected density of galaxies in each morphological class. The contours are from the left panel for the full sample. We see a morphological dependance of the distribution of galaxies on sSFR- M_* plane where the LTS are in the lower mass end ($\log M_*/M_\odot \leq 10.5$) star-forming sequence, ETS are in the high mass end of the star-forming sequence and near the green valley, S0s have a large population in the quenched region and a tail in the green valley, and the Es are mostly quenched.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Figure 2.7: Dependence of specific star formation rate on stellar mass for ETS further split into more detailed morphologies. The region between the horizontal green lines is the green valley. The density map shows the location of galaxies with different morphologies. Top left: Sa spirals, Top right: Sab spirals, Bottom-left: Sb, Bottom-right: Sbc. As we move along the Hubble sequence from Sa to Sbc, galaxies move from the quenched region through the green valley to the star-forming region.

Table 2.2: Morphological fraction of galaxies which are in star-forming, green valley and quenched regions.

	Star-forming	Green-valley	Quenched
Total No.	2184	1288	2789
Es	0.3%	8.3%	46.2%
S0s	11.8%	39.9%	42.1%
Sa	10.7%	18.4%	7.8%
Sab	11.0%	11.2%	1.3%
Sb	26.8%	15.1%	2.3%
Sbc	18.6%	4.4%	0.3%
Sc-Sd	20.8%	2.7%	0.0%

2.3.1.1 Dependence of morphology on the sSFR- M_* plane

We plot sSFR and stellar mass (M_*) for our sample in the left panel of Figure 2.6. Most of the galaxies in our sample have a redshift below 0.07, and hence mass-incompleteness is not a major issue. We nevertheless correct for the mass-incompleteness in the sample using the $1/V_{max}$ method (Schmidt, 1968). In this method we simply weight each galaxy by the maximum volume it can be detected referred by V_{max} . The weight for each galaxy is then $1/V_{max}$. We use the $1/V_{max}$ provided by the NA10 catalogue for every galaxy in our sample. In the left panel of Figure 2.6 the contours shows the $1/V_{max}$ -corrected density of galaxies on the stellar mass and sSFR plane. On the top-right corner the error bars shows the typical uncertainties in the estimation of stellar mass and sSFR. In order to estimate the typical uncertainty, we first find the median value of both the 16th and 84th percentile from the marginalized posterior probability distribution function for each parameter. We then take the mean of these two values which represent the error bar. The typical uncertainty in $\log M_*$ is about 0.048 dex, and in \log sSFR is about 0.125 dex.

Following Salim (2014), galaxies above the upper green line (\log sSFR = -10.8) are termed as star forming galaxies (SFGs), and those lying under the lower green line (\log sSFR = -11.8) are termed as quenched galaxies (QGs). The region between the horizontal green lines in Figure 2.6 defines the green valley. We clearly find a bimodality in the distribution of sSFR also previously noticed in the literature (Brinch-

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

mann et al., 2004; Peng et al., 2010; Salim et al., 2007; Weinmann et al., 2006; Wetzel et al., 2012).

We then separate our sample by morphology in to four groups: late-type spirals (LTS), early-type spirals (ETS), S0s, and Ellipticals (Es). In LTS, we group together Sc, Scd, and Sd morphologies, and in ETS we group together Sa, Sab, Sb, and Sbc morphologies. We then plot each of these groups separately on the sSFR- M_* plot as shown in right panel of Figure 2.6 in shades of blue. In this figure, the $1/V_{max}$ -corrected density map shows the position of a particular group on the sSFR- M_* plane and the contours are repeated for the full sample from the left panel of Figure 2.6. The region between the green lines is the green valley. The star forming sequence is populated mostly by LTS at the low mass end ($\log M_*/M_\odot \leq 10.5$) and by the ETS at the high mass end. ETS with high mass are also present in the green valley and in the quenched region. Es and S0s populate the region defined for quenched galaxies in the sSFR- M_* plane with the S0s having a tail in the green valley. Table 2.2 shows the percentage of galaxies of a given morphology in the star-forming, green valley and quenched regions. As expected, the star-forming region contains a very small number of Es (0.3%) and a small number of S0s (11.8%). ETS, comprising Sa, Sab, Sb, and Sbc morphologies, constitute 67.1% and LTS constitute 20.1% of the galaxies in the star-forming region. Thus, in the local Universe majority of the recent star formation in massive galaxies happens in ETS and LTS. On the other hand, the quenched region predominantly contains Es (46.2%) and S0s (42.1%) with a small contribution from ETS (11.7%) and almost no contribution from LTS. In the green valley, majority is populated by ETS (49.1%) and S0s (39.9%) and a small percent are Es (8.3%) and LTS (2.7%). Bouquin et al. (2015) also found that in the green valley, defined using GALEX data, S0-Sa galaxies are more common. We find that, in the local Universe, massive galaxies in the green valley are predominantly disk galaxies with a prominent bulge. Further, similar results were also seen from the Galaxy Zoo (GZ) project by Schawinski et al. (2014) which identified galaxies as only early-types and late-types. Since we have detailed morphological classification, we can have a closer look at the morphology of galaxies undergoing quenching. In particular, a comparison of Fig. 2.6 with (Schawinski et al., 2014, see Fig. 3) shows that for massive galaxies, most of the GZ late-type galaxies in the green valley and quenched region are likely to have Sa-Sb morphologies. The small number of GZ early-type galaxies in the green valley are mostly S0 galaxies.

In Figure 2.7, we split the ETS into their morphological subtypes to explore their distribution on the sSFR- M_* plane. We can see that as the bulge becomes more prominent when we move along Sbc to Sa morphology, galaxies gradually make a transition to the quenched region through the green valley. Table 2.2 also shows that the star-forming region comprises higher percentage of Sbc and Sb galaxies than Sab and Sa. Whereas in the green valley there is a higher percentage of Sa, Sab, and Sb galaxies relative to Sbc galaxies. Also, in the quenched region SAs galaxies are more numerous than Sab, Sb, and Sbc. The main systemic difference between these different subtypes of ETS is in the size and luminosity of the bulge component. The variation we see points towards the importance of the bulge component in the quenching of galaxies. A similar result was also found by Bluck et al. (2014), wherein they found that the bulge mass correlates most with the passive state of a galaxy. Mendez et al. (2011) studied the morphologies of green valley galaxies in the redshift range $0.4 < z < 1.2$ and found that 14% are in merger, 51% are late-type galaxies, and 35% are early-type galaxies. Under the simplistic assumption that all of the merging galaxies in that redshift range will eventually transform into early-type galaxies, the fraction of green valley early-type galaxies will increase to 49%, which is very close to the fraction of early-type galaxies (Es and S0s) in the green valley that we find, which is 48.1%. In reality, the situation may be much more complicated wherein the environment also plays a role in transforming late-type galaxies into early-type galaxies.

2.3.1.2 Fraction of galaxies of different morphologies at fixed sSFR, and the differential effect of environment

We study the fraction of LTS, ETS, S0s, and Es in bins of log sSFR (Fig 2.8). Here again we correct for the Malmquist bias, using the $1/V_{max}$ method, while calculating the fractions. In each of the log sSFR bin, we find the fraction of each morphological type as follows (following van den Bosch et al., 2008, eq. 2):

$$f_{\text{morph}|sSFR} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N_a} w_i}{\sum_{j=1}^{j=N_b} w_j}, \quad (2.1)$$

where w_i is the weight for each galaxy calculated using $1/V_{max}$. And N_a is the total number of galaxies of a particular morphological type for a given log sSFR bin. N_b is the total number of galaxies in that log sSFR bin. In all the sections that follow, all

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Figure 2.8: Fraction of galaxies of different morphological type (LTS in blue, ETS in green, S0s in red, and Es in brown) as a function of log sSFR. The errorbars are jackknife errors. Fraction of LTS and ETS decline with decreasing log sSFR, which coincides with an increase in the fraction of S0s and Es. S0s on the other hand also show a second population, which is actively forming stars. See text for a detailed discussion.

Figure 2.9: Fraction of galaxies of different morphological type (the colour code is same as Fig. 2.8) in each panel. And in each panel we further split with environmental density in terms of low density ($\log \Sigma \leq -0.5$)-filled line, intermediate ($-0.5 < \log \Sigma < 0.5$) density-dashed line, and high density ($\log \Sigma \geq 0.5$)-dotted line. The errorbars are jackknife errors. Notice that fraction of ETS at fixed log sSFR does not change significantly with environment. Es are more abundant in intermediate and high densities. LTS are more abundant in low and intermediate densities. There continue to be two populations of S0s (green valley/quenched S0s and star forming S0s) in all environments.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

the fractions are $1/V_{max}$ -corrected using this method. The errors on these fractions are calculated using the jackknife technique following the approach described in [van den Bosch et al. \(2008\)](#).

It is interesting to see in [Fig. 2.8](#) that the trends for different morphological types are quite different. In accord with earlier results, LTS have a higher fraction (~ 0.3) for $\log \text{sSFR} \sim -10$ and there is a sharp decline in the fraction of LTS with decreasing $\log \text{sSFR}$. Meanwhile, the fraction of ETS shows a steep increase as $\log \text{sSFR}$ decreases, with a peak at the boundary of the star-forming and green valley regions. This is followed by a sharp decline in the green valley and then settling at about 10% in the quenched region. Such a decline in the ETS and LTS coincides with an sharp increase in the fraction of S0s and Es with decreasing $\log \text{sSFR}$. A simple interpretation is a morphological transformation of LTS and ETS to S0s and Es, which is accompanied by a decline in the sSFR. Our results are in agreement with the GZ based study of galaxy morphology and color ([Skibba et al., 2009](#), see [Fig. 5](#)) where they see a correlation between morphology and color such that the likelihood of early-type galaxy increases as the galaxy color becomes redder. We can put a stronger constraint on the morphologies by suggesting that they are ETS transforming in S0 galaxies in the green valley. Several physical processes can lead to such morphological transformations from late-type to early-type galaxies which also quench the star formation in these galaxies (see [Boselli & Gavazzi, 2006](#), for a review and the references therein). This has also been observed in high redshift, upto ~ 1 ([Kovač et al., 2010](#)). Interestingly, there are also two distinct class of S0s galaxies: one which is in the green valley and quenched region and thus hosting an older stellar population, and the other which is actively forming stars (with $\log \text{sSFR}$ in the range $[-9, -8]$) hosting a younger stellar population. The latter class of S0s are almost as abundant as the LTS in that $\log \text{sSFR}$ bin. [Barway et al. \(2013\)](#) have found similar populations of young and old S0s using UV-near IR colours of galaxies. [Johnston et al. \(2014\)](#) have found S0s in clusters with a younger bulge thus proposing that the final episode of star formation might be happening in the central regions of cluster S0s.

Some of the physical processes which lead to changes in the star formation and morphologies of galaxies are thought to depend on environment which hosts these galaxies, e.g. ram-pressure stripping ([Gunn & Gott, 1972](#)), galaxy harassment ([Farouki & Shapiro, 1981](#); [Moore et al., 1996](#)), and strangulation ([Larson et al., 1980](#)). Hence,

Table 2.3: Fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies each morphological type.

	E	S0	Sa	Sab	Sb	Sbc	Sc-Sd
Total No. of galaxies	1478	1787	671	429	846	502	548
Star forming galaxies	0.4%	13.5%	34.1%	56.9%	69.6%	86.1%	92.5%
Green valley galaxies	7.9%	26.9%	34.8%	34.4%	23.2%	12.1%	7.2%
Quiescent galaxies	91.7 %	59.6%	31.1%	8.7%	7.2%	1.8%	0.3%

we need to study the impact of the environment on the relation between morphology and sSFR.

To do this, we split our sample into low density ($\log \Sigma \leq -0.5$), intermediate ($-0.5 < \log \Sigma < 0.5$) density, and high density ($\log \Sigma \geq 0.5$) environments and study the fraction of different morphologies as a function of \log sSFR (Fig. 2.9). We notice that environmental density does not significantly alter the fraction of individual morphologies as a function of \log sSFR, except for Es, which are more abundant in intermediate and high density environments. This is a manifestation of the morphology-density relation (Dressler, 1980). The two populations of S0s seen in Figure 2.8 continue to be present in all the three environments. S0s in green valley and the quenched region show similar trends in all density environments, albeit with large uncertainties.

This result, along with our analysis presented in Section 2.3.4, indicates that morphology is strongly correlated with sSFR, independent of the environment.

2.3.1.3 Fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies at fixed morphological T-type, and the differential effect of environment

We divide our whole sample of galaxies into three parts as star-forming (\log sSFR ≥ -10.8), green valley ($-10.8 > \log$ sSFR > -11.8) and quenched (\log sSFR ≤ -11.8). We then plot the $1/V_{max}$ -corrected fraction of galaxies in each of these types for a fixed morphological T-type (Fig. 2.10) using the same method illustrated in the earlier subsection. As we use all the morphological subtypes in this section, we have S0s in three stages: S0- (S0s with a smooth light profile), S0 (S0s with some structure in their light profile), and S0/a (S0s in a transition from Sa spirals). Spiral galaxies range from Sa

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Figure 2.10: Fraction of star-forming (blue), green valley (green) and quenched (red) galaxies for a fixed morphological T-type going to Es to Im spirals. The errorbars are jackknife errors. Notice that the quenched fraction decreases as we move from early-type galaxies to late-type. The fraction of green valley galaxies increases from Es to S0s and upto Sab spirals beyond which there is a steep decline. Interestingly Sa spirals shows equal fractions of all three stages of star-formation.

Figure 2.11: Fraction of star-forming (blue), green valley (green) and quenched (red) galaxies for a fixed morphological T-type shown in the left, middle, and right panel respectively. In each panel we further split in three environmental bins: low density ($\log \Sigma \leq -0.5$)-filled line, intermediate ($-0.5 < \log \Sigma < 0.5$) density-dashed line, and high density ($\log \Sigma \geq 0.5$)-dotted line. The errorbars are jackknife errors. Notice that in all environments as we go from early-type galaxies to late-type the quenched fraction decreases. However, the effect of environment on quenching is most apparent on Sa and S0s, wherein their quenched fraction increases substantially in high density environments. Interestingly, in low density environments the fraction of star-forming S0/a galaxies is high.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

to Sd.

The overall trend seen in Figure 2.10, that as we go from early-type to late-type galaxies the quenched fraction decreases, is well expected. However, it is interesting to see that some of the Es are in the green valley (7.9%), and a negligible fraction of them are star-forming (0.4%). These Es may have recently undergone gas-rich minor/major merger which leads to triggering of star-formation in these galaxies. About 70% of the S0– and 65% of the S0 galaxies are quenched. Thereafter, there is a rapid fall in the fraction of quenched S0/a galaxies (and hence a corresponding increase in the star-forming and green valley S0/a). Further, the quenched fraction of Sa spirals only slightly decreases, and interestingly it is almost equal to both the fraction of green valley and star-forming Sa spirals. Spirals from Sab to Sd show a rapid decline in the quenched fraction and green valley. These fractions in terms of percentages are summarized in Table 2.3.

We also examine the role of environment in the quenched fraction of a fixed morphological type. We plot the fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies for a fixed morphological T-type in three different panels. In each panel, we further split in terms of three environmental bins: low, intermediate, and high density (Fig 2.11). The quenched fraction of Es in all the three environments remains high and almost the same with a small fraction of them in the green valley. LTS (Sc-Sd) remain mostly star forming in all environments.

Interestingly, quenched ETS are present in all environments and their quenched fraction increases with increasing environment density. The strongest effect of environment is seen on the Sa spirals and S0/a galaxies, wherein their quenched fraction increases with increasing environmental density. Note that the fraction of quenched Sa spirals which is around 30% in low and intermediate density environments, suddenly rises to about 50% in the high density environment. This shows that environment does play a role in quenching of Sa spirals, however the physical process of quenching is likely to be gentle since their spiral arms are intact. This rules out ram-pressure stripping for the quenching of these galaxies, and makes a gentler process like strangulation more likely. Our results are in agreement with those of [van den Bosch et al. \(2008\)](#) and [Peng et al. \(2015\)](#), where the authors argue for strangulation as the dominant quenching mechanism in local galaxies.

The quenched fraction of S0/a galaxies, which are in transition from Sa to S0, also increases with increasing environmental density. S0– and S0 are mostly quenched in all environments with their fraction increasing by about 10% in high density environment. The abundance of quenched S0– and S0 in intermediate and particularly in low density environments is intriguing. According to Baldry et al. (2006) (see their Fig. 9 caption), $\log \Sigma > 0.8 \text{ Mpc}^{-2}$ corresponds to cluster like environments. Thus, our definition of low and intermediate densities, $\log \Sigma < 0.5 \text{ Mpc}^{-2}$, will correspond to field and group like environment. Thus, at low densities, ram-pressure stripping may not be a dominant mechanism in the formation of S0 galaxies. Interestingly, in low density environments about 30% of the S0/a galaxies are star-forming. Even though this fraction decreases with increasing density, in intermediate and high densities about 20% and 10% of the S0/a galaxies are star-forming, respectively. About 10% of the S0 and S0– are star-forming in the low density environment, and their fraction decreases when we go to the high density environment. The presence of such star-forming S0s in all environments gives rise to the second population of star-forming S0s previously seen in Figure 2.9.

Thus, we conclude that for massive galaxies in the local Universe, only the quenched fraction of S0/a and S0 galaxies show a significant dependence on environmental density. Further, the fact that the quenched fraction of S0/a galaxies is more close to that of Sa spirals and much lower than that of S0 and S0–, shows that S0/a galaxies likely undergo a different quenching process than that of S0 and S0– galaxies.

2.3.2 Relation between morphology and local environment

Next we study the dependence of morphology on the local environmental density. We follow a similar procedure as in Section 2.3.1. We first examine the fraction of galaxies with different morphologies in fixed environmental bins. We then study the differential effect of sSFR on this relation.

In Figure 2.12, we plot the the $1/V_{max}$ -corrected fraction of Es, S0s, ETS, and LTS galaxies in fixed environmental bins. In high density environments ($\log \Sigma > 0.5$) the fraction of ETS decreases and the fraction of Es increases. This is the well known morphology-density relation (Dressler, 1980). Interestingly, the fraction of S0s does not increase as we go to high densities. One reason might be that we only have massive galaxies in our sample, and the effects of environment (e.g. ram-pressure stripping), which can transform a spiral into an S0, is stronger for low-mass galaxies (Bekki, 2009;

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Figure 2.12: Fraction of LTS (blue), ETS (green), S0s (red), and Es (brown) in fixed environmental bins. The errors shown are jackknife errors. Notice the fraction of ETS decreases, and the fraction of Es increases in the high density environments.

Figure 2.13: Fraction of LTS (blue), ETS (green), S0s (red), and Es (brown) in fixed environmental bins split in three parts: star-forming galaxies in the left panel, green valley galaxies in the middle panel, and quenched galaxies in the right panel. The errors shown are jackknife errors. Notice the presence of star forming S0s at all environmental densities. ETS and S0s populate the green valley galaxies in all environments, except in the highest environmental density bin. Further, the fraction of green Es increase with increasing environmental density. See the text for a detailed discussion.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Table 2.4: Fraction of galaxies of different morphological types in low, intermediate, and high density environments.

	Low density	Intermediate density	High density
Total No.	2158	2968	1135
Es	12.0%	21.4%	42.7%
S0s	29.2%	31.9%	31.4%
Sa	13.4%	10.9%	7.1%
Sab	7.9%	6.9%	4.5%
Sb	15.7%	14.1%	8.4%
Sbc	9.4%	7.9%	3.5%
Sc-Sd	12.4%	6.9%	2.4%

Table 2.5: Fraction of galaxies in low, intermediate, and high densities for different morphological types.

	E	S0	Sa	Sab	Sb	Sbc	Sc-Sd
Total No. of galaxies	1478	1787	671	429	846	502	548
Low density	18.2%	31.8%	40.8%	38.9%	38.8%	41.3%	52.7%
Intermediate density	46.8%	48.3%	47.6%	49.0%	50.0%	50.3%	41.8%
High density	35.0%	18.4%	11.6%	12.1%	11.2%	8.4%	5.5%

(Emerick et al., 2016; Fillingham et al., 2016; Marcolini et al., 2003; Mori & Burkert, 2000). LTS are most abundant in very low densities ($\log \Sigma \sim -1.5$) and gradually decline with increasing environmental density. The morphological fraction of galaxies split in three environmental bins: low-density, intermediate density, and high density is summarised in Table 2.4.

We split our sample into star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies and plot the fraction of galaxies with different morphologies in fixed environmental bins (Fig. 2.13). Notice that the morphology-density relation does change, this is partly because of the paucity of star-forming Es and quenched/green valley LTS. In the left panel of Fig. 2.13, fraction of star-forming LTS gradually declines with increasing environment and the fraction of star-forming ETS increases, although within errorbars it is not very significant. Except that in the highest density bin ($1.5 < \log \Sigma \leq 2.0$) the trend is reversed; however this feature is not very significant due to the large errorbars. Interestingly, in all environments, except in the lowest density bin, about 10% of the star-forming galaxies are S0s. These are the second population of actively star-forming S0s observed in Figure 2.9. The ubiquity of these S0s in all environments, from low density to high density requires further study. In all environments, the green valley galaxies (middle panel of Fig. 2.13) are mostly ETS (around 50%) and S0s (around 40%), except in the highest density bins which show a decline. The fraction of green valley Es increases with increasing density with a steep rise in the highest density bin, wherein around 75% of the green valley galaxies are Es. These might be Es which have undergone recent gas rich minor/major merger(s). Since the rate of merger increases with increasing environmental density we find more Es in green valley in such environments. For quenched galaxies (right most panel of Fig. 2.13), the fraction of Es increase with increasing environmental density which most likely arises from the morphology-density relation. Except in the lowest density bin, the fraction of quenched S0s show a weak decline with increasing density, which is possibly because of the increase in the fraction of Es. The fraction of ETS declines very rapidly from the lowest density bin towards intermediate densities and then remains constant at around 10% with a small decline in the highest density bin. Interestingly, in the lowest density bin ($\log \Sigma < -1.5$) there are no quenched S0s, and about 80% of the galaxies are ETS and about 20% are Es.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Figure 2.14: Fraction of star-forming (blue), green valley (green), and quenched (red) galaxies for fixed environmental bins. The errorbars are jackknife errors. Notice that the fraction of star-forming galaxies decreases with increasing environmental density. The fraction of green valley galaxies does not show a significant change with environmental density.

We examine the percentage of Es, S0s, ETS, and LTS in low, intermediate, and high densities as shown in Table 2.5. Surprisingly, most of the Es, S0s, and ETS are present in the intermediate density environment.

2.3.3 Relation between specific star formation rate and local environment

We now study the relation between the two remaining parameters, sSFR and environment. We follow a similar procedure as in the earlier two subsections. We first examine the fraction of star-forming, green valley and quenched galaxies for fixed environmen-

Figure 2.15: Fraction of star-forming (blue), green valley (green), and quenched (red) galaxies for LTS (top left), ETS (top right), S0s (bottom left), and Es (bottom right). LTS(Es) are star-forming(quenched) as a function of environment. The errorbars are jack-knife errors. Star-forming ETS fraction decreases and quenched S0 fraction increases with increasing environmental density.

Table 2.6: Fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies in low, intermediate, and high densities.

	Low density	Intermediate density	High density
Total No.	2158	2968	1135
Star forming	46.1%	35.1%	15.6%
Green valley	21.9%	21.6%	17.3%
Quenched	32.0%	43.3%	67.1%

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Table 2.7: Fraction of galaxies in low, intermediate, and high densities which are in star-forming, in green valley, and in the quenched regions.

	Star forming	Green valley	Quenched
Total No.	2184	1288	2789
Low density	44.0%	35.1%	24.6%
Intermediate density	48.0%	49.9%	47.7%
High density	8.0%	15.0%	27.7%

tal bins. Then we use the morphological classification in terms of LTS, ETS, S0s and Es to study the differential effect of morphology on the relation between sSFR and environment.

The $1/V_{max}$ -corrected fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies in fixed environmental bins is shown in Figure 2.14. The quenched fraction increases with increasing environmental density (and hence the star-forming fraction decreases). Interestingly, the fraction of green valley galaxies remains almost constant at about 20% in all environments, except in the lowest and highest environment bin where there is a small decline in the fraction of green valley galaxies. This was also observed by [Wetzell et al. \(2012\)](#) for the green valley defined using $H\alpha$ based SFRs. In Table 2.6, we summarise the percentage of star forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies in low, intermediate, and high density environments where we observe the same trend as in Figure 2.14. This shows a strong effect of environment in quenching of galaxies.

The fraction of star-forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies for fixed environmental bins, separately for LTS, ETS, S0s, and Es is shown in Figure 2.15. We see that most of the LTS are star-forming and most of the Es are quenched in all environments. About 10% of all the Es are in the green-valley in all environments. Star-forming ETS decrease with increasing environmental density, which will get quenched and hence the quenched fraction will increase. Some of them may also transform into quenched S0s which is seen as an increase in the quenched fraction of S0s. Interestingly, S0s in lowest environmental density bin are mostly star-forming (the exact fraction however has very large uncertainty) and there are no green valley, and quenched S0s. Further, the fraction of star-forming and green valley S0s show a gradual decline with increasing environmental density.

Finally, we report the percentage of galaxies in low density, intermediate density, and high density environments which are in the star-forming, green valley, and quenched region in Table 2.7. As expected, the percentage of star-forming galaxies is highest at low/intermediate densities and drastically decreases at high densities. The percentage of green valley galaxies increases from low to intermediate densities and then shows a significant decrease at high densities. The percentage of quenched galaxies increases from low to intermediate densities and then decreases at high densities.

2.3.4 Partial correlation coefficient between morphological T-type, sSFR, and Σ

In the previous sections, we studied the relation between each of the three parameters, morphology, sSFR, and environment, taken two at a time, and then studied the differential effect of the third parameter. In this section, we quantify these relations using the partial correlation coefficient (PCC).

The PCC measures the correlation between any two variables by removing the effect of a set of control variables. For instance, in our study we know that morphological T-type and log sSFR are correlated (as the T-type increases log sSFR increases). However, we know that T-Type and environmental density (Σ) is anti-correlated because of the morphology-density relation (as Σ increases the fraction of early-type galaxies increases i.e. T-type decreases). And Σ and log sSFR are also anti-correlated, since as Σ increases, log sSFR decreases. Thus, it is possible that the correlation between morphology and log sSFR is caused by the effect of environment. In other words, because it is more likely to find early-type galaxies in high density environments, and because high density environments are more efficient at quenching galaxies, we find that early-type galaxies are mostly quenched. Similarly, it is possible that we see a morphology-density relation because as the density increases quenching becomes more efficient, and hence the log sSFR decreases, and because low levels of log sSFR is found mainly in early-type galaxies, we see a anti-correlation between morphology and density . A similar case can be made of the other two variables.

Thus, we find the PCC between: morphological T-type-log sSFR with Σ as the control variable, morphological T-type- Σ with log sSFR as the control variable, and log sSFR- Σ with morphological T-type as the control variable for our final sample of 7079 galaxies.

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

Table 2.8: Results from the partial correlation coefficient analysis. The errors on the correlation coefficients are calculated using the jackknife method.

Variables (control variable)	Spearman's ρ	PCC
T-type-log sSFR (Σ)	0.752 ± 0.003	0.735 ± 0.003
T-type- Σ (log sSFR)	-0.256 ± 0.010	-0.099 ± 0.011
Σ -log sSFR (T-type)	-0.256 ± 0.010	-0.100 ± 0.010

The PCC between any two random variables A and B with C as the control variable is calculated using,

$$\rho_{AB \cdot C} = \frac{\rho_{AB} - \rho_{AC}\rho_{CB}}{\sqrt{1 - \rho_{AC}^2}\sqrt{1 - \rho_{CB}^2}}, \quad (2.2)$$

where ρ_{AB} is the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient between the variables A and B.

The results of our PCC analysis are given in Table 2.8, for reference we also show the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (Spearman's ρ). Since we use 6194 data points for the PCC analysis, our results are highly significant. The Spearman's ρ shows that the correlation between T-type and log sSFR is high, which remains so even for the PCC. This suggests that morphology correlates very well with log sSFR, independent of the environment. The Spearman's ρ between T-type- Σ , and Σ -log sSFR is weakly anti-correlated, which considerably decreases after computing the PCC.

Thus we find that for massive galaxies, morphology is the strongest indicator of log sSFR, and that such a relationship is real and not just an indirect effect due to the morphology-density relation and density-sSFR relation. This shows that, for massive galaxies, the physical processes which shape the galaxy morphology are also the most important in deciding their star forming state.

2.4 Summary

In this work, we have studied the spectral energy distributions of massive galaxies (log $M_*/M_\odot \geq 10.0$) along the Hubble sequence, from Es to spirals, using multi-wavelength SED fitting using UV-optical-mid IR data from GALEX-SDSS-2MASS-WISE, for a sample of 6194 galaxies. For these galaxies, we are able to simultaneously constrain the recent star formation using UV data and also take into account the dust attenuation

from warm dust using IR data. We compute the star formation rate and the stellar mass for each galaxy in our sample using stellar population synthesis models. Further, due to the availability of GALEX UV data, we could define a green valley which has less contamination from the star-forming and quenched region. For our whole sample, the detailed visual morphologies in terms of the Hubble T-types were taken from NA10. Also for our whole sample we had local environmental density from [Baldry et al. \(2006\)](#). Using the morphological classifications, specific star formation, and environmental density information, we studied the mutual dependence of each of these parameters. Our results are summarised as follows:

1. We find that for massive galaxies in the local Universe, LTS, and Es are primarily star-forming and quenched, respectively. The green valley is mostly populated by ETS (49.1%) and S0s (39.9%). A further split of ETS into Sa, Sab, Sb and Sbc shows that the growth of the bulge plays an important role in quenching. Given that these galaxies are more likely to host a classical bulge which is already quenched, the final process of quenching likely takes place in the disk. The typical quenching timescale of green valley disk galaxies are known to be large, of the order of more than 1 Gyr ([Schawinski et al., 2014](#)) and hence the disk quenching must be a slow process (e.g., halo-quenching, strangulation). S0s, on the other hand, which also host a bigger bulge have a disk that may have quenched more rapidly (timescales of less than 250 Myrs) than ETS and hence they are more abundant in the quenched region. The properties of both the ETS and S0s show that at least at the high mass end ($M_{\text{stellar}} > 10^{10} M_{\odot}$), bulge growth is important for quenching, as was also observed by [Bluck et al. \(2014\)](#).
2. The fraction of galaxies of different morphological types (LTS, ETS, S0s and Es) as a function of $\log \text{sSFR}$ show very different trends. The distribution of LTS peaks at much lower $\log \text{sSFR}$ and falls quite rapidly for $\log \text{sSFR} > -10$. On the other hand, the fraction of ETS peak near the blue end of the green valley, and falls as we enter the green valley. Interestingly, this fall coincides with the rise in the fraction of S0s, which peak near the red end of the green valley. This points towards the morphological transformation from ETS to S0s. Beyond the green valley, in the quenched region, the fraction of S0s and ETS declines, and the fraction of Es starts dominating. Interestingly, we also find a

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

second population of S0s galaxies which are actively star forming. A split of our sample into low, intermediate and high densities shows that this relation does not change significantly with environment. Remarkably, even the second population of star forming S0s is present in all the three environmental bins. This supports the view that morphology is a strong indicator of the sSFR of a galaxy, with a weaker dependence on the environment.

3. The fraction of star forming, green valley, and quenched galaxies for a given morphological T-type shows that as we go from Es to late type galaxies, the quenched fraction decreases. As was earlier observed, the fraction of green valley galaxies rises from S0- to Sab galaxies, showing that, in the local Universe, they are the galaxies in transition from star forming to the quenched region. Remarkably, the quenched fraction of S0- and S0 galaxies is much higher compared to the quenched fraction of S0/a galaxies, which is more closer to that of Sa spirals. Furthermore, when we split this relation into low, intermediate and high densities, we find that at low densities, the fraction of star forming S0/a galaxies is higher than the quenched fraction. Further, at high densities there is a rise in the quenched fraction of S0/a galaxies. Also, the quenched/star-forming fraction of S0/a galaxies more closely follows the Sa galaxies in all environments, and unlike the S0- and S0 galaxies, who have a much higher quenched fraction in all environments. This indicates that S0/a galaxies undergo a different quenching process than that of S0-, and S0 galaxies.
4. We observe the morphology-density relation for our sample of galaxies, with the exception that the fraction of S0s remain roughly constant as we go to higher densities. This is likely because, we only have high mass S0s in our sample. The split of the morphology-density relation in terms of star-forming, green valley and quenched galaxies shows that there are green valley galaxies in all environments and they are mostly dominated by ETS, and S0s. The fraction of green valley Es rise with increasing environmental density, suggesting that they may have undergone recent gas rich major/minor merger(s). Interestingly, we also see the presence of star forming S0s in all environments, from low to high densities.
5. The quenched fraction increases with increasing environmental density, and except for the lowest and the highest density bin, the fraction of green valley galaxies

remains constant. This shows that, in the local Universe, massive galaxies are recently undergoing transition in all environments. A split of this relation with different morphological class (LTS, ETS, S0s, and Es) shows that ETS and S0s are the galaxies most affected by environment. The fraction of star forming ETS decline with increasing density, some of which move into the green valley and quenched regions. This decline coincides with the increase in the fraction of quenched S0s, showing that possibly some of the quenched ETS also undergo a morphological transformation into S0s. Star forming S0s are most abundant in the lowest density bin, and they decrease as we go to higher densities.

6. Because morphology, log sSFR, and environmental density are correlated with each other, we find the partial correlation coefficient by taking two of the variables with the third variable as the control parameter. Our analysis shows that the correlation between morphology and log sSFR is strongest, and independent of the environment. Whereas the anti-correlations between morphology-density, and density-sSFR are both weaker when we remove the effect of the third parameter.

2.5 Conclusion and Future Work

In conclusion, we studied the star formation history using multi-wavelength data from UV-optical-mid IR along the Hubble sequence for a sample of 6194 galaxies. Our results shows that, in the local Universe, for massive galaxies, ETS and S0s are currently undergoing transition from star-forming to the quenched region. There are two populations of S0s, a quenched and an actively star forming one which is present in all environments. Further, our study of morphology, star formation and environment shows that morphological T-type is the strongest indicator of the sSFR of a galaxy independent of the environment. The impact of environment in deciding whether a galaxy is quenched or not, is seen mainly on S0/a,Sa, and Sab type galaxies.

In our current work, the galaxy morphologies are quantified using the Hubble T-types are based on a somewhat subjective definition. In the future, we hope to follow-up this work with an objective and physically motivated quantification of morphology in terms of the stellar angular momentum (Cortese et al., 2016; Fall & Efstathiou, 1980; Fall & Romanowsky, 2018; Obreschkow & Glazebrook, 2014; Romanowsky & Fall, 2012). This can be achieved using galaxy stellar kinematics using IFU observations

2. ON THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF GALAXY MORPHOLOGY, STAR FORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENT IN MASSIVE GALAXIES IN THE NEARBY UNIVERSE

which are now available for a several thousands of galaxies using the MaNGA and SAMI survey. Such a large sample will allow us to make several cuts to study the interdependence of galaxy morphology, star-formation and environment properties. Using angular momentum we will be able to make a direct comparison of our results with large-scale cosmological simulation e.g., with Illustris (Snyder et al., 2015) and EAGLE (Clauwens et al., 2018).

Here we also only used the projected galaxy density to measure the environment. In the future, we would also like to use various other measures of environment e.g., the halo mass, central/satellite, velocity dispersion of the group to name to few, to do a more thorough analysis on the effect, if any, of other measures of environment. The current work focused only on massive galaxies. We would also like to carry out a similar analysis on the interdependence of various physical parameters on low mass and dwarf galaxies. Here we expect the stronger effect of environment e.g., ram-pressure stripping and harassment primarily due to shallower gravitational potential.

3

Radio continuum properties of blueberry galaxies

This chapter is based on [Sebastian & Bait \(2019\)](#).

3.1 Introduction

There is now an overwhelming amount of evidence which suggests that the neutral Universe underwent a phase transition and was reionized by $z \sim 6$ (see e.g., [Becker et al., 2001](#)). However, the nature of sources (star-forming galaxies or Active galactic nuclei (AGN)) which contributed to this transition is still under debate. It is widely believed that star-formation (SF) plays the major role in providing the ionizing photons required for fully ionizing the Universe ([Barkana & Loeb, 2001](#)). Several observations and simulation suggest that a significant fraction may be contributed by low mass starburst galaxies (e.g., [Drake et al., 2017](#); [Dressler et al., 2015](#)), a subset of which could be Lyman- α emitters (LAEs).

It is very difficult to do a detailed multi-wavelength study of these faint high- z galaxies due to sensitivity limitations of the current generation telescopes and hence it is useful to search for their local analogues. Currently, the best low- z candidates for such galaxies are the bright green and compact (typically ≤ 5 kpc) galaxies termed as “green peas” (GPs; [Cardamone et al., 2009](#)) discovered by volunteers from the Galaxy Zoo project. These galaxies have high SFRs, relatively low stellar masses ($\sim 10^9\text{--}10$ M_{\odot}), low metallicities, compact sizes (typically ≤ 5 kpc), very high [OIII]/[OII] ratios (e.g.,

3. RADIO CONTINUUM PROPERTIES OF BLUEBERRY GALAXIES

Jaskot & Oey, 2013) and bright green color in SDSS images due to the large [OIII] λ 5007 Å equivalent width (EW). Such compact star-forming galaxies are also known to leak a significant amount of Ly- α continuum photons (Izotov et al., 2016). Yang et al. (2017) have recently searched for the low redshift counterparts ($z < 0.05$) of green pea galaxies in the SDSS *ugriz* broadband images. This gives them the sensitivity to probe the fainter (and hence lower stellar mass and metallicity) counterparts of green peas. They have found a sample of extremely starbursting dwarf galaxies with even smaller sizes (≤ 1 kpc), lower stellar masses, low metallicities, termed as “Blueberry” (BB) galaxies (Yang et al., 2017). These are also supposed to be the local analogs of the high- z faint Lyman- α emitters (Yang et al., 2017).

A complementary study of this peculiar population of galaxies at radio frequencies can provide an independent estimate of their total (dust-obscured and unobscured) SFRs (e.g., Bera et al., 2018; Condon, 1992; Magnelli et al., 2015; Pannella et al., 2015). Radio emission from high redshift ($z \sim 3 - 4$) Lyman-break galaxies (LBGs) has been reported only by stacking analysis, (e.g., Carilli et al., 2008; Ho et al., 2010; To et al., 2014). This stacked radio luminosity was also found to be systematically lower than that expected from the ultra-violet (UV) luminosity (Carilli et al., 2008). However, for such galaxies, it is hard to separate the effect of an increased inverse Compton (IC) cooling of the relativistic electrons due to scattering from cosmic microwave background (CMB) photons versus an intrinsic deficit. The local analogs of LBGs and LAEs will have a negligible amount of IC-CMB losses and are also easier to detect. However, in a previous study on green peas, a direct detection in radio was found only for two of them using the Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT) (Chakraborti et al., 2012).

In this study, we push these radio studies to the even younger and lower mass population of blueberry galaxies. We report their first ever radio detections, which has been possible due to the wideband backend of the upgraded GMRT (uGMRT, Gupta et al., 2017) allowing us to reach an rms of $\sim 15 \mu\text{Jy beam}^{-1}$ with reasonable integration time at 1.25 GHz (Section 3.2). Here we compare their radio-based SFRs with the UV+IR and optical based SFR and estimate their non-thermal fraction.

Throughout this chapter, we use the standard concordance cosmology from WMAP9 (Hinshaw et al., 2013) with $\Omega_M = 0.286$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.714$ and $h_{100} = 0.69$.

3.2 GMRT Observations

3.2.1 Sample

In this pilot study, we selected a subset of the 40 confirmed blueberry galaxies from [Yang et al. \(2017\)](#) as follows. The SFR from [Yang et al. \(2017\)](#) were used to calculate the expected non-thermal flux density at 1.4 GHz for a normal star-forming galaxy following [Yun & Carilli \(2002\)](#). Since this calibration can vary for our population of young starburst galaxies, we selected 10 of the brightest sources to ensure direct detections.

3. RADIO CONTINUUM PROPERTIES OF BLUEBERRY GALAXIES

Table 3.1: Sample and observation details

ObjID ^a	R.A. (deg)	Decl. (deg)	Redshift ^b	Flux density (μ Jy)	Beam Size ($'' \times ''$)	Beam P.A. (deg)
27	01h46m53.307s	+03d19m22.360s	0.047	105 \pm 15	6.87'' \times 3.24''	+71.96
34	03h57m13.516s	+18d08m45.582s	0.037	70 \pm 14	3.04'' \times 2.48''	+88.50
3	08h25m40.449s	+18d46m17.209s	0.038	72 \pm 11	3.30'' \times 2.51''	+77.96
5	10h32m56.727s	+49d19m47.226s	0.044	<39 ^c	4.23'' \times 2.40''	+75.81
66	11h13m12.241s	+03d01m12.831s	0.023	56 \pm 15	3.39'' \times 2.42''	-10.31
67	11h23m48.949s	+20d50m31.297s	0.033	373 \pm 17	3.88'' \times 2.31''	+87.74
6	13h23m47.462s	-01d32m52.008s	0.023	91 \pm 18	2.59'' \times 2.43''	+49.60
10	15h09m34.173s	+37d31m46.117s	0.033	345 \pm 16	3.14'' \times 2.55''	-69.71
12	15h56m24.474s	+48d06m45.792s	0.050	107 \pm 12	3.20'' \times 2.36''	-41.99
13	16h08m10.363s	+35d28m09.346s	0.033	58 \pm 17	7.32'' \times 3.31''	+55.38

^a - The ObjIDs correspond to those from Yang et al. (2017)

^b - The redshifts are taken from Yang et al. (2017)

^c - 3σ upper limit on the flux density

Figure 3.1: Contours of the 1.25 GHz continuum image overlaid on the optical *grz*-band color composite image ($14.4'' \times 14.4''$ in size) from DECaLS or MzLS (for sources without DECaLS data) or SDSS (for sources without DECaLS or MzLS data). The contour levels represent $3\sigma \times (-1.0, 1.0, 1.19, 1.41, 1.68, 2.0, 2.38, 2.83, 3.36, 4.0, 4.76, 5.66, 6.73, 8.0, 9.51, 11.31) \mu\text{Jy beam}^{-1}$ where $\sigma = 11.0, 13.0, 18.0, 16.0, 12.0, 14.3, 15.0, 14.0, 10.0, 20.0$ for each of the sources sorted in the ascending order of their ObjIDs. The clean beam is shown in the bottom left corner of each cutout.

3. RADIO CONTINUUM PROPERTIES OF BLUEBERRY GALAXIES

These galaxies were observed using uGMRT (project ID: 34_123) at Band-5 (1000-1450 MHz) for ~ 2 on-source. The details of the observations are listed in Table 3.1.

3.2.2 Data Analysis

Basic editing and calibration of the data were carried out using standard procedures in AIPS. Data corrupted by RFI were identified and removed using the automatic flagging algorithms in AIPS. We carried out flux, phase and bandpass calibration using standard calibrators. The flux calibrators used were 3C 147, 3C 286 and 3C 48. The time resolution used for this observation was 10.1s and no further time averaging was carried out. Few channels were then averaged using task ‘SPLAT’ in AIPS which resulted in a final channel width of ~ 3.5 MHz. This channel width would lead to 3% reduction in the flux 5 arcmin away from the centre of the field due to bandwidth smearing, whereas at the location of our target, there will only be negligible errors. The calibrated target source was then extracted out of the main data set. Initial rounds of imaging and self-calibration were carried out in AIPS using only a central bandwidth of 100 MHz to make sure bandwidth effects do not adversely affect the image quality. Four rounds of the phase-only self-calibration were carried out in AIPS to remove antenna based ionospheric errors. The target source was then exported to CASA and imaged using MS-MFS algorithm (Rau & Cornwell, 2011). The flux densities of the target sources were then estimated using ‘JMFIT’ task in AIPS. The flux density values of all the sources in our sample are summarized in Table 3.1. The errors on flux density quoted in Table 3.1 represent the rms from the images. However, for all the rest of the calculations we add 10 % calibration error on the flux density in quadrature. We found detections for 9 of the 10 sources in our sample. Figure 3.1 shows the contours of radio images of these nine sources overlaid on the *grz*-band color composite image from the Dark Energy Camera Legacy Survey (DECaLS) or the Mayall z-band Legacy Survey (MzLS) (Dey et al., 2019). We used the *gri*-bands from SDSS (Abazajian et al., 2009) in the case of one source, ObjID-34 due to the unavailability of DECaLS or MzLS images.

Figure 3.2: Ratio of the $\text{SFR}_{1.4 \text{ GHz}}/\text{SFR}_{\text{H}\alpha}$ vs. $\text{SFR}_{\text{H}\alpha}$. The blue points correspond to detections and the red star corresponds to the three sigma upper limit on the ratio for one of the non-detection in our sample. The dashed line shows the median value of the ratio.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Comparison between radio and $\text{H}\alpha$ based SFRs

Normal star-forming galaxies show a tight correlation between the SFR and non-thermal radio emission and typically have a negligible amount of thermal emission at frequencies of ~ 1 GHz and below ($\sim 10\% \pm 9\%$, e.g., [Tabatabaei et al., 2017](#)). Here we investigate the SFR derived from the radio continuum emission for our sample of the blueberry galaxies and compare it with the SFR derived using optical emission lines.

The radio-based SFRs for our sample is derived using the 1.4 GHz luminosity calibration from [Murphy et al. \(2011\)](#) Eq. 17. For our sample of blueberries, the median value of the SFR from this calibrator is $0.15 \text{ M}_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$. In [Figure 3.2](#) we plot the ratio of the radio SFR and the SFR derived using the $\text{H}\alpha$ line from [Yang et al. \(2017\)](#) as a function of SFR from $\text{H}\alpha$. Note that here and in all other further analysis we do not use ObjID 5 (red star) since it was not detected in our observation and hence does not have a reliable flux measurement. Both the SFR calibrators use Kroupa IMF with the same stellar mass limits (0.1 M_{\odot} - 100 M_{\odot}). Hence we do not expect any difference in the two SFRs due to a difference in either the IMF and it's adopted stellar mass range. We find that the radio emission is significantly lower than the ones deduced from $\text{H}\alpha$. The median value of the suppression is ~ 0.3 (shown in dashed line). Blueberries can

3. RADIO CONTINUUM PROPERTIES OF BLUEBERRY GALAXIES

be dust obscured (Rong et al., 2018), which could mean that the $SFR_{H\alpha}$ needs some dust correction. However, it will only further enhance the radio-suppression observed here.

The stacking detection of Green pea galaxies with VLA FIRST data showed suppression of radio continuum emission by a factor of ~ 0.53 (Chakraborti et al., 2012), however, the individual detections were closer to the expected values. Carilli et al. (2008) also find a depression in the stacked radio continuum emission for a sample of high- z LBGs. They proposed that such a reduction can be a result of increased IC-CMB losses at high- z or a combination of IC-CMB losses and intrinsic reduction in radio continuum. Since our sample of blueberry galaxies are at very low redshifts and the effects of IC-CMB is negligible which implies that the suppression is intrinsic. And it is possible that even the high- z LBGs show an intrinsic suppression of radio continuum.

One reason for the diminished radio emission might be the young age itself. Greis et al. (2017) point out that the standard SFR calibrators depend upon the stellar population age and star formation history. $H\alpha$ emission traces the recent star formation (~ 10 Myrs), whereas the synchrotron or non-thermal radio emission traces star formation which has been continuing for about 100 Myrs. Another reason for the diminished radio emission could be that the relativistic electrons produced in the galaxy escape from these galaxies easily compared to other massive systems due to their shallow gravitational potential (Greis et al., 2017).

In both the above situations, only the non-thermal radio emission will show a decrement in the flux densities. Hence, the thermal radio emission should be consistent with that deduced using emission lines. Tabatabaei et al. (2017) provides a calibration for converting the thermal radio emission to SFR using the KINGFISH galaxy sample (Kennicutt et al., 2011). Under this assumption, we can estimate the non-thermal fraction as follows. Let δ be thermal fraction such that the thermal luminosity at L-band (L_{th}) is δ times the total observed radio luminosity at L-band (L_{tot}). And let β be the thermal radio calibration factor used to estimate the SFR from Tabatabaei et al. (2017). We can then relate the SFR from $H\alpha$ emission and δ as: $SFR_{H\alpha} = SFR_{th} = \beta \times (L_{th}) = \beta \times (\delta L_{tot})$. The non-thermal fraction, which is nothing but $(1-\delta)$, can be estimated using this above relation.

Figure 3.3: Estimated non-thermal fraction as a function of stellar mass for our sample of blueberry galaxies.

The median value of the non-thermal fraction for our sample of blueberry galaxies is ~ 0.49 . Such a low non-thermal fraction was also previously observed in other types of dwarf galaxies e.g., in blue compact dwarfs (Ramya et al., 2011; Thuan et al., 2004), in IC 10, a post-starburst dwarf irregular galaxy (Heesen et al., 2011) and in a sample of faint star-forming dwarf galaxies (Roychowdhury & Chengalur, 2012). Greis et al. (2017) showed that the fraction of thermal radio emission can be as high as $\sim 100\%$ for a sample of local Lyman break analogs (LBAs).

The difference in the non-thermal fraction in a sample of dwarf galaxies with that of normal galaxies suggests that there might be an evolution of the non-thermal fraction with the growth of galaxies, particularly in their stellar mass. We explore this in our sample by plotting the non-thermal fraction against the galaxy stellar mass in Figure 3.3. We see some correlation between the non-thermal fraction and stellar mass. The Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient between the two variable is 0.68 (with a p-value of 0.04). However, given that the uncertainties in this fraction are large and our sample is small, we only claim a tentative correlation.

3.3.2 Comparison between radio, UV+24 μ m and H α based SFRs

We attempt to do an inter-comparison of SFR derived from different bands, namely, radio, UV+24 μ m and H α . These indicators probe SFRs on different timescales ranging from the highest from UV+24 μ m (~ 100 Myr) to H α (~ 10 Myr). We use the UV+24 μ m

3. RADIO CONTINUUM PROPERTIES OF BLUEBERRY GALAXIES

Figure 3.4: Left-panel: Comparison of UV+24 μm based SFR with the ratio of SFR from radio 1.4 GHz and UV+24 μm . Right-panel: Comparison of H α based SFR with the ratio of SFR from radio UV+24 μm and UV+24 μm .

based SFR instead of a purely UV based SFR since blueberry galaxies are known to be extremely red in the WISE colour-colour diagram (Rong et al., 2018), pointing to the presence of a high level of dust. We extract the far-UV fluxes from GALEX and the 24 μm fluxes from WISE W4 band. The WISE W4 magnitudes were converted to fluxes following Wright et al. (2010) with an additional 10% correction since all the sources were extremely red¹. Out of the 10 galaxies observed in our sample we found a combined FUV and W4 detections for only five galaxies. For the UV+24 μm based SFR we used the relation from Murphy et al. (2011). In Fig. 3.4 the left-panel shows the comparison between the SFR ratio between radio 1.4 GHz and UV+24 μm as a function of SFR from UV+24 μm . Whereas the right-panel shows a similar comparison between the UV+24 μm and H α based SFR. Notice that although the radio and UV+24 μm typically probes SFR on similar timescales we still find a large suppression in radio (about 5 times) for 3 out of the 5 blueberries with more than 40% suppression in the rest of the two blueberries. Interestingly, the UV+24 μm and H α based SFR also do not seem consistent with each other. Here the UV+24 μm based SFR is lower by about 20-40% for three of the blueberries and higher by 20% and 120% for the other two blueberries. The mild offset between the UV+24 μm and H α based SFR can be due to the different ages it probes, however, it is not clear if the offsets can also be as large as 120%. Since the SF in such young starbursting galaxies can be highly stochastic a

¹Following the suggestion in http://wise2.ipac.caltech.edu/docs/release/allsky/expsup/sec4_4h.html#red.

detailed modelling of the SF history is necessary to estimate the “true” SFR of these galaxies. It is also possible that the dust properties (e.g., the dust temperature, sizes etc.) in these galaxies might be different from typical galaxies and hence a modified relation is also required for the $24\mu\text{m}$ based calibrator. Note that the comparison done in this section is based on small number statistics, which we hope to remedy in the future with observations of a larger sample.

3.4 Discussion

In order to identify the reason for the deficit and the evolution in the radio non-thermal emission we compare the characteristic timescales of various processes (age of the recent starburst, build up of SN rate and CRE escape via diffusion or outflows).

3.4.1 Young ages

Assuming that most of the stellar mass was built up in the starburst phase, we can use the current SFR to put an upper limit on the time elapsed since the onset of this burst. We find that this timescale ranges from 30 - 370 Myr with a median value of 70 Myr for our sample of galaxies. Greis et al. (2017) show using a stellar population synthesis for a system which forms stars at a rate of $1 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ that the SFR traced by $\text{H}\alpha$ and $[\text{O II}]$ becomes significant just after the star formation commences. Whereas the synchrotron emission takes about 10 Myr to become significant and matches with the optical-based SFRs only after 100 Myr after the onset of star formation. Thermal emission, on the other hand, traces the SFR on timescales similar to $\text{H}\alpha$ and $[\text{O II}]$. Moreover, even the evolution of the non-thermal fraction (see Figure 3.3) can be easily explained if the decrement is due to young age. Here a lower stellar mass galaxy would have undergone less number of past supernovae events and would thus have a lower non-thermal fraction.

3.4.2 CRE escape via diffusion/outflows

The deficit in the non-thermal radio emission can also be explained by the escape of CREs via diffusion and/or winds/outflows. This happens only if their timescales are lower than the synchrotron-loss timescales (Carilli et al., 2008). Diffusion timescale (t_D) can be estimated as $t_D = \frac{R^2}{D}$, where D , the diffusion coefficient is equal to $\frac{l_0 c}{3}$

3. RADIO CONTINUUM PROPERTIES OF BLUEBERRY GALAXIES

and R is the size of the galaxy. The typical values of the mean free path, $l_0=0.3$ kpc (see [Chakraborti et al. \(2012\)](#) and [Calvez et al. \(2010\)](#) for details). For an upper-limit of 1 kpc on the size we put an upper-limit of 0.033 Myr on t_D . We estimate the synchrotron-loss timescales using the relation, $\tau_{syn} = 33.4 B_{10}^{-\frac{3}{2}} \nu_1^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ Myr ([Pérez-Torres & Alberdi, 2007](#)), where B_{10} is the magnetic field value in units of 10 μ G, and ν_1 is the critical frequency in GHz. The median equipartition magnetic fields for our sample is estimated to be $\sim 27 \mu$ G, following [Beck & Krause \(2005\)](#). For a critical frequency of 1.2 GHz the synchrotron-loss timescales are ~ 6.87 Myr. Since $t_D \ll \tau_{syn}$, CRE diffusion might be playing a major role in the suppression of radio continuum emission in these galaxies. Note that our equipartition magnetic fields are much higher than those observed in typical galaxies (typically 9μ G; [Niklas, 1995](#)). However, a lower magnetic field will only increase the synchrotron loss timescales which argues in our favour.

Another possibility is the escape of CREs due to winds or outflows. Galactic superwinds were shown to be present in all the galaxies which had global SFR densities (SFRDs) greater than $0.1 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$ ([Heckman, 2002](#)). Assuming an upper limit of 1 kpc for the size of these blueberry galaxies, the SFRDs of all the galaxies are higher than $0.1 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$. The typical wind terminal velocities attained in starbursting galaxies hosting superwind are in the range, 2000 - 3000 km/s ([Heckman et al., 1990](#)). Assuming a wind velocity of 2000 km/s, and a galaxy size of 1 kpc, we obtain escape timescales of 0.5 Myr, which is also lower than the synchrotron loss timescales. Such an outflow would only be a natural consequence of the massive amount of star formation in these young galaxies.

In our study, we are not able to distinguish between the different scenarios which lead to the decrement in the radio continuum emission.

3.5 Future Work

As discussed in this work the standard calibrators of SFR do not work for blueberry galaxies and hence they are ideal laboratories to study SF in very young and starbursting galaxies. We clearly see a suppression in the radio based SFR compared to the $H\alpha$ and to an extent with the UV+24 μ m based SFR. A comparison between the UV+24 μ m and $H\alpha$ does not show any consistent picture. In the future, we aim to do

a detailed comparison of SFRs from different indicators (e.g., UV+IR, $H\alpha$, radio flux density and multi-wavelength spectral energy distribution fitting). We also aim to do a detailed radio spectral modeling (Klein et al., 2018) to make accurate estimates of the thermal/non-thermal fraction and as a result, the magnetic field. In the case where CREs escape the galaxy and causes the decrement in the radio emission, it would show a break in the radio synchrotron spectrum (Klein et al., 2018; Lisenfeld et al., 2004). We would also increase the sample size to include both the lower mass and higher mass galaxies (green pea galaxies) to study the evolution of the non-thermal and SF properties in these systems.

Author contributions

In this work, the GMRT observing proposal was written with an equal contribution from both the authors. The data was analysed by the lead author, Biny Sebastian. The GMRT observations and data analysis section was contributed by Biny Sebastian. Omkar Bait contributed in writing the introduction section, estimating the SFR from the fluxes, in producing the SFR comparison plots and some of the associated description in the results section. Both the authors contributed in writing the discussion section and future work.

3. RADIO CONTINUUM PROPERTIES OF BLUEBERRY GALAXIES

4

H α emission around galaxies in SDSS-IV MaNGA

This chapter is based on [Bait et al. \(2019b\)](#).

4.1 Introduction

Large-scale galactic outflows due to both starbursts and active galactic nuclei (AGN) are quite common, particularly at high redshifts, and play an important role in providing feedback in galaxy formation and evolution (see [Veilleux et al., 2005](#), for a review). Such galaxy outflows can appear as H α emission away from the galaxy. The classic example is that of Messier 82 (M82) which shows large scale bipolar superwinds ([Bland & Tully, 1988](#); [Shopbell & Bland-Hawthorn, 1998](#)) due to the ongoing starburst at the centre. Interestingly, M82 also shows an H α cap like structure at a projected distance of about 11 kpc from the disc ([Devine & Bally, 1999](#); [Lehnert et al., 1999](#)). Typically such galactic outflows are known to trigger star formation in the host galaxy as a consequence of gas compression. However, [Maiolino et al. \(2017\)](#) has also found observational evidence for star formation occurring in the galactic outflow at a rate of more than 15 solar masses per year.

Another interesting case of an outlying emission line region is that of the Hanny's Voorwerp ([Lintott et al., 2009](#)), discovered serendipitously, lying near the spiral galaxy IC 2497. This object was discovered as part of the Galaxy Zoo project in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) g -band image due to its strong emission in the [OIII]4959,

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

5007 lines. It has been suggested that the gas in Hanny’s Voorwerp has a tidal origin (Józsa et al., 2009). This gas was then photoionised by the nucleus of IC 2497, which, in turn, was a quasi-stellar object (QSO) that has faded dramatically in the last 10^5 years, thus producing a quasar light echo (Lintott et al., 2009; Schawinski et al., 2010). In Keel et al. (2012b), Galaxy Zoo volunteers have carried out further searches to identify 19 more such objects, which are termed as extended emission-line regions (EELRs). Of these, most are in interacting or merging state which further makes the tidal origin of gas which was photoionised by an AGN a more plausible explanation of EELRs.

With the advent of large scale integral field unit (IFU) surveys e.g., the Mapping Nearby Galaxies at Apache Point Observatory (Bundy et al., 2015, MaNGA), Calar Alto Legacy Integral Field Area survey (Sánchez et al., 2012, CALIFA), and the Sydney-AAO Multi-object Integral-field spectrograph Galaxy survey (Bryant et al., 2015, SAMI) we can now search for such outlying H α emitters around several thousand galaxies. In the MaNGA survey, Cheung et al. (2016) found an outlying H α complex without any optical counterpart about 6.3 kpc away from the effective radius of the host galaxy and at about 3 times the effective radius of the galaxy. Using a detailed analysis of the gas kinematics, gas phase metallicity, and emission-line ratios the authors argue that the scenario is most consistent with an gas accretion event. Recently, Lin et al. (2017) have discovered a large outlying H α blob (~ 3 -4 kpc in radius) around 8 kpc away from the host galaxy which is undergoing a dry galaxy merger. Here the authors argue that this could either be an AGN outburst or a possible “ultra-diffuse galaxy”. Using the SAMI survey, Fogarty et al. (2012) have discovered an outlying emission-line region off the plane of the disk of edge-on galaxy ESO 185-G031 which is ionised due to shock excitation from a starburst driven wind. Richards et al. (2014) have found a large HII complex in the dwarf galaxy GAMA J141103.98–003242.3 which is similar to the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) and 30 Doradus complex. Recently, using the Multi Unit Spectroscopic Explorer (MUSE), Epinat et al. (2018) has found a large diffuse ionised gas complex ($\sim 10^4$ kpc² in area) in [OII] $\lambda\lambda$ 3727, 3729 in a galaxy group COSMOS-Gr30 at a redshift of 0.725 with two kinematic sub-structures. The authors argue that at least one of the gas component has a non-primordial origin arising either due to tidal interactions between the group galaxies or gas expelled due to AGN outflows. More recently, López-Cobá et al. (2019) have conducted a systematic search for galaxy outflows in the Local Universe using the CALIFA survey and have

found 17 objects which show evidence of galactic winds. They find that these objects do not show any excess in their integrated star formation rates (SFRs) compared to normal star forming galaxies. However, the SFR density in the inner regions shows an excess and is an important driver of galaxy outflows.

Thus a systematic study of outlying $H\alpha$ emitters is important from the point of view of understanding galaxy outflows and interestingly also in-situ star formation in these extreme environments. With a view to increase the sample size of these interesting but rare class of objects, we have carried a systematic search of outlying $H\alpha$ emitters in the recently released SDSS IV MaNGA IFU survey. We use the recently released MaNGA value added catalogue, analysed using the Pipe3D pipeline (Sánchez et al., 2016b, 2018), of 2,755 galaxies (see Sec. 4.2 for details on the sample selection). We visually identify outlying $H\alpha$ emitting regions around MaNGA target galaxies on which the IFU is centered. These emission line regions also shows a different velocity component from that of the host galaxy. Note that our search criteria differ from those of López-Cobá et al. (2019), where they have used various diagnostic diagrams (e.g., $EW(H\alpha)$, $[NII]/H\alpha$ line ratios etc.) which are tuned to find galactic winds, whereas we are interested in finding extended emission line regions away from the MaNGA target galaxies. We have found a total of six such outlying $H\alpha$ emitters which have extended $H\alpha$ structure around the host galaxies (see Sec. 4.2). Interestingly using the Baldwin Philip and Terlevich (BPT) diagram, we find that the extended $H\alpha$ emitters shows various sources of ionisation (see Section 4.3.1.1). In section 4.3.2 we briefly discuss the possibility that these extended emitters are low luminosity counterparts of Hanny’s Voorwerp (Lintott et al., 2009) like objects. In section 4.4 we briefly discuss some of the interesting sources in our sample. We will then summarise and conclude in Sec 4.5.

Throughout this chapter we use the standard concordance cosmology with $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$ and $h_{100} = 0.7$.

4.2 Sample Selection

Our sample is drawn from Mapping Nearby Galaxies at Apache Point Observatory (Bundy et al., 2015, MaNGA) survey which was released as part of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey Data Release 14 (Abolfathi et al., 2018, SDSS DR14). This recent data release contains a sample of 2,812 MaNGA datacubes. These datacubes were analysed

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

using the Pipe3D data analysis pipeline by the MaNGA team and their final catalogue of 2,755 galaxies forms our sample, wherein we search for outlying H α emitters.

4.2.1 The MaNGA survey

MaNGA is an integral field unit (IFU) survey which aims to observe a total sample of $\sim 10,000$ nearby galaxies. The MaNGA instrument consists of 17 hexagonal shaped science IFUs mounted on the 2.5 metre Apache Point Observatory which has a 3° field of view. The IFU sizes range from 19 fibres with $12''$ on-sky diameter to 127 fibres with $32''$ on-sky diameter. Additionally, there are 12 mini-bundles with 7 fibres each which are used for spectrophotometric calibration, and 92 single fibres used for sky subtraction. The details of the MaNGA instrument are described in [Drory et al. \(2015\)](#). The MaNGA fibres are then fed to the two Baryon Oscillation Sky Survey (BOSS) spectrographs ([Smee et al., 2013](#)), each of which contain a red and a blue camera which together have a wavelength coverage from 3600 \AA to 10300 \AA and a spectral resolution, $R \sim 2000$. The integration time for each of the MaNGA targets depends on the signal to noise ratio requirement of $5 \text{ \AA}^{-1} \text{ fibre}^{-1}$ in r -band continuum at a surface brightness of $23 \text{ AB arcsec}^{-2}$ ([Law et al., 2015](#)). The raw data are then reduced using the MaNGA Data Reduction Pipeline (DRP) as described in [Law et al. \(2016\)](#), which constructs the sky subtracted and flux calibrated datacubes for each of the MaNGA galaxies. The MaNGA PSF can be well described by a single Gaussian with median spatial resolution of $\sim 2.54 \text{ arcsec FWHM}$. The median instrumental velocity resolution is 72 kms^{-1} . The typical relative flux calibration errors are 1.7% between H α and H β , and about 4.7% between [N II] $\lambda 6583$ and [O II] $\lambda 3727$ ([Yan et al., 2016](#)).

The primary MaNGA selection criteria produce a sample of roughly 10,000 galaxies which is complete above the stellar mass limit of $10^9 M_\odot$ and has a roughly flat stellar mass distribution (See [Bundy et al., 2015](#); [Wake et al., 2017](#)). More constraints are put in order to maximise spatial coverage and S/N which favours a lower redshift sample. Other constraints favour a higher redshift sample. Taking these constraints into account the MaNGA target galaxies are divided into two classes: Primary and Secondary samples. The Primary sample has a mean redshift of 0.03 and reaches 1.5 times the galaxy half-light radius (R_e) for roughly 80% of its targets. The Secondary sample has a slightly higher mean redshift of 0.045 and reaches $2.5 R_e$ for roughly

80% of its targets. Of the total target sample of $\sim 10,000$ galaxies, the data release 14 contains a sample of 2,812 reduced MaNGA datacubes.

4.2.2 PIPE3D value added catalogue

In this study, we use the MaNGA value added catalogue analysed using the PIPE3D pipeline (Sánchez et al., 2016b, 2018) which is based on FIT3D, the details of which are described in Sánchez et al. (2016a). We briefly describe the fitting algorithm here.

FIT3D follows a two level modelling of the integral field spectroscopy (IFS) data. At the first level, it models the stellar kinematics, stellar population and dust attenuation using the continuum. At this level, initially the stellar kinematics (only the velocity and dispersion) are estimated assuming a Gaussian profile¹. This is achieved by first fixing the velocity dispersion and varying the velocity from the minimum to the maximum value until a best fit velocity is found. Then the velocity is fixed to the best fit value and the velocity dispersion is varied till the best-fit value is found. Following this, the dust attenuation is varied until the best fit dust attenuation is found, while keeping the velocity and velocity dispersion fixed to their best fit values. Once the best fit value of these three parameters are found FIT3D performs the stellar population synthesis (SPS) modelling using the GSD16 stellar template library (Cid Fernandes et al., 2013). GSD16 contains a total of 156 templates with 39 stellar ages, ranging from 1 Myr to 13 Gyr, and 4 metallicities: 0.2, 0.4, 1, and 1.5 times solar metallicity. Each of these templates are shifted according to the velocity, convolved with the velocity dispersion and dust attenuated, following the dust attenuation law of Cardelli et al. (1989), using the best fit values of the individual parameters. The average properties of the stellar population (e.g., stellar mass, light/mass weighted stellar age, metallicity, mass-to-light ratio, etc.) is derived using the weights on the individual single stellar population.

The second level of FIT3D deals with the measurement of nebular emission lines. The emission line only spectrum is derived by subtracting the modeled stellar continuum obtained from the previous level. The uncertainties involved in the stellar population modelling are propagated to the emission line-only spectrum. Thereafter, around each emission line a single Gaussian and a low order polynomial is fitted. Following a similar procedure as in the previous level, the velocity, velocity dispersion and

¹FIT3D does not model higher order kinematics as it is primarily developed for lower spectral resolution ($R \lesssim 2000$) IFS.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

the intensity of each line is derived starting by first fitting for the velocity and fixing the other two parameters. This is followed by fitting for the velocity dispersion and finally for the intensity of the emission line. Furthermore, the H α emission line is corrected for dust attenuation using the Balmer decrement for every spaxel assuming a H α /H β line ratio of 2.86 and adopting a [Cardelli et al. \(1989\)](#) dust attenuation law and specific dust attenuation of R_V of 3.1.

The current data release of the PIPE3D value added catalogue¹ has provided data-products and catalogue for 2,755 galaxies in the MaNGA sample.

4.2.3 Optical Photometric data

We also use the publicly available optical g , r , and z band imaging data from the SDSS DR14, which have a 5σ depths of 23.13, 22.7 and 20.71 respectively. We also use the data release 5 of the Dark Energy Camera Legacy Survey (DECaLS) and data release 6 of the Mayall z -band Legacy Survey (MzLS) + Beijing-Arizona Sky Survey (BASS). The DECaLS survey is being carried out on the Dark Energy Camera (DECam) on the Blanco 4m telescope at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory and it will provide the optical imaging for the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) footprint. DECam with its large field of view and good sensitivity can reach a 5σ depths of 24.0, 23.4 and 22.5 in the g , r , and z band respectively. The BASS survey is being carried out on the 2.3m Bok telescope using the 90Prime camera in the g and r band, and it will reach similar 5σ depths of 24.0 and 23.4 in g and r band respectively. Similarly the MzLS survey is being carried out on the Mayall telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory using the MOSAIC-3 camera only in the z -band and will reach a 5σ depth of 23.0.

4.2.4 Selection Criteria

We identify a region of H α emission as an outlying H α emitter if the following three criteria are satisfied:

1. A signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of H α flux greater than 5 and which covers at least one MaNGA PSF which corresponds to ~ 5 spaxels.

¹<http://www.sdss.org/dr14/manga/manga-data/manga-pipe3d-value-added-catalog/>

Figure 4.1: MaNGA observation of a galaxy with MaNGA ID: manga-8601-12701. Top-left: MzLS/BASS grz [Lupton et al. \(2004\)](#) colour composite image with the MaNGA IFU extent around the galaxy shown in purple in world coordinate system (WCS). Top-right: H α flux map in logarithmic units. Bottom-left: H α velocity map. Bottom-right: Stellar velocity map of the host galaxy. The outlying H α emitters are circled in red in all the panels. Notice that the H α emitter does not have any bright optical counterpart, it also has a velocity component different from the host galaxy.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

2. No bright optical counterpart in SDSS *gri* colour composite image or in the DECaLS, MzLS/BASS *gri* colour composite image.
3. H α velocity of the emitter which is different (typically upto 400 km/s) from the velocity field of the parent galaxy and/or the H α emission is clearly extra-planar.

Under these criteria, we follow a fairly straightforward, two step approach, to visually search for such outlying H α emitters. In the first step we select galaxies which satisfy the first two criteria. To do this, we produce panels for each galaxy in the MaNGA sample having the DECaLS/MzLS-BASS colour image and the H α flux map. We visually inspect each galaxy using this panel and search for H α emitting regions which do not show any bright optical counterpart. Starting from a sample of 2,755 MaNGA galaxies released in the PIPE3D catalogue, we visually identify 133 galaxies which satisfy these two criteria.

In the second step, we inspect the H α velocity map of these shortlisted galaxies to make sure that the outlying H α emission is different from that of the host galaxy. Fig. 4.1, shows an example of an outlying H α emitter in our sample. Notice the large scale H α emission away from the optical extent (first and second panel) of the host galaxy highlighted in red ellipses. The H α velocity of the outlying emission is also different from that of the optical galaxy shown as seen from the third and fourth panels. Such a galaxy satisfies all the three selection criteria and is added in the sample of outlying H α emitting region. We visually inspect the velocity map of all the 133 shortlisted galaxies in the first step of the selection and find a final sample of 41 galaxies which satisfy all the three selection criteria.

We then individually inspect the spectrum of these outlying H α emitters and find that 35 objects are artefacts since the FWHM of the H α line is very narrow (~ 2 Å) compared to the instrumental width of the MaNGA IFU. Of them about 29 of them appear like hot-pixels in the H α image as shown in Fig. 4.2, and 6 have extended emission but a very narrow H α FWHM. Notice that Fig. 4.2, shows the outlying emission with a very high SNR (as shown in red circle) and also has a very different velocity component from the host galaxy, however after visually inspecting the spectrum it is flagged as an artefact. The full list of artefacts in the MaNGA survey is given in the Sec. 4.7, which is available in the online version of this paper. Our final sample of

Figure 4.2: MaNGA observation of a spiral galaxy with MaNGA ID: manga-8257-12703. Left panel: $H\alpha$ flux map in logarithmic units. Middle panel: $H\alpha$ logarithm of the signal to noise ratio with truncation below SNR of 5. Note that the apparent outlying $H\alpha$ emitter which satisfies all the criteria and circled red is an artefact since it has a very narrow emission line width as seen in the MaNGA datacube (not shown here). The full list of such artefacts is given in the Sec. 4.7.

outlying $H\alpha$ emitters is summarised in Table 4.3. We have also independently rediscovered the outlying $H\alpha$ emitter from Lin et al. (2017), but do not discuss it here as it has been extensively studied in their paper.

4.3 Results and Discussions

In this section, we measure the integrated emission line fluxes using aperture photometry of the outlying $H\alpha$ emitters. We then study their position on the emission line ratio diagnostic diagram of Baldwin et al. (1981). Finally, we individually describe the objects in our sample.

4.3.1 Integrated properties of outlying $H\alpha$ emitters

In this section, we study the integrated emission line fluxes of the outlying $H\alpha$ emitters from our sample. In particular, in order to know the source of ionisation we want to identify the location of these outlying $H\alpha$ emitters on the “BPT diagram” (Baldwin et al., 1981). Hence, we measure the total emission line flux in the $H\alpha$, $[\text{NII}]\lambda 6583$, $[\text{OIII}]\lambda 5007$, and the $H\beta$ lines.

We make elliptical apertures ¹ around all the extended $H\alpha$ emitters (xHAEs) to

¹The aperture photometry was performed using the photutils package <https://photutils.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.3: Final Sample of outlying H α emitters in the SDSS MaNGA.

Obj ID	RA J2000 (hhmmss)	DEC J2000 (ddmms)	plate-ifu	Host SDSS Obj ID	RA (Host) J2000 (deg)	DEC (Host) J2000 (deg)	z
X1	14:09:06.710	+53:27:55.644	8591-6101	1237661416601878596 (HX1)	14:09:06.87	+53:27:48.70	0.0785
X2.1	16:30:52.685	+41:17:22.074	8601-12701	1237655374109802661 (HX2)	16:30:53.11	+41:17:10.81	0.0936
X2.2	16:30:53.268	+41:17:04.565	8601-12701	1237655374109802661 (HX2)	16:30:53.11	+41:17:10.81	0.0936
X3	08:47:47.430	+54:01:29.807	8724-6102	1237651533336281291 (HX3)	08:47:46.76	+54:01:36.02	0.0472
X4	08:18:50.238	+22:57:14.864	8939-12701	123766108534513774 (HX4)	08:18:49.61	+22:57:16.37	0.0924
X5	11:15:47.004	+50:24:09.997	8947-3701	1237657855533056062 (HX5)	11:15:47.46	+50:24:05.75	0.0475

Notes. Column (1) gives the object ID of the outlying H α emitter, column (2) and (3) gives the RA and DEC of the outlying H α emitter respectively. Column (4) and (5) gives the MaNGA plateifu name and SDSS DR14 object ID of the host galaxy respectively. And columns (6), (7) and (8) give the RA and DEC and SDSS spectroscopic redshift of the host galaxy respectively.

estimate the total $H\alpha$ flux. We similarly construct the [NII], [OIII], [SII] λ 6717, 6731 and $H\beta$ emission line maps, and measure the total flux in each of the emission lines respectively. We also estimate the total error in the emission line flux inside the aperture by adding the error in each spaxel in quadrature. We do this for each of the four emission line maps and for all the outlying $H\alpha$ emitters in our sample. Table 4.4 shows the integrated fluxes of the individual sources in our sample. We also extracted the integrated spectrum in these apertures for each source from the MaNGA datacube which is shown in Sec. 4.6.

4.3.1.1 BPT diagram

In this section, we use the BPT diagnostic diagram to identify the source of ionisation in the outlying $H\alpha$ emitters. The BPT diagram is widely used to classify galaxies into star forming (SF), Seyferts, and low-ionisation emission line regions (LINERs) (e.g., Kauffmann et al., 2003c; Kewley et al., 2006). The BPT classification scheme is also used in resolved IFU studies (e.g., Belfiore et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2017). In our study we use the [OIII] λ 5007/ $H\beta$ vs. [NII] λ 6583 ([SII] λ 6717, 6731)/ $H\alpha$ diagram. For simplicity, we will refer to the [OIII] λ 5007, [NII] λ 6583, [SII] λ 6717, 6731 (which is the sum of the two lines) as [OIII], [NII], and [SII] respectively.

Figure 4.5 left (right) panel shows the [OIII]/ $H\beta$ vs. [NII]([SII])/ $H\alpha$ diagnostic diagram for our sample of outlying $H\alpha$ emitters. The corresponding line ratios for the host galaxies are determined using SDSS DR14 spectroscopy. In both the panels the red solid line is for the theoretical maximum starburst line from Kewley et al. (2006) which we refer as the Ke06 line hereafter. And the black dashed line in the left panel is semi-empirical line from Kauffmann et al. (2003c) which we refer to as the Ka03 line hereafter. In the [NII]/ $H\beta$ BPT diagram the source of ionisation for the region below the Ka03 line is purely from star formation. For the region above the Ke01 line the source of ionisation is from a type 2 AGN wherein it is from a Seyfert AGN if it is above the blue solid line and LINER if it is below the blue solid line (Cid Fernandes et al., 2010). For the region between the Ka03 and Ke01 lines the source of ionisation is from a mix of star formation and non-star formation, and it is termed as “composite”. Moreover, ionisation due to slow shocks has been also shown to push the points into the LINER region (Farage et al., 2010; Rich et al., 2010). In the [SII]/ $H\alpha$ BPT diagram, the region below the Ke06 line has ionisation purely due to star formation. The region

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.4: Integrated fluxes and uncertainty of H α , [OIII], [NII], H β , [SII] λ 6717, and [SII] λ 6731 emission lines for the extended outlying H α emitters.

Obj ID	F _{Hα} ($\sigma_{H\alpha}$)	F _[OIII] ($\sigma_{[OIII]}$)	F _[NII] ($\sigma_{[NII]}$)	F _{Hβ} ($\sigma_{H\beta}$)	F _{[SII]λ6717} ($\sigma_{[SII]\lambda6717}$)	F _{[SII]λ6731} ($\sigma_{[SII]\lambda6731}$)	BPT classification
X1	2.166 (0.033)	0.884 (0.053)	0.894 (0.038)	0.595 (0.048)	2.004 (0.117)	0.302 (0.113)	composite/LINER
X2.1	2.641 (0.033)	1.39 (0.044)	0.804 (0.042)	0.772 (0.037)	0.472 (0.065)	0.256 (0.072)	composite/star forming
X2.2	7.323 (0.039)	15.332 (0.098)	2.208 (0.067)	2.357 (0.053)	1.338 (0.102)	0.549 (0.092)	Seyfert
X3	2.464 (0.037)	0.778 (0.055)	0.565 (0.05)	0.594 (0.064)	1.027 (0.034)	0.368 (0.04)	star forming ¹⁰⁴
X4	4.085 (0.051)	9.535 (0.102)	5.525 (0.12)	1.603 (0.091)	3.655 (0.16)	1.672 (0.17)	Seyfert/LINER
X5	4.218 (0.055)	7.1 (0.087)	0.45 (0.065)	1.421 (0.066)	0.525 (0.056)	0.403 (0.052)	star forming/Seyfert

Notes . Column (1) gives the object ID of the outlying H α emitter. Columns (2), (3), (4), (5), (6) and (7) give the total flux and 1σ uncertainty for the H α , [OIII], [NII], H β , [SII] λ 6717 and [SII] λ 6731 line respectively. For non-detections, the fluxes are replaced by the $3\text{-}\sigma$ upper limits. All values are in units of 10^{-16} ergs s^{-1} cm^{-2} . Column (8) gives the BPT classification of the xHAFs. See Sec. 4.3.1.1 for details.

Figure 4.5: Left Panel: The $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ vs. $[\text{NII}]/\text{H}\alpha$ BPT diagnostic diagram. The red solid line is the extreme starburst line from Kewley et al. (2006, Ke06). The black dashed line is from the semi-empirical fit to the SDSS galaxies from Kauffmann et al. (2003c, Ka03). The region below the Ka03 line is termed as star-forming (SF) region. In the region above the Ke01, the blue solid line from Cid Fernandes et al. (2010) separates the Seyferts from LINERS. The region between the Ke06 and Ka03 line is termed as composite region, which has emission from both star formation and AGN. Right Panel: The $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ vs. $[\text{SII}]\lambda 6717, 6731/\text{H}\alpha$ BPT diagnostic diagram. The red dashed line is the extreme starburst line from Kewley et al. (2006, Ke06). The extended $\text{H}\alpha$ emitters are shown in orange dots. These show various sources of ionisation in their spectrum. The blue points are for the corresponding host galaxy. See the text for details.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

above the Ke06 line and above the blue line has ionisation due to Seyfert AGN and region above the Ke06 line and below the blue line has ionisation due to LINER like AGN.

In Figure 4.5, the most striking result is that of X2.2, which is classified as ionized due to a Seyfert AGN in both the diagrams. X2.1, which is at the edge of extreme starburst line in the [NII]/H α BPT diagram, has moved within the starburst line in the [SII]/H α diagram. Interestingly, the corresponding host galaxy (HX2) has a Seyfert AGN in the centre, which provides the ionising photons for X2.2, thus putting it in the Seyfert region. X1 is classified as composite and LINER in the [NII]/H α and the [SII]/H α BPT diagrams respectively. The host (HX1) also shows a corresponding LINER emission line ratio in its centre. X4 is classified as Seyfert and LINER in the [NII]/H α and the [SII]/H α BPT diagram respectively. However, peculiarly the host (HX4) does not show any nuclear activity. X5 which is classified as at the edge of extreme starburst in the [NII]/H α diagram is shifted to the Seyfert region in the [SII]/H α diagram. The host galaxy (HX5) also shows a Seyfert-like line ratios in the centre, and thus could be the source of ionisation. X3 is still consistent with being at the edge of extreme starburst line from both the BPT diagrams. The host galaxy (HX3) is devoid of any emission lines and thus does not have any nuclear activity or SF in the centre (and hence it is not shown in Figure 4.5).

Thus the extended emitters show a mix sources of ionisation ranging from star formation to composite emission. In particular X2.2 and X4 show clear signatures of Seyfert/LINER like emission line ratios. Except in the case of X4, the corresponding host galaxies have a active nuclei which could be the source of ionisation of these regions. The extended morphology and Seyfert/LINER like emission line ratios lead us to think that these objects are extended emission line regions (EELRs) e.g. the Hanny's Voorwerp (Keel et al., 2012a; Lintott et al., 2009) and similar EELRs searched by the Galaxy Zoo candidates (Keel et al., 2012b), and Unger et al. (1987) and Tadhunter & Tsvetanov (1989). We describe each of these objects in detail in the next section.

4.3.2 Comparison of H α luminosities of xHAEs with literature

Keel et al. (2012b), using the Galaxy Zoo candidates, have carried out a systematic search for extended emission line regions (EELRs) and have documented 19 objects.

A detailed study of the sources of ionisation in their EELRs shows that they are photoionised due to an AGN. The objects reported in our sample also show similar morphological features as those in the [Keel et al. \(2012b\)](#) sample and are also primarily photoionised due to an AGN. However, unlike their sample, our sample objects do not show any bright optical counterparts in deep optical images. The median values of the $H\alpha$ luminosities of our xHAEs is 4.47×10^{39} ergs/s. This is about 4.5 times fainter than the median $H\alpha$ luminosity of the [Keel et al. \(2012b\)](#) sample (2×10^{40} ergs/s). Thus, using our selection method with MaNGA data we are able to detect fainter counterparts of Hanny’s Voorwerp like objects.

In conclusion, we find that the xHAEs have ionisation due to various kinds of sources ranging from Seyfert AGN, star formation and also a mixture of both. Moreover, their $H\alpha$ luminosities show that they are fainter counterparts of the EELRs.

4.4 Remarks on individual sources

In this section we will briefly describe the xHAEs in our sample .

1. X1 (host SDSS objID: 1237661416601878596): As shown in the $H\alpha$ image in [Figure 4.6](#), there is an extended outlying $H\alpha$ emission (highlighted with a red ellipse and referred to as X1). The host galaxy, which has an elliptical morphology ([Graham et al., 2018](#), G18 hereafter), does not show any features of interaction in its light profile both at the location of the $H\alpha$ emission and elsewhere. The $H\alpha$ velocity map of the galaxy on the contrary shows very disturbed features. There appears to be some kind of rotation along the northeast-southwest diagonal axis, with the gas in the northeast direction moving away from us and the gas along the southwest direction coming towards us. The outlying $H\alpha$ emission on the other hand has a different velocity from this, and is coming towards us with an velocity of about 100 km/s. Moreover, the stellar velocity shown in the last panel is completely misaligned from the velocity flow of the $H\alpha$ emission. Such an misalignment is a signature of recent gas rich merger. X1 has a composite/LINER emission line ratios from the BPT diagram (see [Table 4.4](#)), and the host galaxy is classified has LINER like emission line ratios in the centre. This could be an example of Hanny’s Voorwerp like object. However, unlike Hanny’s Voorwerp

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.6: Top-left panel: Shows the DECALs or MzLS-BASS *grz* Lupton et al. (2004) colour composite image of the host galaxies with the MaNGA IFU extent in purple. Top-right panel, bottom-left and bottom-right panel shows the H α emission map, H α velocity map and stellar velocity map respectively for X1 in physical units in kpcs. In each panel the red ellipse highlights the location of the xHAEs. See text for details.

4.4 Remarks on individual sources

Figure 4.7: Continued. Here we show the outlying emission for X3.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.8: Continued. Here we show the outlying emission for X4.

Figure 4.9: Continued. Here we show the outlying emission for X5.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

X1 has no detectable optical counterpart and hence this object is likely a fainter counterpart of the Voorwerp.

2. X2.1 & X2.2 (host SDSS objID: 1237655374109802660): In Fig. 4.1, both X2.1 and X2.2 have emission coming from a merging system of two galaxies (G18). Here we identify the host galaxy not with the galaxy on which the MaNGA IFU is centered (ObjID: 1237655374109802660), but rather with the galaxy adjacent to it (ObjID: 1237655374109802661), due to the continuity of the H α emission with it. X2.1 has a velocity very near the velocity of the host galaxy and could be a case of extraplanar gas. This merger is caught in the MaNGA IFU field of view. The IFU is centred around the galaxy 8601-12701. X2.1 is at the edge of composite/star forming region, and X2.2 has Seyfert emission line ratios. The host galaxy (HX2) also has Seyfert AGN in the centre. It is intriguing to see that both X2.1 and X2.2 emitting regions which are on opposite sides of the host galaxy show a connected bridge. Moreover, the velocity map shows a gradient as we go along the connecting bridge around the host galaxy. Both X2.1 and X2.2 are examples of fainter counterparts of Hanny's Voorwerp.
3. X3 (host SDSS objID: 1237651533336281291, see Figure 4.7): The host galaxy has an elliptical morphology (G18) with no clear indication of recent merger/integration in its light profile. The host galaxy of X3 is however, devoid of any emission lines and thus does not have an active nucleus. Interestingly, X3 is a large star forming region, however it has a velocity which is very different (about 400 km/s) from the disc as seen in the stellar velocity profile (due to poor H α SNR of the host galaxy the velocity map is not visible). It is possible that this galaxy may have undergone a recent merger with a galaxy which may have left a tidal tail or there has been a recent event of gas accretion as in the case of [Cheung et al. \(2016\)](#). Given that there is such a high velocity difference, it is also possible that the H α emission is not associated with HX3, and is rather associated with a neighbouring galaxy (SDSS ObjID: 1237651252560461948), which is about 570 km/s offset from it, which also has an active nucleus. Thus, a past interaction with HX3 may have left a tidal tail, which is being photoionised by the neighbouring galaxy.

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4. X4 (host SDSS objID: 1237661085345513774, see Figure 4.8): The host galaxy is a spiral galaxy with a close companion nearby (G18) and has a LINER/composite emission line ratios. It is possibly interacting with another early type galaxy. X4 has Seyfert/LINER like emission line ratio. The $H\alpha$ gas and stellar rotation is in the same direction although there is an misalignment between the two. X4 is also an example of Hanny’s Voorwerp like object.
 5. X5 (host SDSS objID: 1237657855533056062, see Figure 4.9): X5, like X2.1 and X2.2, also shows a continuity with the host galaxy. The host of X5 is an S0 galaxy (G18) which has a Seyfert AGN in the centre. Interestingly, X5 is at the edge of the star forming/Seyfert region. The $H\alpha$ velocity map shows that the gas has very different velocity from the host galaxy and is moving away from the galaxy with a velocity of at least 300 km/s, which is fairly large. However, given the continuity in the $H\alpha$ emission with the host galaxy we believe that it is associated with it. It is possible that this is a event of outflowing gas due to AGN feedback, and this gas is undergoing in-situ star formation. [Maiolino et al. \(2017\)](#) have recently observed such an event of in-situ star formation in galactic outflows at a redshift of 0.0448. Intriguingly, the $H\alpha$ velocity map shows a gradient, and thus there are likely multiple velocity components in the emission region. This feature is also seen in the integrated spectrum shown in the Sec. 4.6 (Figure 4.15), where we see two velocity components in the spectrum.

4.5 Summary and Future Work

In summary, we have conducted a systematic search for outlying $H\alpha$ emitters in the entire PIPE3D value added catalogue of the recently released DR14 SDSS IV MaNGA survey of 2,755 galaxies. We have found six outlying extended $H\alpha$ emitters (xHAEs) which have strong $H\alpha$ emission away from the host galaxy and without any bright optical continuum counterpart in the deeper optical images from the DECaLS or MzLS/BASS survey. These $H\alpha$ emitters also show a $H\alpha$ velocity component which is different from that of the host galaxy, ranging from about 150-400 km/s. We have also found several artefacts in the MaNGA datacubes most of which appear unresolved sources in the $H\alpha$ maps. However, their $H\alpha$ line-widths are much narrower than the instrumental width of the MaNGA IFU. These are likely to be spurious cosmic rays which were not

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

flagged by the MaNGA data reduction pipeline. The integrated line flux ratios show of the six xHAEs shows various kinds of sources of photoionisation. Three of the xHAEs show photoionisation due to an AGN, two of them have composite emission line ratio and one of them have photoionisation due to star formation. These xHAEs have H α luminosities at the lower end of the previously known EELRs and are thus their fainter counterparts.

Due to the poor spatial resolution of the MaNGA IFU it is very difficult to study the emission line regions with more detail, in particular since it can blend emission lines from two different, but spatially nearby, sources of ionisation into a single line. To address this limitation, we intend to follow-up these objects in our sample with a higher spatial resolution IFU e.g., SITELLE (Spectromètre Imageur à Transformée de Fourier pour l'Etude en Long et en Large de raies d'Emission) on the Canada-France-Hawaii-Telescope (CFHT). This will also give us a larger field of view which can capture more emission line regions which are missed in the narrow field of view of MaNGA. Along with these new IFU observations, we also hope to obtain deep optical images to locate the optical counterparts of the H α emitters in our sample.

4.6 Integrated spectrum of each of the sources in our sample

We used elliptical apertures around the extended emitters to extract the integrated spectrum for each of the sources in our sample, directly from the MaNGA datacube. The integrated spectra are shown in Figure 4.10-4.15. We also show the host galaxy spectrum from the SDSS DR14 spectroscopic survey for reference in the bottom-most panel of each of figure.

4.7 List of artefacts found in the MaNGA datacube

In our visual search for outlying H α emitters in the entire data release 14 of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) IV MaNGA data release, we have found the following list of objects which are found to be artefacts. These artefacts are of two kinds: ones that appear like unresolved blobs (see Table 4.17) and ones that appear like extended sources. All the unresolved blobs appear like high signal-noise ratio emitters, with

4.7 List of artefacts found in the MaNGA datacube

Figure 4.10: Top: Integrated spectrum for X1. The grey shaded regions indicate regions with strong sky lines in the SDSS spectrum. Middle: A zoomed-in spectrum around the [OII] doublet (left), [OIII] λ 4960, 4963, and 5007 and H β (middle), and H α and the [NII] doublet (right). Bottom: Observed frame host galaxy spectrum from the SDSS DR14 spectroscopic survey.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.11: Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X2.1 and its corresponding host galaxy.

4.7 List of artefacts found in the MaNGA datacube

Figure 4.12: Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X2.2 and its corresponding host galaxy.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.13: Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X3 and its corresponding host galaxy.

4.7 List of artefacts found in the MaNGA datacube

Figure 4.14: Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X4 and its corresponding host galaxy.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.15: Continued. Here we show the integrated spectrum for X5 and its corresponding host galaxy.

4.7 List of artefacts found in the MaNGA datacube

a different velocity component (see Fig. 4.2 in the main text). However, a manual inspection of their spectra shows that their $H\alpha$ FWHM is much narrower than the instrumental width. Additionally, they do not show line emission in other lines like $H\beta$, [OIII], [NII] which usually accompany strong $H\alpha$ emission. We believe that these artefacts are caused by some spurious low-intensity cosmic rays which are not correctly flagged by the MaNGA data reduction pipeline¹.

The extended emitters shows two types of artefacts, the first type is same as that of the unresolved blobs, which show a very narrow line width, the second kind show a strong $H\alpha$ emission in the PIPE3D output, however there is no emission line in the MaNGA datacube. Moreover, the integrated $H\alpha/H\beta$ emission line ratio is unrealistically higher than expected by any realistic assumptions about the nebular regions. We surmise that such artefacts could be due to incorrect fitting in the PIPE3D pipeline. See Table 4.18 for the full list.

¹<https://www.sdss.org/dr14/manga/manga-caveats/>

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.16: List of artefacts in the MANGA datacube which appear like unresolved blobs.

Obj ID	RA J2000 (hhmmss)	DEC J2000 (ddmms)	plateifu	Host SDSS Obj ID	RA (Host) J2000 (deg)	DEC (Host) J2000 (deg)	z
B1	15:28:03.533	+42:48:41.535	7443-9102	1237662501076336774	15:28:03.32	+42:48:49.11	0.0918
B2	03:12:46.534	-01:01:16.964	8081-12701	1237666299480899906	03:12:47.18	-01:01:22.27	0.0818
B3	03:44:31.591	+00:00:14.240	8086-12704	1237663238741622872	03:44:31.59	+00:00:23.94	0.1087
B4	07:30:40.578	+40:11:37.756	8131-6103	1237663530789503529	07:30:40.96	+40:11:30.39	0.1204
B5	08:00:28.325	+41:39:46.527	8143-6103	1237673705042935885	08:00:27.99	+41:39:38.32	0.0438
B6	07:51:14.337	+28:09:05.193	8146-9102	1237657630579163404	07:51:14.77	+28:09:13.01	0.0526
B7	07:58:25.691	+27:09:44.698	8149-12702	1237657773924417752	07:58:26.21	+27:09:41.50	0.0473
B8	07:49:38.378	+48:30:53.394	8239-9102	1237663786879942876	07:49:37.25	+48:30:56.46	0.0229
B9	09:07:18.893	+41:23:18.897	8247-6102	1237657775543746865	09:07:18.10	+41:23:18.33	0.0273
B10	11:08:01.255	+46:51:09.80	8257-12703	1237660636535652531	11:08:00.70	+46:51:03.66	0.0252
B11	12:00:42.109	+43:21:14.227	8259-12705	1237661968502358077	12:00:41.45	+43:21:16.47	0.1131
B12	12:17:32.214	+43:45:25.412	8262-3704	1237661871329640526	12:17:32.74	+43:45:26.50	0.0244
B13	14:20:04.917	+47:07:08.663	8326-6102	1237661957225119836	14:20:04.29	+47:07:16.82	0.07038
B14	13:58:33.421	+41:43:32.770	8332-3704	1237661850403602575	13:58:33.54	+41:43:27.00	0.0431
B15	11:31:20.193	+21:25:41.810	8338-12705	1237667734503882923	11:31:20.04	+21:25:28.85	0.1337
B16	13:46:48.895	+39:04:48.592	8447-12702	1237664296371421207	13:46:49.38	+39:05:01.32	0.0618
B17	09:49:31.512	+42:07:34.148	8459-12701	1237660637066100922	09:49:30.96	+42:07:48.99	0.0721
B18	15:55:47.193	+56:07:37.761	8481-3703	1237651539797737641	15:55:46.82	+56:07:31.92	0.0423
B19	16:00:44.508	+53:46:24.932	8481-3704	1237651538724978813	16:00:44.81	+53:46:31.93	0.1104

Notes. Column (1) gives the object ID of the outlying H α emitter, column (2) and (3) gives the RA and DEC of the outlying H α emitter respectively. Columns (4) and (5) give the MANGA plateifu name and SDSS DR14 object ID of the host galaxy respectively. And columns (6), (7) and (8) give the RA and DEC and SDSS spectroscopic redshift of the host galaxy respectively.

4.7 List of artefacts found in the MaNGA datacube

Figure 4.17: Continued

Obj ID	RA		DEC		plate-ifu	Host SDSS Obj ID	RA (Host)		DEC (Host)		z
	J2000 (hhmmss)	J2000 (ddmmss)	J2000 (hhmmss)	J2000 (ddmmss)			J2000 (deg)	J2000 (deg)	J2000 (deg)	J2000 (deg)	
B20	16:27:45.899	+44:10:29.753	8484-9101	1237655128765235356	16:27:46.29	+44:10:39.00	0.1398				
B21	15:31:17.835	+45:25:11.211	8551-12702	1237661386000826593	15:31:17.56	+45:24:59.53	0.07051				
B22	07:39:07.686	+41:23:33.537	8566-6102	1237673310428856407	07:39:07.71	+41:23:39.42	0.0986				
B23	10:22:09.520	+38:31:01.478	8568-12704	1237661137960632446	10:22:10.31	+38:31:04.17	0.0533				
B24	16:32:32.982	+39:07:39.957	8603-12701	1237659326566564084	16:32:33.73	+39:07:51.74	0.1306				
B25	21:10:15.857	+10:24:20.440	8618-12705	1237653008120610948	21:10:16.51	+10:24:31.63	0.1186				
B26	08:10:42.094	+48:55:06.267	8720-6104	1237651496296382666	08:10:42.56	+48:55:07.58	0.03864				
B27	08:52:41.457	+54:25:57.881	8724-9101	1237651192432885982	08:52:40.82	+54:26:03.09	0.0386				
B28	10:25:42.860	+36:01:31.483	8943-12704	1237662224594436134	10:25:43.87	+36:01:24.98	0.0546				
B29	14:48:51.586	+30:33:43.129	9002-12701	1237662696493547575	14:48:50.84	+30:33:51.74	0.061				

Notes. Column (1) gives the object ID of the outlying H α emitter, column (2) and (3) gives the RA and DEC of the outlying H α emitter respectively. Columns (4) and (5) give the MaNGA plateifu name and SDSS DR14 object ID of the host galaxy respectively. And columns (6), (7) and (8) give the RA and DEC and SDSS spectroscopic redshift of the host galaxy respectively.

4. H α EMISSION AROUND GALAXIES IN SDSS-IV MANGA

Figure 4.18: List of artefacts in the MaNGA datacube with extended features.

Obj ID	RA J2000 (hhmmss)	DEC J2000 (ddmmss)	plate-ifu	Host SDSS Obj ID	RA (Host) J2000 (deg)	DEC (Host) J2000 (deg)	z
X6 ^a	08:20:52.800	+18:01:04.896	8241-12702	1237667142860407201	08:20:52.48	+18:00:55.96	0.0441
X7 ^b	10:28:15.339	+42:58:07.480	8253-12701	1237660634384761005	10:28:14.10	+42:58:05.32	0.0452
X8 ^a	23:50:35.753	-1:07:52.374	8655-12705	1237663275779227768	23:50:36.42	-01:07:40.97	0.0456
X9 ^a	07:46:03.970	+39:53:23.003	8713-12702	1237651192424890568	07:46:04.58	+39:53:11.06	0.0418
X10 ^b	12:59:12.968	+27:46:32.067	8931-6103	1237667323797700611	12:59:13.49	+27:46:28.53	0.0231
X11 ^a	15:29:43.233	+27:06:47.309	9042-12701	1237662697034613032	15:29:44.01	+27:06:43.18	0.0457

Notes. Column (1) gives the object ID of the outlying H α emitter where X#^a represents artefact due to the PIPE3D pipeline and X#^b represents artefact due to a spurious cosmic ray, column (2) and (3) gives the RA and DEC of the outlying H α emitter respectively. Column (4) and (5) gives the MaNGA plateifu name and SDSS DR14 object ID of the host galaxy respectively. And column (6), (7) and (8) gives the RA and DEC and SDSS spectroscopic redshift of the host galaxy respectively.

5

Discovery of a large HI ring around the quiescent galaxy AGC 203001

This chapter is based on [Bait et al. \(2019a\)](#).

5.1 Introduction

Ring galaxies have been studied in the optical for a long time, starting from the now famous “Cartwheel” ring ([Zwicky, 1941](#)). This ring harbours a wide range of features like a bright blue ring, spokes, an inner secondary ring and a nucleus. The first breakthrough in understanding their origin came from [Lynds & Toomre \(1976\)](#) and [Theys & Spiegel \(1977\)](#) who showed that such rings could form due to a density wave from a head-on high speed collision with an intruder galaxy. Such rings, which are classified as P-type rings (also termed as collisional rings), typically have an off-centre nucleus and a knotty structure ([Few & Madore, 1986](#)). They differ from another class of ring galaxies, termed as O-type rings, which have a central nucleus and a smooth profile ([Few & Madore \(1986\)](#)) and are believed to have formed due to Lindblad resonances ([Binney & Tremaine, 2008](#); [de Vaucouleurs, 1959](#)). The strong impact in collisional rings leads to a burst of star formation (SF) in the whole system ([Appleton & Struck-Marcell, 1987](#); [Struck-Marcell & Appleton, 1987](#)). It was shown in a recent simulation of a Cartwheel-like galaxy, that the location of active SF follows a particular sequence,

5. DISCOVERY OF A LARGE HI RING AROUND THE QUIESCENT GALAXY AGC 203001

wherein SF is first enhanced in the ring shortly after the interaction, then in the spokes and finally in the nucleus (Renaud et al., 2018). Collisional rings are also known to form knots due to their self-gravity, a phenomenon known as “bead instability” (Dyson, 1893), as first pointed out by Theys & Spiegel (1977) and also seen in a more detailed simulation by Hernquist & Weil (1993). This leads to the fragmentation of the ring in about 100 Myr (Theys & Spiegel, 1977) and it fades almost completely in about 0.5 Gyr (Mapelli et al., 2008) thus making the ring fairly short-lived. Interestingly, such collisional rings are also produced in large scale cosmological simulations whose SF properties are found to be consistent with observations (Elagali et al., 2018; Snyder et al., 2015).

Almost all of the previously known ring galaxies were initially found in the optical and were later studied at multiple wavelengths. Only one case of an optically devoid HI ring is known at present – the ‘Leo ring’ (Schneider, 1985; Schneider et al., 1983, 1989). Here the HI is distributed in the form of a spectacularly large and clumpy ring of about 200 kpc diameter around the early-type galaxy (ETG) pair NGC 3384 and M105, and has no obvious ultra-violet (UV)/optical counterpart. It was thus long thought to have a primordial origin (Schneider, 1985; Schneider et al., 1983, 1989). However, recent observations found UV (Thilker et al., 2009), optical (Michel-Dansac et al., 2010), weak dust emission (Bot et al., 2009) and also metal-line absorption in the ring (Rosenberg et al., 2014). The metallicity of the Leo ring was found to be pre-enriched (Michel-Dansac et al., 2010; Rosenberg et al., 2014) suggesting a galactic origin. Targeted simulations further showed that it could also have a collisional origin (Michel-Dansac et al., 2010). An alternative scenario for the formation of such massive, HI clouds devoid of optical emission is the stripping of a gas-rich low surface brightness (LSB) galaxy with an extended HI disc by the tidal field of galaxy groups (Bekki et al., 2005).

In this chapter, we report the discovery of a large (~ 115 kpc in diameter) HI ring off-centered around a massive quenched galaxy, AGC 203001 using the Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT). We also present deep optical g , r , and i band imaging of the HI ring using the Canada France Hawaii Telescope (CFHT). In the context of this discovery, we discuss possible formation mechanisms for large HI rings.

Throughout this chapter, we use the standard concordance cosmology from WMAP9 (Hinshaw et al., 2013) with $\Omega_M = 0.286$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.714$ and $h_{100} = 0.69$.

5.2 Target selection

Our target, AGC 203001 belongs to a sample of quenched galaxies selected in the following manner. We first select galaxies with specific star formation rate (star formation rate/stellar mass) below 10^{-11} yr^{-1} from the Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX)–Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS)–Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE) Legacy Catalog (GSWLC; Salim et al., 2016). Such galaxies are designated as quenched galaxies (Salim, 2014). Subsequently, we put a redshift cut of $z < 0.025$ on this sample to ensure sufficient spatial resolution with the GMRT and then we cross-match this sample with the optical counterparts identified from the single dish Arecibo Legacy Fast ALFA (ALFALFA; Haynes et al., 2018) HI survey. This resulted in a sample of 24 galaxies, of which 12 galaxies had early-type morphology and showed no signs of recent star-formation or interactions. From these, AGC203001 was picked at random as a pilot object for observing the full sample with the GMRT. AGC 203001 is at a redshift of 0.01867 ($v_{\text{helio}} = 5597 \text{ km/s}$), has a stellar mass (M_*) of $1.5 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ (Salim et al., 2016) and a S0 morphology (Nair & Abraham, 2010b). It has a SF rate (SFR) of $0.011 M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$ which is very low for its stellar mass, and hence the galaxy is considered quenched. Yet, it has copious amounts of HI ($\log(M/M_{\odot}) = 9.53 \pm 0.05$) as measured by the single dish ALFALFA survey.

5.3 Observations and data analysis

5.3.1 Deep HI imaging of AGC 203001

The GMRT 21 cm line observations of AGC 203001 were carried out on 23rd and 24th December 2017 for a total on-source time of ~ 10 hours with the GMRT software backend. The total bandwidth was configured at 16.66 MHz divided into 512 channels, thus corresponding to a velocity resolution of $\sim 7 \text{ km/s}$, and centered at the heliocentric redshift of AGC 203001. The data analysis was carried out using standard tasks in the Astronomical Imaging Processing System (AIPS ; Wells, 1985) package. The initial flagging and calibration was done manually. Then a continuum image was made from the line free channels which was used for self-calibration. After applying the self-calibration solution to the line visibilities, the continuum emission was subtracted using the task UVSUB. The cube was then imaged using the task IMAGR, and residual

5. DISCOVERY OF A LARGE HI RING AROUND THE QUIESCENT GALAXY AGC 203001

Table 5.1: Positions and magnitudes of optical counterparts to the ring

ObjID	RA J2000 (deg)	Dec J2000 (deg)	g (mag)	r (mag)	i (mag)
OC1	155.52844	13.80845	23.65 ± 0.18	23.04 ± 0.15	–
OC2	155.53990	13.79961	24.81 ± 0.40	–	–
OC3	155.54692	13.78085	25.65 ± 0.91	–	–
OC4	155.53694	13.76658	23.33 ± 0.12	23.26 ± 0.17	22.98 ± 0.28
OC5	155.53220	13.75176	23.51 ± 0.14	23.21 ± 0.13	–

continuum was subtracted out using the task IMLIN. We reach a noise level of ~ 0.67 mJy/beam for a velocity resolution of 14 km/s and with a beam size of $38.02'' \times 35.24''$. The HI integrated intensity image and velocity field were made using the task MOMNT.

5.3.2 Deep optical imaging of the HI ring

On the publicly available images from optical imaging surveys such as DeCALs or PanSTARRS, the HI ring does not show any obvious optical counterpart. To check whether faint emission could nevertheless be associated, we have obtained deep multi-band optical images of the field around AGC 203001 with the MegaCam camera installed on the Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope. The observation and data-reduction procedure which is optimised for the detection of low-surface brightness structures was the same as that used for the MATLAS/Atlas3D survey (Duc et al., 2015). Final images were obtained with the Elixir-LSB software combining 7 individual images acquired with relative offsets up to 20 arcmin, from which a master sky had been subtracted. Total exposure times were 34 min in the g' and r' bands, and 25 min in the i^* band. Weather conditions were photometric.

5.4 The HI ring around AGC 203001

We find that the HI in this galaxy is distributed in the form of a large ring around it, with a diameter of ~ 115 kpc, as shown in blue contours in Fig. 5.1, with the optical g , r , and i -band colour composite image from CFHT in the background. Notice that the ring is asymmetrically distributed around the host galaxy. Fig. 5.2 shows the HI

Figure 5.1: The HI ring around AGC 203001 in blue contours overlaid on the CFHT optical g , r , i -band color composite image. The lowest contour corresponds to a HI column density of $2.8 \times 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and subsequent contours rise in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The HI ring has a projected diameter of ~ 115 kpc. The arrows show the positions of the identified optical counterparts.

5. DISCOVERY OF A LARGE HI RING AROUND THE QUIESCENT GALAXY AGC 203001

Figure 5.2: The HI velocity map of the ring.

Figure 5.3: A 1.8×1.8 arcmin² zoom-in near the various optical counterparts of the ring. The HI column density contours are repeated from Fig. 5.1.

5. DISCOVERY OF A LARGE HI RING AROUND THE QUIESCENT GALAXY AGC 203001

velocity map of the ring, where we see that the ring is clearly rotating around AGC 203001.

There is no diffuse stellar emission along the HI ring in the CFHT Megacam image going down to a depth of ~ 28 mag/arcsec². However, we find several rather blue compact optical counterparts (OCs) close to several high column density HI condensations of the ring as denoted in Fig. 5.1. In Fig. 5.3 we show a zoom-in of the five OCs. We obtained their magnitudes using aperture photometry in IRAF. The magnitudes were then measured using circular apertures for all the OCs with a size of ~ 3 times the FWHM using the PHOT task in the IRAF APPHOT. The background was determined by making an annulus around the OCs. Table 5.1 summarises the positions and magnitudes of all the OCs of the ring. Note that in the i-band for all the OCs except for OC4 and in the r-band for OC2 and OC3 we could not get a reliable measure of the magnitude due to poor SNR. The $g - r$ colours of the OCs range from about 0.1 to 0.6 mag and are thus consistent with star-formation.

Fig. 5.4 shows the larger field of view of the HI image of the ring and the galaxies around it. Here galaxies denoted by G2, G4 and G1 (AGC 203001) are classified to be part of the same group based on the friends-of-friend group-finding technique (Tempel et al., 2014). HI is detected in G2, a known member of the group. Additionally, we also detect G3 in HI. G3 is a dwarf galaxy which does not have spectroscopic data in the SDSS DR 14 (Abolfathi et al., 2018). From our HI detection we get a systemic velocity of ~ 5525 km/s. Hence, G3 is at a similar distance as AGC203001 and likely part of the group. Notice that along the north-west section of the ring we see a curved LSB feature in the g-band image which appears to be associated with the ring. However, it is slightly misaligned with the ring and is possibly Galactic cirrus emission.

5.5 Discussion

In this section we show how the HI ring in this study compares with other known HI bearing ETGs, in particular the ATLAS^{3D} galaxies (Serra et al., 2012). We then briefly mention the possible formation scenarios for such a HI dominated ring.

Figure 5.4: Large scale image of the HI ring overlaid on the CFHT g-band image shown in reversed greyscale wherein the background is shown in white and emission is shown in grey. The *gri* colour composite image is superimposed to identify the objects. The HI contours are shown in black with the contour levels repeated from Fig. 5.1. Here we show the two more sources for which we detected HI, denoted as G2 and G3. See text for more details.

5. DISCOVERY OF A LARGE HI RING AROUND THE QUIESCENT GALAXY AGC 203001

Figure 5.5: The HI gas fraction vs. NUV-r plane. The blue points represent the median values from the xGASS survey (Catinella et al., 2018). AGC 203001 is marked with a red star and the Leo ring is marked with a black point. The yellow points represent the ATLAS^{3D} galaxies and the brown points represent the HI-excess galaxies (with GASS3505 highlighted) from (Geréb et al., 2016, 2018). The names of some of the HI-rich ATLAS^{3D} galaxies, UGC09519 and NGC0680, and a ring galaxy NGC4262 are highlighted. The region within the green dashed line correspond to the green-valley from (Salim, 2014), and the region on the left and right corresponds to the SF and quenched region respectively. See text for discussion.

5.5.1 Comparison with HI observations of early-type galaxies

It is well known that ETGs can commonly host HI (e.g., [Morganti et al., 2006](#); [Oosterloo et al., 2002, 2010](#); [Serra et al., 2012](#); [van Driel & van Woerden, 1991](#)), and even more so in non-cluster ETGs ([Serra et al., 2012](#)). Here we use the HI gas fraction ($\log(M_{\text{HI}}/M_*)$) vs. NUV-r plane ([Catinella et al., 2018](#)) to see how AGC 203001 compares particularly with ATLAS^{3D} galaxies (which forms a representative sample for ETGs with HI) and other known HI bearing ETGs from the literature.

For AGC 203001 and ATLAS^{3D} galaxies the NUV magnitudes are from the revised catalogue of GALEX UV sources from [Bianchi et al. \(2017\)](#). For NGC 0770, NGC 3458 and NGC 4262 the NUV magnitudes were missing from the [Bianchi et al. \(2017\)](#) catalogue and were hence taken from the older [Gil de Paz et al. \(2007\)](#) catalogue. The NUV magnitudes are corrected for Galactic extinction following [Wyder et al. \(2007b\)](#) with $E(B - V)$ values from the [Schlegel et al. \(1998\)](#) dust maps. For ATLAS^{3D} galaxies the extinction corrected SDSS r -band magnitudes are taken the catalogue of nearby ETGs ([Dabringhausen & Fellhauer, 2016](#)). The stellar masses for the ATLAS^{3D} galaxies are also taken from [Dabringhausen & Fellhauer \(2016\)](#). The stellar mass and r -band magnitude for AGC 203001 is taken from GSWLC ([Salim et al., 2016](#)) and SDSS DR15 ([Alam et al., 2015](#)) respectively. The HI masses for the ATLAS^{3D} galaxies are from [Serra et al. \(2012\)](#). We use the HI mass for AGC 203001 from the single dish ALFALFA survey since in our GMRT observations we did not recover all the flux. [Michel-Dansac et al. \(2010\)](#) show that the Leo ring most likely formed due to a head-on collision between NGC 3384 and M 96. Hence for the Leo ring, we assume that NGC 3384 is the host galaxy and use its stellar mass and r -band magnitude from ([Dabringhausen & Fellhauer, 2016](#)) and NUV magnitude from [Bianchi et al. \(2017\)](#). Assuming a distance of 11.574 Mpc (same as that of NGC 3384) for the Leo ring, we take its HI mass to be $2.14 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$ ([Schneider et al., 1983](#)).

In Fig. 5.5, we compare AGC 203001 (red star) with ATLAS^{3D} galaxies shown in yellow points on the HI gas fraction vs. NUV-r plane. For reference we show the median values from the mass-selected xGASS survey ([Catinella et al., 2018](#)). The green dashed lines differentiate the star-forming (SF), green-valley and quenched region ([Salim, 2014](#)). Most of the ATLAS^{3D} galaxies, are gas poor, particularly in the quenched region. Whereas AGC 203001 is much more gas rich and yet is in the quenched

5. DISCOVERY OF A LARGE HI RING AROUND THE QUIESCENT GALAXY AGC 203001

region (by virtue of its selection) and is rather more close to the Leo ring, UGC 09519 and NGC 0680. We also show a sample of HI-excess galaxies with very low star-formation efficiency from Geréb et al. (2016, 2018) (shown in brown), with GASS3505 highlighted. These galaxies were found to be outliers on the gas fraction vs. $NUV - r$ colour and stellar mass surface density. Compared to AGC 203001, these galaxies are much more gas rich and are relatively more star-forming. We also highlight NGC 4262 (which is also part of the ATLAS^{3D} sample), a typical example of a barred lenticular galaxy with a polar-ring (Krumm et al., 1985). In this case, the HI ring shows much more vigorous star formation in the form of multiple star-forming knots (Bettoni et al., 2010).

One of the galaxy, NGC 0680 which is as HI rich as AGC 203001 is an interacting galaxy with an unsettled disc and thus has a very different morphology compared to AGC 203001 (Serra et al., 2012). The other galaxy, UGC 09519, is classified to have a large HI disc/ring morphology (Serra et al., 2012). However, HI disc/ring extends well within the optical extent of galaxy which is also very different from AGC 203001. Moreover, in the relatively deeper Mayall z -band Legacy Survey/Beijing-Arizona Sky Survey (MzLS/BASS) images (Dey et al., 2019) it clearly shows a diffuse optical ring unlike in AGC 203001. The Leo ring is also an outlier in this gas scaling relation (similar to AGC 203001) and also has a quenched host galaxy (even if we assume the host to be NGC 3379). More importantly, its HI morphology in the form of a large off-centered ring with no bright optical counterpart most closely resembles that of AGC 203001.

Thus the HI ring around AGC 203001 is not like a typical ATLAS^{3D} galaxy, and is rather more similar to the rare Leo ring, in terms of its HI morphology, optical properties, gas content and star-formation activity of the host galaxy.

5.5.2 Possible formation scenarios for the ring around AGC 203001

The off-center nucleus of the HI ring makes it a P-type ring based on the classification by Few & Madore (1986). These types of rings are thought to have a collisional origin with an intruder galaxy which is typically within two diameters of the ring. We identify a nearby galaxy (G2) at a projected distance of ~ 109 kpc, which could be the possible intruder. A recent collision between G2 and the host galaxy at a relatively high speed could have triggered the formation of this ring. We also see asymmetrical

outer isophotes in the optical image of the host galaxy which could be the signs of such an interaction. We note, however, that both the stellar and HI components of G2 do not show any signs of recent interaction.

In some aspects, our ring is strikingly different from typical collisional ring galaxies. It lacks any bright optical counterpart suggesting almost negligible amounts of past and current events of SF. The high SFRs in the more traditional rings are due to gas compression after the collision. In a recent simulation of Cartwheel-like ring galaxies it was shown that SF first takes place in the expanding ring, soon after the collision, due to the induced density wave (Renaud et al., 2018). However, the HI gas column density in our ring is much below the SF threshold (of $\sim 10^{21}$ cm⁻²), thus suggesting that the gas may not have been sufficiently compressed after the collision to induce star formation. Very locally, the gas density was high enough though to allow the onset of limited star-formation, indicated by the presence of the blue OCs.

We propose a possible explanation and alternative scenarios for our observations as follows. It is possible that the host galaxy was a HI -rich ETG, like those of the ATLAS^{3D} galaxies (Serra et al., 2012), which have low column density HI gas disc to begin with and hence low SF, which underwent a collision to form the ring. This can explain the low SFR in the host galaxy and the ring. Another natural solution for all the discrepancies is that the possible collision of the gas between the intruder and AGC 203001, may have imparted a strong shock which can heat the gas in the host to very high temperatures a possibility pointed out by Appleton & Struck-Marcell (1996). Such a heating of the gas may have prevented SF in the ring, leading to a more diffuse HI ring. The inclusion of such a shock heating in collisional ring galaxy simulations, an effect largely ignored until now, may provide extra parameter space to produce such a large and optically devoid HI ring. Alternatively, as suggested by simulations in Bekki et al. (2005), such a ring-like structure could have formed due to tidal stripping of the outer-gas from a LSB galaxy having an extended HI disc by the group potential. In their simulations, the HI gas column density is expected to be quite low and it lacks any SF which is consistent with our observations of the HI ring.

5. DISCOVERY OF A LARGE HI RING AROUND THE QUIESCENT GALAXY AGC 203001

5.6 Conclusion & Future Work

In conclusion, we have discovered an extremely rare example of a HI ring, extending almost seven times the optical size of the host galaxy, AGC 203001. Our deep g , r , and i -band images show that this ring has several faint optical counterpart at surface brightness levels of ~ 28 mag/arcsec². The origin of such HI-dominated rings is still poorly understood. Conventionally, ring galaxies are thought to have a collisional origin, although they also predict large amounts of SF in it, which is contrary to our observations.

The selection criteria used to find AGC 203001 can be followed to construct a larger sample of such objects. Following which we found a total of nine more such galaxies which had similar HI gas fractions in the ALFALFA survey as AGC 203001 yet have absolutely no signs of star formation both from the NUV - r colour selection criteria and from the optical emission lines. All the galaxies also had an early-type morphology similar to AGC 203001. We also do not find any bright companions in the ALFALFA beam which could be the source of HI. These nine galaxies are being observed in the current cycle (Cycle 36) of uGMRT. After a uGMRT study we hope to follow up these objects with the CFHT to obtain their deep optical images.

Author contributions

The GMRT observing proposal was led by Omkar Bait (OB), Sushma Kurapati and Peter Kamphuis. The CFHT observing proposal was led by OB and Pierre-Alain Duc. The GMRT data was reduced by OB and Sushma Kurapati. OB would also like to acknowledge Nissim Kanekar for help with self-calibration of the data. The optical data was reduced by Jean-Charles Cuillandre. All coauthors provided input on the manuscript.

6

Summary of the thesis and Future Work

In this thesis, I carried out a multi-wavelength study on various aspects of star formation both within galaxies and in their outskirts. In the first part of the thesis, we focused on two opposite ends of the stellar mass function. We studied which parameter strongly drives galaxy evolution for massive galaxies. And we investigated if the standard star formation calibrators work for the extremely low mass, young and starbursting galaxies. In the second part of the thesis we studied two peculiar cases of large amounts of star-formation, and ionized and neutral gas in the galaxy outskirts.

In each of the four research projects described in this thesis, I have summarized and mentioned possibilities for future work, in the respective chapters. In this overall summary, I describe some of the key results from this thesis and my plans for future work:

- For massive galaxies in the local Universe, the morphology is most strongly correlated with the star-forming state, independent of the environment. There is a smooth transition in morphologies as galaxies undergo quenching. The green valley is dominated by ETS (Sa-Sbc) and S0s with possibly a morphological transformation happening between them. We also find an interesting population of star-forming S0s which are present in all environments. A small fraction of spirals are also quenched. Using partial correlation coefficients, we show that morphology is the strongest indicator of sSFR independent of the environment. In the future, we hope to follow up this work by replacing the visual morphologies

6. SUMMARY OF THE THESIS AND FUTURE WORK

with stellar angular momentum which is a more physically motivated measure of the morphology.

- We have studied very low mass starbursting galaxies termed as blueberry galaxies, which are the local analogues of high- z galaxies. A comparison between the radio and $H\alpha$ based SFR shows that the radio emission is highly suppressed and is possibly dominated by thermal emission. We find such a suppression even when we compare with the UV+24 μ m based SFR. However, there is no consensus between the different SFR calibrators. In the future a detailed modelling of their star formation histories can help in estimating their “true” SFRs. We also plan to take more data in different radio frequencies to do a detailed spectral modelling in order to directly estimate the thermal fraction in these galaxies.
- The presence of large amounts of ionized gas is not restricted within galaxies, rather in a few rare cases there can be large amounts of ionized gas in galaxy outskirts. These could be possible cases of Hanny’s Voorwerp like systems. We hope to search for more such objects in the upcoming MaNGA data release which will increase our search sample by a factor of two. We hope to obtain deeper IFU spectra for these outlying ionized gas regions using which we can carry out a detailed photo-ionization modelling.
- In very rare cases, there can even be large amounts of neutral gas surrounding early-type galaxies in the form of large rings, which are devoid of any obvious optical counterparts. We have identified nine more such HI-rich ETGs which are currently being observed with the uGMRT. We also hope to do a detailed targeted simulation to better understand the formation of such rare HI rings.

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